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USE OF RESIDUE CONTAINING RAW MILK AS FEED
*- Risk assessment on antimicrobial drug residues
and hazard identification of pathogens*

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antimicrobial drug residues and
hazard identification of pathogens*

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Tekijät	Ulla Karlström, Lasse Nuotio, Laura London, Riitta Majjala
Julkaisun nimi	Jäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon rehukäyttö - Riskinarviointi mikrobilääkejäämistä ja patogeenivaarojen tunnistaminen
Tiivistelmä	<p>Meijereiden omavalvonnassa hylätään vuosittain mikrobilääkejäämäepäilyjen vuoksi noin puoli miljoonaa litraa raakamaitoa Suomessa. Tätä maitoa ei käytetä elintarvikkeeksi vaan se toimitetaan tavallisesti eläinten rehuksi. Sivutuoteasetuksen (1774/2002) raakamaidolle asettamien käsittelyvaatimusten vuoksi on Eläinlääkintä- ja elintarviketutkimuslaitoksessa (EELA) tehty Maa- ja metsätalousministeriön (MMM) pyynnöstä vuosien 2003–2004 aikana riskinarviointi mikrobilääkejäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon rehukäytöstä. Työ on tehty yhteistyössä Elintarvikeviraston (EVI) ja Kasvintuotannon tarkastuskeskuksen (KTTK) kanssa.</p> <p>Rehussa, joka sisältää mikrobilääkejäämäepäilyn vuoksi hylättyä raakamaitoa, voi olla mikrobilääkejäämiä ja taudinaiheuttajia, jotka voivat aiheuttaa terveydellistä vaaraa rehua syöville eläimille (ja siten myös välillisesti kuluttajille). Tämä raportti keskittyy meijereillä jäämätestauksessa positiiviseksi todetun raakamaidon rehukäyttöön sika- ja vasikkatiloilla. Se sisältää seuraavat osat:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Riskinarviointi mikrobilääkejäämistä: testiposiitiivisen raakamaidon rehukäytön aiheuttama riski em. rehua saaville sioille ja vasikoille. • Testimenetelmät: mikrobilääkejäämätestauksessa käytettävien menetelmien merkitys jäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon toteamisessa. • Kuumennus, hapotus ja entsyymivalmisteiden käyttö: näiden menetelmien vaikutus mikrobilääkejäämien vähentämisessä. • Patogeenivaarojen tunnistaminen: arvio siitä, mitkä Kansainvälisen eläintautijärjestön (OIE) A- ja B-listojen naudoilla esiintyvistä taudeista, sekä EU:n uuden zoonosilainsäädännön mukaisesti raportoitavista zoonooseista voivat levitä testiposiitiivisen maidon välityksellä sika- tai vasikkatiloille, ja joiden osalta varsinainen riskinarviointi voisi olla tarpeellinen.

Tässä työssä testiposiitiivisen raakamaidon rehukäyttöön liittyen ei arvioitu:

- kysymystä mikrobilääkeresistenssin kehittymisestä
- ihmisten altistumista mikrobilääkejäämille
- patogeenivaarojen aiheuttamaa riskiä
- tilannetta, jossa raakamaidon tuonti Suomeen lisääntyisi tai lääkintä- ja testauskäytäntö muuttuisi

Bentsyylipenisilliini on Suomessa yleisimmin nautojen hoidossa käytetty mikrobilääke ja kemiallisten analyysien perusteella myös yleisin testiposiitiivisen tuloksen aiheuttaja raakamaidossa. Tämän tutkimuksen tulosten perusteella todennäköisin bentsyylipenisilliinipitoisuus jäämättestatuloksen vuoksi hylättyä raakamaitoa sisältävässä rehussa oli vuosina 2002–2003 2,5 µg/litra. Lihaskojen, emakoiden ja vasikoiden keskimääräinen päivittäinen altistuminen ei siten ylittänyt bentsyylipenisilliinin toksikologista ADI-arvoa (acceptable daily intake). Myöskään muiden arviotujen mikrobilääkejäämien osalta ADI-arvojen ylitystä ei tapahtunut. ADI-arvoja, eli hyväksyttäviä päivittäisiä saantiarvoja käytetään arvioitaessa ihmisten mikrobilääkejäämille altistumisen turvallisuutta. Toksikologiset ADI-arvot määritetään eläinkokeiden perusteella käyttämällä herkintä mahdollista eläinlajia ja turvallisuusmarginaaleja. Erillisiä eläinlajikohtaisia ADI-arvoja ei ole määritetty. Siksi tässä tutkimuksessa pidettiin perusteltuna ADI-arvojen käyttämistä myös sikojen ja vasikoiden mikrobilääkejäämäarvioinnissa.

Meijerillä positiivisen jäämättestituloksen vuoksi hylättyä raakamaitoa ei kuumenteta. Kuumentamaton raakamaito voi periaatteessa välittää alkuperätilan lypsylehmissä esiintyviä taudinaiheuttajia tätä maitoa rehuna käyttäville sika- tai nautiloille. Tämän arvion perusteella mahdollinen vaara liittyi arvioiduista 38 taudista vain suolistoperäisiin kampylobakteeri-, enterohemorraaginen *Escherichia coli* (EHEC) ja *Listeria monocytogenes* -bakteereihin.

Johtopäätökset vuosien 2002 ja 2003 tilanteen perusteella:

1. Tämän tutkimuksen perusteella meijerillä positiivisen testituloksen vuoksi hylätyssä raakamaidossa ja siitä valmistetussa rehussa olevien mikrobilääkkeiden jäämät eivät aiheuta toksikologista riskiä sikojen ja vasikoiden terveydelle nykyisessä tilanteessa.
2. Kun tankkiauton sisältämä raakamaito testataan meijerillä, siinä mahdollisesti olevat mikrobilääkkeiden jäämäpitoisuudet ovat laimentumisen seurauksena niin matalia, että käytännössä jäämättestaus pystyy havaitsemaan maidosta ainoastaan ampicilliinin, bentsyylipenisilliinin, kefaleksiinin ja kloksasilliinin. Aminoglykosideja ja novobiosiinia käytetään naudoilla ainoastaan yhdistelmä-lääkkeinä bentsyylipenisilliinin ja kefaleksiinin kanssa. Vaikka jäämättesti ei havaitsekaan aminoglykosideja ja novobiosiinia meijeritestauksessa, niitä voi kuitenkin päätyä raakamaidon mukana rehuun testauksen havaitessa bentsyylipenisilliinin tai kloksasilliinin jäämiä raakamaidossa.
3. Koska kohdassa 2 mainitut mikrobilääkkeet muodostavat suurimman osan nautojen mikrobilääkekäytöstä, voidaan todeta, että meijeritestauksen avulla voidaan estää huomattava osa naudalla käytettävien mikrobilääkejäämien päätyemisestä raakamaidosta valmistettujen elintarvikkeiden kautta kuluttajille.
4. Arvion mukaan muiden kuin kohdassa 2 mainittujen mikrobilääkeainejäämien pitoisuudet ovat laimentuneet meijerille saapuessaan alle EU:n asettamien jäämien sallitun enimmäismäärän (MRL).

5. Raakamaidon kuumentaminen tai rehun hapottaminen eivät vähennä merkittävästi mikrobilääkejäämien pitoisuuksia. Sen sijaan raakamaidon käsittely β -laktamaasientsyymillä vähentää tehokkaasti bentsyylipenisilliinin ja aminopenisilliinien pitoisuuksia maidossa, mutta sillä ei ole vaikutusta muihin mikrobilääkejäämiin.
6. Mikrobilääkejäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon rehukäytöstä kuluttajille aiheutuva jäämätariski ei arvioitu tässä raportissa. Eläinten vähäisen altistumisen perusteella voidaan kuitenkin tehdä se johtopäätös, että meijerillä jäämättestauksen perusteella hylätyn raakamaidon rehukäytöstä johtuva ihmisten altistuminen sian- tai naudanlihan kautta mikrobilääkejäämille on hyvin vähäistä nykyisessä tilanteessa.
7. Raakamaidossa, joka hylätään meijerillä mikrobilääkejäämätestauksen perusteella, voivat suolistoperäiset kampylobakteeri-, enterohemorraaginen *E. coli* (EHEC) ja *L. monocytogenes* -infektiot olla mahdollisia vaaroja, joiden suhteen tarkempaa riskinarviota voi olla syytä harkita.

Avainsanat	Mikrobilääkejäämä, raakamaito, rehu, riski, patogeeni
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Beskrivning

Utgivare	Forskningsanstalten för veterinärmedicin och livsmedel, EELA
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Titel	Obehandlad mjölk som innehåller mikrobläkemedelsrester och dess användning i foder -en riskvärdering av mikrobläkemedel och identifiering av patogenfara
Referat	<p>Vid de finländska mejeriernas egenkontroll förkastas varje år ungefär en halv miljon liter obehandlad mjölk på basis av misstankar om rester av mikrobläkemedel. Denna mjölk används inte som livsmedel utan den blir vanligen djurfoder. På grund av de krav som biproduktförordningen (1774/2002) ställer på behandlingen av obehandlad mjölk har Anstalten för veterinärmedicin och livsmedel (EELA), på begäran av Jord- och skogsbruksministeriet, åren 2003-2004 gjort en värdering av riskerna med användningen av obehandlad mjölk (som innehåller rester av mikrobläkemedel) i foder. Arbetet har gjorts i samarbete med Livsmedelsverket och Kontrollcentralen för växtproduktion.</p> <p>Obehandlad mjölk, vilken förkastats på grund av misstankar om rester av mikrobläkemedel, kan innehålla mikrobläkemedel och sjukdomsalstrare. Dessa kan utgöra en hälsofara för de djur som utfodras med foder som innehåller sådan mjölk (och kan sålunda indirekt även medföra en hälsofara för konsumenterna). Denna rapport gäller obehandlad mjölk som vid mejeriernas testning har konstaterats innehålla rester och som gårdarna använder i foder för uppfödning av svin eller kalvar. Rapporten består av följande delar:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Riskvärdering avseende mikrobläkemedelsrester: en värdering av den risk som användningen av testpositiv mjölk vid utfodring av svin och kalvar utgör med avseende på mikrobläkemedelsrester. • Testmetoder: testmetodernas betydelse för konstaterandet av rester av mikrobläkemedel i obehandlad mjölk. • Upphettning, syrabehandling och användning av enzympreparat: metodernas effektivitet för att minska halterna av mikrobläkemedelsrester. • Identifiering av sjukdomsalstrare som kan anses utgöra en fara: en bedömning av vilka av de på Internationella byrån för epizootiska sjukdomars A- och B-listor förekommande nötkreaturssjukdomar, samt vilka av de zoonoser som rapporteras i enlighet med EU:s nya zoonoslagstiftning, som kan sprida sig till svin- eller kalvgårdar via testpositiv mjölk. Dessutom identifieras de sjukdomsalstrare för vilka en egentlig riskvärdering borde övervägas.

Följande frågor har inte värderats i denna rapport:

- frågan om utveckling av resistens mot mikrobläkemedel
- människors exponering för mikrobläkemedelsrester
- den risk patogener utgör
- en situation där importen av obehandlad mjölk till Finland skulle öka eller medicinerings- eller testpraxis skulle ändras

Benzylpenicillin är vanligast bland de mikrobläkemedel som används för att behandla nötkreatur i Finland. Dessutom är det enligt utförda kemiska analyser också den vanligaste orsaken till ett positivt testresultat för obehandlad mjölk. Enligt denna undersökning var den sannolikaste halten benzylpenicillin i foder innehållande obehandlad mjölk, som förkastats på grund av testresultatet, 2,5 µg/liter under åren 2002-2003. Det toxikologiska ADI-värdet (acceptable daily intake), dvs. det godtagbara dagliga intaget av benzylpenicillin för slaktsvin, suggor och kalvar överskreds inte. ADI värdena för de andra mikrobläkemedlen som bedömdes överskreds ej heller. ADI-värdena används för att bedöma säkerheten gällande människors exponering för mikrobläkemedelsrester. De toxikologiska ADI-värdena fastställs med hjälp av djurförsök på de mest känsliga djurarterna och med hjälp av säkerhetsmarginaler. Det ansågs därför i denna undersökning motiverat att använda ADI-värdena även för att bedöma mikrobläkemedelsrester hos svin och kalvar.

Obehandlad mjölk som förkastats vid mejeriet på grund av ett positivt testresultat upphettas inte. Obbehandlad mjölk som inte upphettats kan i princip överföra sjukdomsalstrare som förekommer hos ursprungsgårdens mjölkkor till de svin- eller nötgårdar som använder denna mjölk i foder. Av de 38 sjukdomsalstrare som utvärderades i denna undersökning bedömdes tarmrelaterade kampylobakterier, enterohemorragiska *Escherichia coli* (EHEC) och *Listeria monocytogenes* vara eventuella faror.

Slutsatser enligt situationen under åren 2002 och 2003:

1. Enligt denna undersökning utgör mikrobläkemedelsrester i mjölk, som i mejerierna förkastas på grund av ett positivt testresultat, och foder som framställts av denna inte i rådande förhållanden en toxikologisk risk för svins och kalvars hälsa.
2. När obehandlade mjölk testas i mejeriet är halterna av eventuella rester av mikrobläkemedel, till följd av utspädning i tankbilen, så låga att man i praktiken kan konstatera endast ampicillin, benzylpenicillin, kefalexin och kloxacillin. Aminoglykosider och novobiocin används endast i kombination med benzylpenicillin och kefalexin. Även om man med testerna inte kan upptäcka aminoglykosider och novobiocin, kan dessa hamna med obehandlad mjölk i foder när rester av benzylpenicillin eller kloxacillin konstateras.
3. De mikrobläkemedel som nämns i punkt 2 står för största delen av de mikrobläkemedel som ges nötkreatur. Därför kan det konstateras att med hjälp av mejeriernas testning kan en betydande del av resterna från de mikrobläkemedel som ges nötkreatur hindras från att nå konsumenterna via livsmedel som framställs av mjölk.
4. Enligt bedömningen har resterna av andra mikrobläkemedel än de som nämns i punkt 2 späts ut vid ankomsten till mejeriet och halterna underskrider den maximihalt som EU tillåter för rester (MRL).

5. Upphetning av den obehandlade mjölken eller syrabehandling av fodret minskar inte i någon betydande mån halterna av mikrobläkemedelsrester. Behandling av obehandlad mjölk med enzymet β -laktamas minskar däremot effektivt halterna av benzylpenicillin och aminopenicillin i mjölken, men har ingen verkan på halterna av andra mikrobläkemedelsrester.
6. Vi har inte i denna rapport värderat risken för att konsumenter exponeras för mikrobläkemedelsrester som en följd av att obehandlad mjölk innehållande rester används i foder. Man kan ändå, på grund av att exponeringsgraden för djur är så låg, dra den slutsatsen att exponeringen av människor för mikrobläkemedelsrester via svin- eller nötkött är på mycket låg nivå i den nuvarande situationen.
7. Tarmrelaterade kampylobakterier, enterohemorragiska *E. coli* (EHEC) och *L. monocytogenes* kan vara möjliga faror med test positiv obehandlad mjölk, som används i foder. En noggrannare riskvärdering beträffande dessa sjukdomsalstrare kunde övervägas.

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Name Use of residue containing raw milk as feed
-Risk assessment on antimicrobial drug residues
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Abstract

Every year, Finnish dairies reject about half a million litres of raw milk due to suspected antimicrobial drug residues discovered in their own checks. This milk cannot be used for human consumption, but is normally used as animal feed. Due to regulations on the way of handling milk by-products (1774/2002), in 2003-2004 the National Veterinary and Food Research Institute (EELA), at the request of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM), did a risk assessment on the use of raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues as feed. This work was done in cooperation with the National Food Agency (NFA) and the Plant Production Inspection Centre (KTTK).

Feed containing raw milk rejected due to the suspected presence of antimicrobial substances can contain residues and infectious agents which can be hazardous to animals which eat such feed (and hence also indirectly be hazardous to consumers). This report focuses on raw milk which tests positive for antimicrobial drug residues at the dairy, and its use as feed in pig and calf farms. It contains the following sections:

- **Risk assessment on antimicrobial drug residues:** the risks for pigs and calves eating feed which contains raw milk testing positive for antimicrobial drug residues.
- The relevance of the **testing methods** used in detecting antimicrobial drug residues in raw milk.
- **The effect of heat treatment, acidification of feed and the use of enzymes** on the reduction of antimicrobial drug residues.
- **Hazard identification of pathogens:** An assessment whether diseases on the World Organization for Animal Health's (OIE) list A and list B, as well as on the EU Council Directive of Zoonotic Diseases can spread via test-positive milk to pigs and calves, and would hence warrant further risk assessment.

In this project, we have not assessed the following issues:

- increase in antimicrobial resistance
- human exposure to antimicrobial residues
- risks caused by pathogenic hazards
- increased imports of raw milk to Finland or changes in current Finnish therapeutic and testing practices

Benzylpenicillin is the most common antimicrobial drug used to treat cattle in Finland and, based on chemical analyses, is the most common drug residue causing test-positive results in raw milk. We demonstrated that in 2002–2003, the most likely concentration of benzylpenicillin in feed containing raw milk rejected due to antimicrobial drug residues was 2.5 µg/litre. The average daily exposure of fattening pigs, sows and calves did not exceed the toxicological ADI-value (Acceptable Daily Intake) of benzylpenicillin. In addition, the ADI-values of the other antimicrobial residues assessed were not exceeded. In this study, we used ADI-values, since exposures at these levels are considered safe for humans. Toxicological ADI-values are determined on the basis of animal tests using the most sensitive animals and safety margins. However, no ADI-values have been set for different animal species. Therefore, in this risk assessment of antimicrobial drug residues we felt it was justified to use human ADI-values for pigs and calves.

Rejected test-positive milk is not heat-treated in dairy plants. Non-heat-treated raw milk can in principle spread infectious agents from the farm of origin to the pig and cattle farms using this milk as feed. We have determined that, of the 38 diseases assessed, intestinally-carried campylobacter, enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli* (EHEC) and *Listeria monocytogenes* bacteria are the possible hazards.

Conclusions based on the situation in 2002–2003

1. Antimicrobial drug residues in test-positive raw milk rejected at the dairy and feed made from this milk do not pose a toxicological health risks to pigs and calves in the current situation.
2. When raw milk from a transportation truck is tested at the dairy, possible drug residue concentrations have been diluted to the extent that in practice residue test can only detect ampicillin, benzylpenicillin, cephalixin, and cloxacillin. Aminoglycosides and novobiocin are used in cattle only in combination with benzylpenicillin and cephalixin, so even though residue test at dairies cannot detect aminoglycosides and novobiocin, they might end up in feed via raw milk testing positive for benzylpenicillin or cloxacillin residues.
3. Since the antimicrobials mentioned in point 2 constitute the majority of antimicrobials used on cattle, with the help of the dairy test it is possible to prevent a significant portion of raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues from going via prepared food stuffs to the consumer.
4. According to the assessment, concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues other than those mentioned in point 2 have, by the time they arrive at the dairy, been diluted to the point where they are under the maximum residue limits (MRL) set by the EU.
5. The heat-treatment of raw milk or the acidification of feed do not significantly decrease the concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues. On the other hand, treating raw milk with β-lactamase enzymes effectively lowers the concentrations of benzylpenicillin and aminopenicillins, but it has no effect on other antimicrobial drug residues.

6. The risks to consumers from the use of raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues as animal feed is not considered in this report. However, based on the very low exposures of animals to these residues we can conclude that the risks of human exposure to antimicrobial residues via pork or beef meat are very small in the current situation.
7. When using raw milk rejected due to a positive test for antimicrobial drug residues as feed, Intestinally-carried campylobacter, enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) and *Listeria monocytogenes* are possible hazards, which may warrant a further risk assessment.

Key words	Antimicrobial drug residues, raw milk, feed, risk, pathogen
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1 Definitions and abbreviations

Lyhenteet ja käsitteet

ADI	Ihmisille hyväksyttävä päivittäinen jäämien saantiarvo
EELA	Eläinlääkintä- ja elintarvike tutkimuslaitos
EMEA	Euroopan lääkearviointivirasto
EVI	Elintarvikevirasto
Hylätty raakamaito	Meijerin omavalvonnassa hylätty raakamaito, jota ei voida käyttää elintarvikkeena koska siinä on todettu testimikrobin kasvua estäviä aineita kuten mikrobilääkejäämiä
KTTK	Kasvintuotannon tarkastuskeskus
MMM	Maa- ja metsätalousministeriö
MRL	EU:n asettama jäämien sallittu enimmäismäärä
OIE	Kansainvälinen eläintautijärjestö
OVR	Sikojen liemiruokinnassa käytetty ohravalkuaisrehu
T101-testi	Testimikrobin kasvua raakamaidossa inhiboivien tekijöiden kuten mikrobilääkejäämien seulontaan käytetty mikrobiologinen testi.

Abbreviations

ADI	Acceptable daily intake
EELA	National Veterinary and Food Research Institute
EMEA	European Medicines Agency
JECFA	Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives
KTTK	Plant Production Inspection Centre
MMM	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry

MRL	Maximum residue limit
NAM	National Agency for Medicines
NFA	National Food Agency
NOEL	No Observed Effect Level
NRCP	National Residue Control Program
PFB	Protein feed from barley used in liquid feeding of pigs
TOXNET	A cluster of databases on toxicology, hazardous chemicals, and related areas
USP DI	The United States Pharmacopeial Convention.
Definitions	
Bioavailability	The fraction of the antimicrobial drug entering the system. In this report used to indicate the absorbed fraction from gastrointestinal track after feeding the animal.
Farm tank	Milk tank at the farm. Raw milk is collected by dairy operators
Feed truck	Transportation truck used for the delivery of feed
Rejected milk	Milk which is not suitable for human consumption and is rejected due to inhibitory test positive results, possibly containing antimicrobial drug residues
T101-test	Microbiological test used for screening of inhibitory substances such as antimicrobial drug residues in raw milk
Test positive milk	Milk possibly containing antimicrobial drug residues which tests inhibitory positive by a microbiological screening test
Trailer	The rear part of the transportation truck with 4–5 compartments containing milk
Transportation tank	Milk tank in the transportation truck arriving at the dairy plant
Truck	The front part of the transportation truck with 3–4 compartments containing milk
Truck compartment	Milk tanks in the transportation truck are divided with walls into separate compartments holding milk

2 Yhteenveto ja johtopäätökset

2.1 Johdanto

Lääkityn lehmän maitoa ei saa lähettää hoidon ja sitä seuraavan varoajan aikana meijeriin, vaan se täytyy käyttää tai hävittää tilalla. Jäämiä sisältävää raakamaitoa päätyy kuitenkin meijereihin jonkin verran. Yleisimpiä syitä ovat inhimilliset erehdykset ja huolimattomuus lääkevalmisteen varoajan noudattamisessa. Raakamaitoa, joka sisältää mikrobilääkejäämiä yli Euroopan unionin (EU) asettamien sallittujen raja-arvojen (MRL) ei saa käyttää elintarvikkeeksi (Neuvoston asetus 2377/90). Meijereihin toimitetun mikrobilääkejäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon määrä on vähentynyt viime vuosina (NFA 2004). Tehostetulla tilaneuvonnalla, tilojen ohjeistamisella sekä laatukselluttamisella pyritään edesauttamaan myönteistä kehitystä (Mäkelä, henkilökohtainen tiedonanto). Lisäksi uusien tekniikoiden kuten AUTE-merkinnän avulla pyritään vähentämään inhimillisiä erehdyksiä tiloilla (Nyman 2003).

EU:n jäsenmaat toteuttavat vuosittain eläimistä saatavien elintarvikkeiden vierasainevalvontaohjelmaa, jonka puitteissa valvotaan mm. raakamaidon mikrobilääkeaineiden jäämiä. Suomessa vierasainevalvontaohjelmassa tutkitaan vuosittain noin 300 raakamaitonäytettä EU:n hyväksymillä kemiallisilla menetelmillä. Virallisten näytteiden lisäksi vuosittain tutkitaan lähes 2000 maitonäytettä mikrobiologisella T101-seulontatestillä. Vuoden 1999 jälkeen Suomesta on vierasaineohjelman puitteissa löydetty ainoastaan yksi raakamaitonäyte, jonka sisältämät mikrobilääkejäämät varmistettiin kemiallisesti (EELA/MMM 2000; EVI/EELA/MMM 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004).

Vierasainevalvonnan lisäksi Suomessa toteutetaan meijereillä omavalvontaa, jolla pyritään estämään prosessiin kelpaamattoman raakamaidon pääsy elintarvikkeeksi. MMM:n asetus (MMM 31/EEO/2001) edellyttää jokaisen meijeriin saapuva raakamaitokuorman testaamista mikrobilääkejäämien varalta. Käytetyin testimenetelmä tähän tarkoitukseen on mikrobiologinen seulontatesti, T101-testi (Valio Oy). EU ei vaadi tällaista seulontatestiä, mutta kansallisesti viranomaiset ovat hyväksyneet sen käytön laitosten omavalvonnassa. T101-testin positiivisen tuloksen aiheuttaa yleensä maidossa oleva mikrobilääkejäämä, tosin eräät muutkin tekijät kuten maidon korkea soluluku voivat antaa positiivisen testituloksen. Testiposiitivista maitoa ei käytetä elintarviketuotantoon.

Vuonna 2002 meijerit poistivat omavalvonnassaan positiivisten testitulosten perusteella elintarvikekäytöstä 47 raakamaitokuormaa sisältäen yli 500 000 litraa raakamaitoa. Vuonna 2003 vastaava kuormien määrä oli vähentynyt edelliseen vuoteen verrattuna; raakamaitokuormia hylättiin yhteensä 37 kappaletta ja n. 360 000 litraa raakamaitoa poistettiin elintarvikekäytöstä (NFA 2004). T101-testiposiitivisen raakamaidon osuus rehuna käytetyistä meijereiden sivutuotteista on pieni. Suomen suu-

rimman maidonjalostajan Valion mukaan T101-testiposiitivisena hylätty raakamaito on noin 0,3–0,4 % kaikista rehuna käytetyistä meijereiden sivutuotteista (Konttinen, henkilökohtainen tiedonanto).

Suomessa käytäntönä on ollut, että testiposiitivisuuden vuoksi hylätyt raakamaitoerät sekä muut elintarvikkeeksi kelpaamattomat meijereiden sivutuotteet toimitetaan rehujakelijan kautta tuotantoeläinten rehuksi tai jätteeksi (NFA 2003a). Tämä käytäntö on noussut ajankohtaiseksi nk. sivutuoteasetuksen (1774/2002) raakamaidolle asettamien käsittelyvaatimusten johdosta. Maa- ja metsätalousministeriön pyynnöstä Eläinlääkintä- ja elintarviketutkimuslaitoksessa aloitettiin syksyllä 2003 mikrobilääkejäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon rehukäytön riskinarviointi.

Rehussa, joka sisältää mikrobilääkejäämäepäilyn vuoksi hylättyä raakamaitoa, voi olla mikrobilääkejäämiä tai taudinaiheuttajia, jotka voivat aiheuttaa terveydellistä vaaraa rehua syöville eläimille (ja siten myös välillisesti kuluttajille). Tämä raportti keskittyy meijereillä jäämätestauksessa positiiviseksi todetun raakamaidon rehukäyttöön sika- ja vasikkatiloilla. Se sisältää seuraavat osat:

- **Riskinarviointi mikrobilääkejäämistä:** testiposiitivisen raakamaidon rehukäytön aiheuttama riski em. rehua saaville sioille ja vasikoille.
- **Testimenetelmät:** mikrobilääkejäämätestauksessa käytettävien menetelmien merkitys jäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon toteamisessa.
- **Kuumennus, hapotus ja entsyymivalmisteiden käyttö:** näiden menetelmien vaikutus mikrobilääkejäämien vähentämisessä.
- **Patogeenivaarojen tunnistaminen:** arvio siitä, mitkä Kansainvälisen eläintautijärjestön (OIE) A- ja B-listojen naudoilla esiintyvistä taudeista, sekä EU:n uuden zoonoosilainsäädännön mukaisesti raportoitavista zoonooseista voivat levitä testiposiitivisen maidon välityksellä sika- tai vasikkatiloille ja joiden osalta varsinainen riskinarviointi voisi olla tarpeellinen.

Tässä työssä testiposiitivisen raakamaidon rehukäyttöön liittyen ei arvioitu:

- kysymystä mikrobilääkeresistenssin kehittymisestä
- ihmisten altistumista mikrobilääkejäämille
- patogeenivaarojen aiheuttamaa riskiä
- tilannetta, jossa raakamaidon tuonti Suomeen lisääntyisi tai lääkintä- ja testauskäytäntö muuttuisi

2.2 Mikrobilääkejäämien riskinarviointi

Mikrobilääkejäämien riskinarvioinnissa käytettiin Codex Alimentarius komission (Codex Alimentarius 2004) ohjeistusta ja arviointi muodostui neljästä osasta:

1. **Vaaran tunnistamisessa** kuvaillaan naudoilla käytettyjen lääkkeiden määrää Suomessa sekä niitä menetelmiä, joita käytetään raakamaidon mikrobilääkejäämien testauksessa. Riskinarvioinnin ensimmäisenä askeleena on tunnistaa ne mikrobilääkkeet, joiden jäämät voisivat nykyisen lääkintä- ja testikäytännön perusteella päätyä raakamaidon mukana eläinten rehuun. Näiden mikrobilääkkeiden ominaisuudet ja erittyminen maitoon kuvaillaan lyhyesti.
2. **Vaaran kuvaamisessa** perustellaan toksikologisten ADI-arvojen (acceptable daily intake) käyttöä eläinten altistumisen arvioinnissa. Tässä osiossa kuvataan edellisessä osiossa tunnistetuiksi vaaroiksi luokiteltujen mikrobilääkkeiden toksikologisia ominaisuuksia, suolistosta imeytymistä sekä ne tutkimukset, joiden perusteella ADI-arvot on määritetty.
3. **Altistuksen arvioinnissa** kuvataan prosessi, jossa mikrobilääkejäämiä sisältävä

raakamaito hylätään meijerillä positiivisen testituloksen perusteella ja toimitetaan rehujakelijoiden kautta sika- ja vasikkatiloille rehuksi. Rehun sisältämiä mikrobilääkejäämämääriä sekä sikojen ja vasikoiden päivittäistä altistumista arvioidaan simulaatiomallin avulla.

4. **Riskin kuvaamisessa** yhdistyvät kaikki kolme edellistä osiota. Simulaatiomallin avulla arvioitua eläinten päivittäistä altistumisesta verrataan toksikologisiin ADI-arvoihin. Näin saadaan käsitys altistumistason suuruudesta ja vakavuudesta.

Riskinarvioinnissa käytettiin EELAssa tilaustutkimuksina analysoitujen raakamaitonäytteiden tuloksia vuosilta 2001–2003 (EELA 2003a). Lisäksi suoritettiin kolme kyselyä, joiden avulla kerättiin tietoja tämän raportin tarpeisiin: analysoitujen raakamaitonäytteiden alkuperää selvitti EELA (EELA 2003b). Elintarvikevirasto (EVI) keräsi meijereiltä tietoja vuoden 2002 sekä alkuvuoden 2003 positiivisten raakamaitokuormien määrästä ja laimentumisprosesseista meijereillä (NFA 2003b). Näiden hylättyjen raakamaitokuormien käyttöä eläinten rehuna selvitti Kasvintuotannon tarkastuskeskus (KTTK) (KTTK 2004a).

2.2.1 Vaaran tunnistaminen

Suomessa eläinlääkkeiden kokonaismyyntiä seuraa Lääkelaitos. Vuonna 2002 myytiin mikrobilääkkeitä eläinten lääkintään yhteensä 13 200 kg (vaikuttavan aineen määränä laskettuna) β -laktaamien ollessa suurin lääkeryhmä. Bentsyylipenisilliini yksin edusti 46 % kaikista myydyistä lääkkeistä (Koppinen ym. 2003).

Mikrobilääkkeiden käyttöä Suomessa eläinlajeittain on tutkittu eläinlääkäreille tehdyllä kyselytutkimuksella, jossa kartoitettiin mikrobilääkkeiden käyttöä yhden viikon aikana. Suurin käytetty lääkeryhmä naudoilla (vaikuttavan aineen määränä laskettuna) olivat β -laktaamit (86 %), seuraavina ryhminä aminoglykosidit (6 %) sekä sulfonamiditrimetopriimiyhdistelmät (5 %) (Rantala 2003).

Suomessa meijereiden omavalvonnassa käytetyin testimenetelmä mikrobilääkejäämien seulontaan raakamaidosta on mikrobiologinen T101-testi (Valio, Finland). Muiden testien käyttö Suomessa on hyvin vähäistä. Teoriassa T101-testi tunnistaa lähes kaikki Suomessa naudan lääkitsemiseen hyväksytyt mikrobilääkkeet, mutta MRL-arvojen mukaisina pitoisuuksina testi toteaa kuitenkin ainoastaan bentsyylipenisilliinin, kefaleksiinin, neomysiinin, pirlimysiinin ja spiramysiinin (Valio 2003).

Kemiallisissa tutkimuksissa yleisimmin todettu positiivisen T101-testin tuloksen aiheuttaja oli bentsyylipenisilliini. Lisäksi maitonäytteistä löydettiin satunnaisesti streptomysiinin, ampicilliinin ja kloksasilliinin jäämiä. Muiden mikrobilääkkeiden jäämämääriä raakamaidossa ei ollut laboratoriotuloksia saatavilla (EELA 2003a).

Hylätyssä raakamaidossa ja siitä valmistetussa rehussa voidaan olettaa olevan ainoastaan niiden mikrobilääkkeiden jäämiä, joita T101-testi tunnistaa meijerillä suoritussa testauksessa. Mahdollisten rehussa esiintyvien mikrobilääkejäämien tunnistamiseksi laskettiin kaikille Suomessa naudan lääkintään hyväksytyille mikrobilääkkeille ”**teoreettinen enimmäispitoisuus**”, joka voisi nykyisen lääkintäkäytännön perusteella erittyä yhden lehmän lääkinnän vuoksi maitoon. Laskelmissa oletettiin, että kaikki jäämiä sisältävä raakamaito kahden lääkintäpäivän ajalta päätyisi yhteen tilatankilliseen raakamaitoa. Utareensisäisten hoitojen osalta oletettiin, että hoito annettaisiin kahteen utareneljännekseen (neljään umpeenpanohoidon yhteydessä) ja 100 % käytetystä mikrobilääkityksestä poistuisi lypsetyn maidon mukana. Kirjallisuuden perusteella injisoiduista mikrobilääkkeistä oletettiin 0,005–2 % erittyvän maitoon. Tilatankki tyhjennettäisiin meijerille toimitettavaan tankkiautoon ja testattaisiin T101-testillä kuorman saapuessa meijeriin. Tätä teoreettista enimmäispitoisuutta verrattiin T101-testin herkkyYTEEN, jonka avulla voitiin arvioida, mitä

mikrobilääkejäämiä mahdollisesti voisi päätyä hylätyn testiposiitiivisen raakamaidon mukana rehuksi.

Tämän **enimmäispitoisuuslaskelman** perusteella arvioitiin, että T101-testin herkkyys riittää tunnistamaan keskimääräisestä, 10 000 litran meijeriin saapuvasta tankkiauton säiliön raakamaidosta ainoastaan ampisilliinin, bentsyylipenisilliinin, kloksasilliinin ja kefaleksiinin.

Meijeritestauksessa dihydrostreptomysiinin, streptomysiinin ja novobiosiinin teoreettiset enimmäispitoisuudet ylittävät MRL-ajan, mutta pitoisuudet jäävät alle T101-testin havaitsemisrajan, eikä testin herkkyys riitä havaitsemaan näitä raakamaidosta. Näitä mikrobilääkkeitä sekä lisäksi framysetiiniä ja neomysiiniä käytetään kuitenkin naudoille ainoastaan valmisteissa, jotka sisältävät myös β -laktaameja. Yhdistelmä-lääkkeiden sisältämät β -laktaamit aiheuttavatkin positiivisen testituloksen ja tämän perusteella voidaan olettaa, että aminoglykosidien ja novobiosiinin jäämiä voi päätyä rehuun hylättyjen raakamaitoerien mukana riippumatta siitä, ylittääkö niiden pitoisuus raakamaidossa T101-testin havaitsemisrajan.

Teoreettisen enimmäispitoisuuslaskelman mukaan rehu, jossa on käytetty T101-testiposiitiivista raakamaitoa, voi sisältää seuraavien mikrobilääkkeiden jäämiä (Kuva 1):

- Ampisilliini
- Bentsyylipenisilliini
- Dihydrostreptomysiini
- Framysetiini
- Kefaleksiini
- Kloksasilliini
- Neomysiini
- Novobiosiini
- Streptomysiini

Näitä mikrobilääkejäämiä kutsutaan tässä raportissa **potentiaalisiksi vaaroiksi**.

Vaikka maidon mahdollisesti sisältämien mikrobilääkejäämien aiheuttamaa riskiä ihmisille ei arvioidakaan tässä tutkimuksessa, voidaan kuitenkin todeta, että edellä esitetyn teoreettisesti enimmäispitoisuuslaskelman perusteella muut kuin edellä mainitut mikrobilääkejäämät olivat laimentuneet maidon keräyksen aikana alle sallitujen MRL-pitoisuuksien. Tällaisen maidon elintarvikekäyttö on hyväksytty EU:ssa.

2.2.2 Vaaran kuvaaminen

Lihasiat, emakot ja vasikat altistuvat raakamaidon sisältämille mikrobilääkejäämille syömällä rehua, jossa on käytetty yhtenä komponenttina T101-testiposiitiivisena hylättyä raakamaitoa.

Altistumisen vakavuuden ja riskin suuruuden arvioimiseksi eläinten altistumista rehun sisältämille mikrobilääkejäämille verrattiin hyväksyttäviin päiväsaantiarvoihin eli ADI-arvoihin. ADI-arvoja käytetään yleensä vertailuarvona silloin, kun halutaan arvioida mikrobilääkejäämille altistumisen turvallisuutta ihmisille. ADI-arvot on määritetty toksikologisten, mikrobiologisten tai farmakologisten tutkimusten perusteella siten, että elinikäisestä altistumisesta ADI-arvojen alittaville pitoisuuksille ei katsota olevan haittaa yksilön terveydelle.

Tässä raportissa eläinten altistumista verrattiin ainoastaan toksikologiin ADI-arvoihin. ADI-arvojen käyttöä eläinten altistumisen turvallisuuden arvioimiseen voidaan perustella mm. sillä, että toksikologiset ADI-arvot on määritetty käyttämällä herkintä mahdollista eläinlajia. Korkein havaittu pitoisuus, jolla kohde-eläimessä ei ole havaittu muutoksia pitkäkestoisen altistuksen seurauksena on ekstrapoloitu

*käytetään naudoilla ainoastaan yhdistelmä lääkkeinä β -laktamien kanssa

Kuva 1.

Mikrobilääkejäämien luokittelu "teoreettisen enimmäispitoisuuslaskelman", T101-testin herkkyyden, MRL-rajojen sekä yhdistelmä lääke käytännön perusteella. Rehuna käytettävä raakamaito voi sisältää niitä mikrobilääkejäämiä, joiden teoreettinen enimmäispitoisuus meijerillä testattavassa raakamaitokuormassa ylittää T101-testin havaitsemisrajan. Lisäksi näiden mikrobilääkkeiden kanssa yhdistelmä lääkkeinä käytetyt aminoglykosidit ja novobiosiini saattaa päätyä raakamaidon mukana rehuun.

laajan turvallisuuskertoimen avulla määrittelemään turvallisuusraja ihmisille. Kertoimen avulla varmistetaan lajien ja yksilöiden välisen vaihtelun huomioonottaminen (EMEA 2004a). Erillisiä eläinlajikohtaisia ADI-arvoja ei ole määritelty. Koska ei ole perusteita olettaa, että sika tai vasikka olisi ihmistä herkempi mikrobilääkejäämille ja lisäksi eläinten oletettu elinikä (ja näin myös altistuminen) on ihmisten elinikää huomattavasti lyhyempi, katsottiin, että ihmisille määritettyjen toksikologisten ADI-arvo-

jen avulla voidaan hyvin arvioida rehun kautta tapahtuvaa sikojen ja vasikoiden altistumista mikrobilääkkeiden jäämille (Taulukko 1).

Mikrobilääkejäämien kertyminen eläimen kudoksiin ja päätyminen elintarvikeketjuun edellyttää jäämien imeytymistä ruuansulatuskanavasta. Sian imeytymistietojen puuttuessa kerättiin tietoa ihmisellä tapahtuvasta imeytymisestä. Sikojen ja ihmisten ruuansulatuskanavan samanlaisuuden perusteella voidaan olettaa, että imeytyminen on samanasteista. Vasikoilla imeytyminen on heikompaa kuin sioilla (Taulukko 2).

Taulukko 1.

Potentiaalisiksi vaaroiksi tunnistettujen mikrobilääkkeiden toksikologiset ADI-arvot ihmisille.

Mikrobilääke	Toksikologinen ADI µg/kg/vrk
β-laktaamit	
Ampisilliini	200 ^{a*}
Bentsyylipenisilliini	0,5 ^b
Kefaleksiini	500 ^b
Kloksasilliini	200 ^a
Aminoglykosidit	
Dihydrostreptomysiini	25 ^b
Framysetiini	60 ^b
Neomysiini	60 ^b
Streptomysiini	25 ^b
Muut	
Novobiosiini	20 ^b

^aAustralian government (2003)

*Ampisilliinin ADI ei ole määritetty.

Oletettu samaksi kuin amoksisilliinin ADI

^bEMEA (2003)

Taulukko 2.

Potentiaalisiksi vaaroiksi tunnistettujen mikrobilääkkeiden imeytyminen suun kautta annettuna.

Mikrobilääke	Imeytymis-% suun kautta annettuna sika	Imeytymis-% suun kautta annettuna vasikka
β-laktaamit		
Ampisilliini	55 ^{a1}	4,5 ^{f3}
Bentsyylipenisilliini	30 ^{b2}	7 ^{g3}
Kefaleksiini	100 ^{a1}	29 ^{h3}
Kloksasilliini	30–80 ^{c1}	te
Aminoglykosidit		
Dihydrostreptomysiini	1 ^{d1}	te
Framysetiini	1 ^{d1}	te
Neomysiini	1 ^{d1}	0,4 ⁱ³
Streptomysiini	1 ^{d1}	te
Muut		
Novobiosiini	30 ^{e2}	te

^aMacGregor & Graziani (1997)

^bUSP DI (2003)

^cToxnet (2004a)

^dToxnet (2004c)

^eEMEA (2003)

^fZiv ym. (1977)

^gMusser & Anderson (2001)

^hSoback ym. (1987)

ⁱPedersoli ym. (1994)

te = tietoa ei saatavilla

¹havaittu ihmisillä

²havaittu eläimillä

³havaittu vasikoilla

2.2.3 Altistuminen

Altistumisen arvioinnissa kuvailtiin ensin altistumisreitti, jossa meijerillä hylätty testiposiitivinen raakamaitokuorma toimitetaan eläinten rehuksi. Näiden tietojen pohjalta luotiin simulaatiomalli, jonka avulla voitiin arvioida todennäköisiä mikrobilääkejäämäpitoisuuksia rehussa ja eläinten altistumista.

2.2.3.1 Altistumisreitti

Raakamaitokuorman saapuessa meijerille vetoautosta ja sen perävaunusta otetaan näyte mikrobilääkejäämien toteamiseksi. Käytännön järjestelyt näytteen ottamiseksi vaihtelevat tapauskohtaisesti. Mikäli T101-testi tai lisätestinä käytetty Snap-testi (Idexx, USA) antaa testiposiitivisen tuloksen, ryhdytään välittömästi seuraaviin toimenpiteisiin (Laitinen 2002; NFA 2003a):

1. Selvitetään mikä osa kuormasta on testiposiitivinen ja puretaan se sivutuotteille varattuun siiloon.
2. Mikäli kuorma on vahingossa purettu jo elintarvikekäyttöön tarkoitettuun siiloon, koko siilon sisältö hylätään ilman lisätestausta.
3. Testiposiitivisen tuloksen aiheuttanut tila pyritään löytämään analysoimalla tilakohtaisia näytteitä. Mikäli tiloilta ei ole otettu raakamaidon keräyksen yhteydessä näytettä, tilakohtaiset näytteet pyritään ottamaan mahdollisimman pian.
4. Maito-osuuskunnan tuotantoneuvoja ottaa yhteyttä tilaan.
5. Valvontaviranomaisille ilmoitetaan tapahtuneesta vahingosta. Useimmiten läänineläinlääkäri suorittaa tilatarkastuksen ja tarkastaa lääkekirjanpidon.
6. Tuotanto-osuuskunta asettaa tilalle aiheutuneen vahingon mukaisen korvausvaatimuksen.
7. Jos mikrobilääkkeiden jäämiä löydetään uudelleen samalta tilalta kolmen vuoden sisällä, valvova viranomainen asettaa tilan erityisvalvontaan.

Elintarvikevirasto keräsi tietoja vuosien 2002 ja 2003 positiivisista raakamaitokuormista. Kyselyn avulla saatiin tietoa kaikista vuoden 2002 positiivisista kuormista (47 kpl) sekä näiden tapauksien lisäksi alkuvuoden 2003 tapauksista (13 tapausta, koko vuonna tapauksia oli 37 kpl). Keskimäärin raakamaitoa hylättiin n.10 000 litraa/testiposiitivinen tankkiauto. Näissä 60 selvitetystä testiposiitivisesta tapauksesta useimmiten hylätty raakamaito toimitettiin eläinten rehuksi (72 %). Raakamaito voitiin sekoittaa ennen kuljetusta meijerin muihin sivutuotteisiin kuten huuhdemaitoihin, heraan tai piimään (60 % tapauksista) jolloin kuormat laimenivat keskimäärin 3,9-kertaisesti. Sekoitus saattoi tapahtua myös suoraan rehujakelijan kuljetussäiliöön (23 % tapauksista). Näiden tapauksien keskimääräinen laimennuskerroin oli 4,4 (NFA 2003b). Hylätty raakamaito voitiin lähettää meijeriltä myös laimentamattomana suoraan sikatiloille, jolloin ne laimennettiin tilalla ylimääräisellä OVR-liemi (ohravalkuaisrehu) lisäyksellä (16 % tapauksista). Ne kuormat, joita ei laimennettu meijereillä, laimennettiin tiloilla keskimäärin 5,8-kertaisesti. Osa hylätyistä kuormista (13 %) päättyi lannoitteeksi, hävitettäväksi tai kaatopaikoille. Lopuissa tapauksissa (15 %) käyttöä ei saatu selville (KTTK 2004a).

T101-testiposiitiviset kuormat hylätään ilman kemiallista varmistusta. Näin ollen testiposiitivisen tuloksen aiheuttaja jää yleensä tunnistamatta ja pitoisuus määrittämättä. Joissain tapauksissa meijeri, tuottaja tai eläinlääkäri haluaa, että näyte tutkitaan tarkemmin ja mikrobilääkejäämä varmistetaan kemiallisin menetelmin. Näitä tilaustutkimuksia suoritetaan EELAn kemian tutkimusyksikössä. Vuosien 2001–2003 kuluessa EELAssa analysoitiin 5 näytettä tilatankeista, 12 näytettä kuljetusautojen säiliöistä ja 3 yksittäisen lehmän maitonäytettä. Näissä tutkimuksissa löydettiin pää-

asiallisesti bentsyyliipenisilliinijäämiä, sekä yksittäistapauksina ampisilliinia ja kloksasilliinia. Streptomysiiniä sisältävien näytteiden streptomysiinipitoisuudet eivät ylittäneet T101-testin määritysrajaa (EELA 2003a; EELA 2003b). T101-testin positiivisen tuloksen oli aiheuttanut todennäköisesti bentsyyliipenisilliini, jota löydettiin kaikista streptomysiiniä sisältävistä näytteistä. Luotettavia tuloksia varsinaiseen altistuksen arviointiin saatiin ainoastaan bentsyyliipenisilliinille. Muiden mikrobilääkejäämien altistuksen arvioinnissa käytettiin teoreettisen enimmäispitoisuuden laskennalla arvioituja pitoisuuksia (kts. luku 5.1.4).

Kasvintuotannon tarkastuskeskus teki jatkoselvityksen Elintarvikeviraston selvitykseen pohjautuen vuonna 2002 ja alkuvuonna 2003 hylättyjen T101-testiposiitivisten raakamaitokuormien rehukäytöstä. Näistä testiposiitivisista kuormista 78 % jäljitettiin aina tilatasolle saakka. Kaikki selvitetty raakamaitokuormat päätyivät sikatiloille, joissa oli keskimäärin 900 lihasikaa. Tiloista 27 % oli yhdistelmäsikaloita, joilla oli lihasikojen lisäksi keskimäärin 200 emakkoa. Kaiken kaikkiaan kuormia vastaanottavia tiloja oli 30, joista 3 oli Suomen rajojen ulkopuolella (KTTK 2004a). Suomalaisia tiloja oli 27 ja ne edustivat 0,7 % koko Suomen sikatiloista (Tietovakka 2003). Varsinaisen selvityksen jälkeen, keväällä 2004, todettiin kaksi tapausta, jossa raakamaitokuormat oli toimitettu vasikoiden välikasvattamoille. Raakamaitoa oli käytetty vasikoiden seosruokinnassa. Hylätyn raakamaidon laimentuminen vasikoiden välikasvattamolla oli samansuuruista kuin sikatiloilla (KTTK 2004b).

Jokainen hylätty raakamaitoa vastaanottava tila sai keskimäärin 16 000 litraa raakamaidon ja muiden meijerin sivutuotteiden seosta, joka purettiin tilalla säilytystä varten siiloon. Nämä siilot saattoivat sisältää valmiiksi jo muita rehuna käytettäviä komponentteja kuten ohravalkuaisrehua (OVR) tai heraa, jolloin raakamaidon sisältämät mikrobilääkkeiden jäämpitoisuudet olisivat edelleen laimentuneet. Tätä mahdollista ylimääräistä laimentumista ei kuitenkaan huomioitu lopullisessa saantiarviossa tiedon puutteen vuoksi.

Lopullinen rehu valmistetaan tiloilla välittömästi ennen jokaista ruokintaa. Meijerin sivutuotteet siirretään sekoitussäiliöön, jossa muut rehukomponentit kuten OVR, jauhettu vilja, vesi, happo ja tiiviste sekoitetaan ja seoksen annetaan tasaantua noin puoli tuntia ennen jakelua. Rehun valmistuksen yhteydessä mikrobilääkejäämiä sisältävä maito laimenee edelleen keskimäärin 2,6-kertaisesti. Valmiin rehun optimaalinen pH on 4,2–4,5 ja lämpötila +20– +30 °C (Kuoppala ym. 2004; KTTK 2004a).

Raakamaidon mikrobilääkkeiden jäämpitoisuudet laimenevat sekä meijereillä että tiloilla tapahtuneen yhteenlasketun laimentumisen vuoksi keskimäärin 14-kertaisesti (vaihtelu 0,3–300-kertaisesti) tankkiauton raakamaidon sisältämään pitoisuuteen verrattuna.

Tiloilla ilmoitettu valmiin rehun käyttömäärä vaihteli eläimen koon mukaan. Täysikasvuisen lihasian arvioitiin syövän 10 litraa, emakon 28 litraa ja vasikan 9 litraa päivässä tätä lopullista rehuseosta. Yhden tiloille toimitetun T101-testiposiitivista raakamaitoa sisältävän kuorman rehua syötettiin eläimille keskimäärin 3,6 päivää (vaihteluväli 1–6 päivää). 40 % sikatiloista sai tutkimuksen aikana ainoastaan yhden T101-testiposiitivista raakamaitoa sisältävän kuorman. Muut tilat vastaanottivat keskimäärin kaksi tällaista kuormaa (vaihteluväli 1–4 kuormaa) neljän kuukauden ajanjaksolla, joka oletettiin lihasian eliniän pituudeksi (KTTK 2004a; KTTK 2004b).

Varsinaisen selvityksen jälkeen todetut kaksi vasikoiden välikasvattamoa vastaanottivat ainoastaan kerran tällaista raakamaitoa tutkimuksen aikana.

2.2.3.2 Altistumisen mallintaminen

Mikrobilääkejäämien aiheuttamaa eläinten altistumista varten rakennettiin laimentumista kuvaava simulaatiomalli. Se sisälsi viisi peräkkäistä, toisistaan riippuvaa vai-

hetta joissa edellisen vaiheen tulos oli suoraan seuraavan vaiheen osatekijä. Nämä viisi mallissa huomioitua vaihetta perustuivat edellä esitettyihin tietoihin. Mallin perusrakenteeseen kuuluivat:

1. Testiposiitivisen kuljetusautotankillisen tilavuuden todennäköisyysjakauma sekä mikrobilääkejäämien pitoisuus tässä tankkikoossa. Bentsyyliipenisilliinipitoisuudet hylätyssä raakamaidossa esitettiin laboratoriotutkimuksissa todettujen pitoisuuksien todennäköisyysjakaumana. Muut mahdolliset mikrobilääkejäämät sisällytettiin malliin teoreettisen enimmäispitoisuuslaskelman piste-estimaatteina.
2. Testiposiitivisen raakamaidon laimentuminen, kun raakamaitoon lisättiin muita meijerin sivutuotteita meijerillä tai rehujakelijan kuljetussäiliössä. Tieto käytettiin mallissa todennäköisyysjakaumana siilon sisältämän raakamaidon tilavuudesta.
3. Mallissa oli myös mahdollisuus valita tilalla tapahtuva laimeneminen, mikäli raakamaito lähti laimentamattomana meijeriltä. Laimeneminen sisällytettiin malliin laimennuskertoimen piste-estimaattina.
4. Rehun sekoittamisesta aiheutuva laimeneminen esitettiin laimenemiskertoimen todennäköisyysjakaumana.
5. Ruokintamäärä perustui tilakyselyjen suurimpaan käytettyyn annoskokoon, joka ilmoitettiin piste-estimaattina. Rehun sisältämän mikrobilääkkeen jäämäpitoisuuden todennäköisyysjakauman sekä ruokintamäärien perusteella voitiin arvioida lihasikojen, emakoiden sekä vasikoiden päivittäinen sekä kokonaisaltistuminen yksittäisille mikrobilääkejäämille.

Monte Carlo -simulaation avulla voitiin altistumiselle luoda todennäköisyysjakautuma. Teknisesti malli on rakennettu Excel-taulukkolaskentaohjelmaan (Microsoft Corp., USA) ja simuloinnit tehtiin @Risk® (Palisade Corporation, USA) lisämoduulin avulla. Iteraatioiden, eli mahdollisten laimentumisskenaarioiden määrä jokaisella simulaatiolla oli vähintään 10 000.

Mallin keskeiset oletukset:

- Todetut bentsyyliipenisilliinipitoisuudet edustavat todellisia hylättyjen raakamaitokuormien pitoisuuksia. Havaittujen pitoisuuksien jakautuma noudatti hyvin normaalijakautuman logaritimuunnosta, ja tätä jakautumaa käytettiin mallin syöttötietona.
- Muiden lääkejäämien pitoisuudet edustavat teoreettista enimmäispitoisuutta.
- Lopullisen rehusekoitteen mikrobilääkepitoisuudet riippuvat osalaimennuksien todennäköisyysjakautumista.
- Eläinten päivittäinen saantiarvio muodostuu valmiin rehusekoitteen mikrobilääkkeen jäämäpitoisuudesta sekä syödyn rehun määrästä.
- Täyskasvuisen lihasian oletetaan painavan 100 kg ja syövän 10 litraa lopullista rehuseosta. Oletus perustuu tiloilta kerättyihin tietoihin lihasian ruokinnasta.
- Emakon oletetaan painavan 200 kg ja syövän 28 litraa rehuseosta päivässä. Oletus perustuu tiloilta kerättyihin tietoihin emakon ruokinnasta.
- Vasikan oletetaan painavan 90 kg ja syövän 9 litraa rehuseosta päivässä. Oletus perustuu tiloilta kerättyihin tietoihin vasikan ruokinnasta.
- Päivittäinen saantiarvio voidaan suhteuttaa eläimen elopainokiloon.
- Jäämien haitallisuutta voidaan arvioida vertaamalla altistumista ihmisille määritettyihin toksikologisiin ADI-arvoihin.
- Altistumisesta alle toksikologisten ADI-arvojen ei katsota olevan vaaraa eläimelle.

Tuloksena malli ilmoittaa rehun mikrobilääkkeiden jäämäpitoisuuksien, päivittäisen altistumisen sekä % -osuuden annetuista ADI-arvoista todennäköisyysjakaumina.

Simulaatiomallin jokainen laimennusvaihe perustuu normaalikäytännöstä kerättyihin tietoihin, joita saatiin runsaasti. Tästä syystä mallia voidaan pitää kohtuullisen luotettavana.

2.2.4 Riskin kuvaaminen

Mallin avulla voitiin arvioida lihasikojen, emakoiden ja vasikoiden päivittäistä altistumista eri mikrobilääkejäämille. Altistumista arvioitiin meijerillä tapahtuvan laimennusvaihtoehdon mukaisina pitoisuuksina, sillä tämä laimennustapa oli kaikkein yleisin. Lisäksi tässä vaihtoehdossa laimenneminen oli vähäisintä, jolloin arviota ei voida pitää liian optimistisena.

Todennäköinen bentsyyliipenisilliinipitoisuus lopullisessa rehussa oli simulaation mukaan 2,5 µg/litra [90 % tuloksista 0–5,8 µg/litra]. Suhteutettuna eläimen syömään päivittäiseen rehumäärään sekä eläimen elopainoon, lihasiat altistuivat bentsyyliipenisilliinille keskimäärin 0,25 µg/kg/päivä [90 % tuloksista 0–0,6 µg/kg/päivä] ja emakot 0,36 µg/kg/päivä [90 % tuloksista 0–0,8 µg/kg/päivä] sinä aikana kun jäämiä sisältävää rehua oli tarjolla (keskiarvo 3,6 päivänä). Vastaavasti vasikat altistuivat bentsyyliipenisilliinille 0,25 µg/kg/päivä [90 % tuloksista 0–0,6 µg/kg/päivä]. Vasikoiden ruokintapäiviä oli keskimäärin 9/toimitettu kuorma (Taulukko 3).

Keskimääräinen päivittäinen altistuminen bentsyyliipenisilliinijäämille oli 50 % (lihasiat), 71 % (emakot) ja 50 % (vasikat) **toksikologisesta ADI-arvosta**. Simulointimallin tuloksista 80 % alitti bentsyyliipenisilliinin ADI-arvon kaikilla tutkituilla eläinryhmillä.

Altistumista muille mikrobilääkejäämille arvioitiin teoreettisten enimmäispitoisuuksien laskelmalla. Vasikoiden, lihasikojen ja emakoiden päivittäinen altistuminen ampisilliinille, kefaleksiinille, kloksasilliinille, framysetiinille, neomysiinille ja novobiosiinille jäi selkeästi (>98 % tuloksista) alle **toksikologisten ADI-arvojen**. Altistuminen dihydrostreptomysiinille ja streptomysiinille oli hieman korkeampaa, mutta keskimääräinen altistuminen jäi selvästi alle toksikologisten ADI-arvojen sekä siolla että vasikoilla.

Taulukko 3.

Simulaatiomallin avulla arvioidut keskimääräiset mikrobilääkkeiden jäämäpitoisuudet rehussa ylittävät raakamaidolle määritetyt MRL-rajat ampisilliinillä, kefaleksiinillä sekä kloksasilliinillä. Lihasikojen, emakoiden ja vasikoiden keskimääräiset päivittäiset saantiarviot alittavat ihmisten toksikologiset ADI-arvot kaikilla arvioiduilla mikrobilääkejäämillä.

Vaikuttava aine	Simuloitu keskimääräinen pitoisuus rehussa µg/litra	Maidolle asetettu MRL-arvo µg/litra	Simulointimallilla arvioitu keskimääräinen päivittäissaanti			Toksikologinen ADI-arvo µg/kg/vrk
			µg/kg/vrk			
			lihasialla	emakolla	vasikalla	
Ampisilliini	18,8 *	4	1,9	2,6	1,9	200
Bentsyyliipenisilliini	2,5	4	0,3	0,4	0,3	0,5
Dihydrostreptomysiini	113,2	200	11,3	15,8	11,2	25
Framysetiini	7,5	1500	0,8	1,0	0,7	60
Kefaleksiini	112,7 *	100	11,3	15,8	11,2	500
Kloksasilliini	37,5 *	30	3,8	5,3	3,7	200
Neomysiini	33,6	1500	3,4	4,8	3,3	60
Novobiosiini	30,1	100	3,0	4,1	3,0	20
Streptomysiini	165,6	200	16,5	23,2	16,3	25

*Pitoisuus rehussa ylittää maidon MRL-arvon

2.2.5 Mallin validointi

Mallin validointi suoritettiin tutkimusajankohdan jälkeen kerättyjen tietojen avulla. Näitä tietoja ei käytetty mallin rakentamiseen. Vuoden 2003 lopussa ja vuoden 2004 alussa meijereillä hylätyistä T101-testiposiitivisista raakamaitokuormista lähetettiin maitonäytteet EELAan, jossa ne tutkittiin mikrobilääkejäämien varalta kemiallisin menetelmin. Hylätyt kuormat sisälsivät ainoastaan bentsyyliipenisilliinijäämiä. Kahden meijerillä hylätyn raakamaitokuorman käyttö jäljitettiin yhteensä 16 tilalle. Näiden tapauksen mukana saatiin tietoa ensimmäisen kerran myös vasikkakasvattamoille päätyneistä eristä.

Keskimääräinen bentsyyliipenisilliinipitoisuus näiden 16 tilan rehussa oli 0,5 (keskihajonta 0,3 µg/litra). Tämä tulos on hyvin linjassa mallin antamien tulosten kanssa ja mallin voidaan katsoa antavan suhteellisen luotettavia ennusteita mikrobilääkkeiden laimentumisesta rehukäytössä.

2.2.6 Riskinhallintatoimenpiteiden vaikutus

Mahdollisina riskinhallintatoimenpiteinä mikrobilääkejäämien vähentämiseksi maidossa selvitettiin kuumentamisen, happamuuden säätelyn ja entsyymivalmisteiden käytön vaikutusta.

2.2.6.1 Kuumennuskäsittely

Kuumennuskäsittelyn vaikutusta mikrobilääkejäämien hajottamiseen raakamaidosta arvioitiin kolmessa eri lämpökäsittelyvaihtoehdossa:

- Pastörinti: 72 °C/ 15 sekuntia
- UHT-kuumennus: 135 °C/ 1 sekunti
- Maitojauheen valmistusprosessi: Lämpökäsittely on ensin maksimissaan 3 minuuttia 120 °C:ssa, jonka jälkeen haihdutusvaiheen lämpötilat vaihtelevat välillä 50–70 °C (20 min). Loppukuivaus tehdään sumutustornissa, jossa lämpötila on muutamia sekunteja korkeimmillaan 80–90 °C.

Arvioidut mikrobilääkkeet hajoavat hitaasti lämpökäsittelyn yhteydessä. 71 °C:ssa bentsyyliipenisilliinin 100 % hajoaminen vaatisi vähintään 28 tuntia. Pastörinti ei siten vähennä mikrobilääkejäämien pitoisuutta maidosta (Shanani 1958).

Bentsyyliipenisilliinin sekä aminoglykosidien hajottaminen lämpötilaa nostamalla vaatisi vähintään käsittelyä 100 °C:ssa 5 tunnin ajan (Pilet ym. 1969) (Annex 6). Millään arvioiduilla lämpökäsittelyvaihtoehdoilla ei siten voida merkittävästi vähentää mikrobilääkejäämiä hylätyssä T101-positiivisessa maidossa.

2.2.6.2 Happokäsittely

Rehun happamuuden säätelyn vaikutusta mikrobilääkejäämiin tutkittiin nykyisessä käytännössä:

- Optimi pH sikojen ruokinnassa käytetylle rehulle on 4–5.
- Hapotettaessa rehua rehun valmistuksen yhteydessä, rehun pH laskee tasolle 4–5 vain n. 30 minuutin ajaksi ennen ruokintaa.
- Raakamaidon laimennuksessa käytetyt komponentit kuten hera ja OVR ovat happamia (pH 4–5), jolloin hylätyn maidon pH laskee useiksi päiviksi ennen ruokintaa lähelle pH-arvoa 5.

Lähes kaikki tutkitut mikrobilääkkeet olivat kaikkein pysyvimpiä pH-alueella 4–5. Yleisesti ottaen niiden hajoamiseen vaaditaan pH-asteikon ääripäitä, joko todella

happamia tai emäksisiä liuoksia. Ampisilliinin puoliintumisaika pH:ssa 4 oli 50 tuntia (Hou & Poole 1969). Ainoastaan bentsyylipenisilliini ja kloksasilliini saattavat hajota jossain määrin annetuissa olosuhteissa. Valitettavasti hajoamiskinetiikkaa ei tunneta pH:ssa 4 ja sen ympärillä. Hapottamisen vaikutusta on tutkittu pääsääntöisesti rehun normaalilämpötilaa (max +30 °C) korkeammissa lämpötiloissa, jolloin hajoamisreaktiot ovat nopeampia. Näin ollen käytännössä hajoaminen rehussa on hitaampaa kuin tutkituissa olosuhteissa (Annex 6).

Hapottamisella voidaan katsoa olevan vain vähäistä vaikutusta lopullisiin mikrobilääkkeiden jäämäpitoisuuksiin rehussa. Näin ollen sitä ei voida pitää tehokkaana keinona jäämäpitoisuuksien vähentämiseen T101-testipositivista raakamaitoa sisältävässä rehussa.

2.2.6.3 Entsyymivalmisteet

Mikrobilääkejäämiä entsyymivalmisteilla hajotettaessa tulisi ottaa huomioon, että

- β -laktamaasientsyymi on ainut Suomessa markkinoilla oleva entsyymivalmiste, joka on tarkoitettu mikrobilääkejäämien hajottamiseen.
- β -Laktamaasientsyymi hydrolysoi molekyylien β -laktaamirenkaan
- β -Laktamaasientsyymiä voidaan käyttää bentsyylipenisilliinin, ampisilliinin ja amoksisilliinin hajottamisessa.
- Se ei hajota muita mikrobilääkejäämiä.

Jos kaupallista β -laktamaasientsyymiä käytetään hylätyn raakamaidon mikrobilääkkeiden jäämäpitoisuuksien vähentämiseen, tulee entsyymi sekoittaa raakamaitoon ennen laimentamista, sillä pH:n muuttuessa entsyymin teho laskee. Jos raakamaito laimennetaan tuotteilla, joiden pH vastaa raakamaidon pH:ta, voidaan β -laktamaasientsyymiä lisätä seokseen myös laimentamisen jälkeen. Entsyymien annetaan vaikuttaa maidossa vähintään 12 tuntia, alkuperäisen pitoisuuden ja lopullisen hajoamistarpeen mukaan (Vetcare 2003, Korycka-Dahl ym. 1985).

Kaupallisen β -laktamaasientsyymien (Antipen™) valmistajan mukaan yksi millilitra (24 000 yksikköä β -laktamaasientsyymiä) riittää täysin hajottamaan penisilliinijäämät 40 litrasta hoidetun lehmän maitoa (Vetcare 2003).

Entsyymivalmisteen tehokas käyttö edellyttää tietoa maidon sisältämien mikrobilääkkeiden jäämäpitoisuudesta ja siitä, mitä jäämiä raakamaito sisältää. Bentsyylipenisilliinin on todettu hajoavan 100 % 24 tunnin kuluessa, kun lisätyn β -laktamaasin pitoisuus suhteessa mikrobilääkkeen jäämäpitoisuuteen on ollut riittävä (Korycka-Dahl ym. 1985).

β -laktamaasi hajottaa tehokkaasti bentsyylipenisilliiniä ja aminopenisilliinejä, mutta sen käyttö on turhaa, mikäli raakamaito sisältää muita mikrobilääkejäämiä.

2.3 Patogeenivaarojen tunnistaminen

T101-testin perusteella testimikrobin kasvua inhiboivaa tekijää sisältävää raakamaitoa ei käsitellä mahdollista laimentamista lukuun ottamatta meijerissä, joten se saattaa kuumentamattomana raakatuotteena sisältää alkuperäisen maidontuotantotilan lehmien kantamia taudinaiheuttajia.

Tämän työn yhteydessä tehtiin kartoitus niistä virus-, bakteeri- ja loistaudinaiheuttajista, jotka voisivat teoriassa siirtyä raakamaidon välityksellä lypsykarjatilalta T101-testipositivista maitoa rehuna käyttävälle tilalle. Kartoituksen lähtökohtina olivat kansainvälisen eläintautitoimiston (OIE) A- ja B-listojen naudoilla esiintyvät taudit, sekä EU:n uuden zoonosilainsäädännön mukaisesti raportoitavat zoonosit.

Arvion kohteena oli kaikkiaan 38 infektiota tai tautia. Näitä koskevat johtopäätökset perustuvat

- Suomen nykyiseen eläintautitilanteeseen
- Infektioiden ja tautien epidemiologiaan
- Taudinaiheuttajien erittymiseen maitoon
- Maidon kontaminoitumismahdollisuuteen uloste- tai virtsaperaisilla patogeeneilla.

Työn pohjalta esitetään lisäksi lyhyt arvio mahdollisten riskinhallintatoimenpiteiden vaikutuksista mahdollisesti tarkempaa arviota vaativiin vaaroihin.

Selvityksen johtopäätökset on esitetty taulukossa 4. Tässä taulukossa kunkin taudinaiheuttajan kohdalla on esitetty arvio siitä, kuinka mahdollista on, että T101-testiposiitivinen raakamaito voisi toimia kyseisen patogeenin välittäjänä. Arvion asteikonä käytetään ei vaaraa (1), vähäinen vaara, ei arviointitarvetta (2), ja mahdollinen vaara, joka voi vaatia tarkempaa riskinarviota (3).

Mahdollisina vaaroina pidettiin vain suolistoperäisiä kampakylobakteeri-, enterohemorraginen *E. coli* (EHEC) ja *Listeria monocytogenes* -bakteereita.

Kokonaisuuden kannalta on muistettava, että T101-testiposiitivisuuden takia hylätty maito muodostaa vain osan meijereillä eri syistä hylätystä raakamaidosta. Korkean solumäärän, happamuuden tai vieraan hajun takia hylätyssä maidossa voi esiintyä merkittävästikin korkeampia bakteeripitoisuuksia. Riskinhallintatoimenpiteistä liemi-rehun hapotus tasolle pH 4–5 vähentää kampakylobakteereiden ja listerioiden määriä, mutta vaikuttaa vain hyvin rajoitetusti enterohemorragisiin *E. coli* (EHEC) bakteereihin. Kaikki kolme taudinaiheuttajaa tuhoutuvat nopeasti pastörintia vastaavassa lämpökäsittelyssä.

Taulukko 4.

Maidon kautta mahdollisesti välittyvien patogeeniin ja niiden aiheuttamaa vaaraa koskevan tarkemman riskinarviointitarpeen tunnistaminen.

Tauti	^a Todettu Suomessa viimeksi vuonna	Suomen virallinen status	^b Erityy maitoon tai fekaalisaastuminen merkittävä	^c Riskinarvioinnin tarve
Suu- ja sorkkatauti	1959	vapaa	3	1
Vesikulaarinen stomatiitti	0	N	2	1
Karjarutto	1877	vapaa	1	1
Naudan keuhkorutto	1920	N	0	1
Lumpy skin -tauti	0	N	0	1
Rift Valley -kuume	0	N	1	1
Bluetongue -tauti	0	N	1	1
Pernarutto (Anthrax)	1988	N	1	1
Aujeskyn tauti	0	vapaa	0	1
Ekinokokkoosi (E. granulosus)	2003	N	0	1
Heartwater	0	N	0	1
Leptospiroosi	2002	N	1	2
Q-kuume	0	N	2	1
Raivotauti (Rabies)	1988	vapaa	0	1
Paratuberkuloosi	2001	N	3	2
Screwworm	0	N	0	1
Anaplasmoosi	0	N	0	1
Punatauti (Babesiosis)	2003	N	0	1
Luomistauti (Brucellosis)	1960	vapaa	3	1
Kystikerkoosi (C.bovis)	2002	N	0	1
Bovine genital campylobacteriosis (vibrioosi)	0	N	0	1
BSE ('hullun lehmän tauti')	2001	N	0	1
Nautatuberkuloosi	1982	vapaa	3	1
Dermatofiloosi	0	N	0	1
Nautaeläinten tarttuva leukoosi	1996	N	1	1
Haemorraaginen septikemia	0	N	0	1
IBR/IBV (naudan tarttuva rinotrakeiitti)	1994	N	1	1
Kinokuume	2003	N	1	1
Theilerioosi	0	N	0	1
Trichomonooosi	1952	N	0	1
Trypanosomoosi	0	N	0	1
Kampylobakterioosi (suolistomuoto)	2003	N	3	3
Listerioosi	2003	N	3	3
Salmonelloosi	2003	N	3	2
EHEC (enterohemoraaginen E. coli) infektiio	2003	N	3	3
Yersinioosi	2003	N	2	2
Cryptosporidioosi	2003	N	1	2
Toksoplasmoosi	2003	N	0	2

^a Tilanne 31.12.2003

0 = Ei todettu koskaan

N = Ei virallista statusta

^b 0: Ei erityy/fekaali eli ulostesaastuminen merkityksetöntä

1: Mahdollista mutta epidemiologisesti merkityksetöntä

2: Mahdollista

3: Erityy tai tunnettu fekaalisaastuminen

^c 1: Ei vaaraa, ei arviointitarvetta

2: Vähäinen vaara, ei arviointitarvetta

3: Mahdollinen vaara, joka voi vaatia tarkempaa arviota

2.4 Johtopäätökset

Johtopäätökset vuosien 2002 ja 2003 tilanteen perusteella:

1. Tämän tutkimuksen perusteella meijerillä positiivisen testituloksen vuoksi hylätystä raakamaidossa ja siitä valmistetussa rehussa olevien mikrobilääkkeiden jäämät eivät aiheuta toksikologista riskiä sikojen ja vasikoiden terveydelle nykyisessä tilanteessa.
2. Kun tankkiauton sisältämä raakamaito testataan meijerillä, siinä mahdollisesti olevat mikrobilääkkeiden jäämäpitoisuudet ovat laimentumisen seurauksena niin matalia, että käytännössä jäämätestaus pystyy havaitsemaan maidosta ainoastaan ampicilliinin, bentsyylipenisilliinin, kefaleksiinin ja kloksasilliinin. Aminoglykosideja ja novobiosiinia käytetään naudoilla ainoastaan yhdistelmä lääkkeinä bentsyylipenisilliinin ja kefaleksiinin kanssa. Vaikka jäämätesti ei havaitsekaan aminoglykosideja ja novobiosiinia meijeritestauksessa, niitä voi kuitenkin päätyä raakamaidon mukana rehuun testauksen havaitessa bentsyylipenisilliinin tai kloksasilliinin jäämiä raakamaidossa.
3. Koska kohdassa 2 mainitut mikrobilääkkeet muodostavat suurimman osan nautojen mikrobilääkekäytöstä, voidaan todeta, että meijeritestauksen avulla voidaan estää huomattava osa naudalla käytettävien mikrobilääkejäämien pääytymisestä raakamaidosta valmistettujen elintarvikkeiden kautta kuluttajille.
4. Arvion mukaan muiden kuin kohdassa 2 mainittujen mikrobilääkeainejäämien pitoisuudet ovat laimentuneet meijerille saapuessaan alle EU:n asettamien jäämien sallitun enimmäismäärän (MRL).
5. Raakamaidon kuumentaminen tai rehun hapottaminen eivät vähennä merkittävästi mikrobilääkejäämien pitoisuuksia. Sen sijaan raakamaidon käsittely β -laktamaasientsyymillä vähentää tehokkaasti bentsyylipenisilliinin ja aminopenisilliinien pitoisuuksia maidossa, mutta sillä ei ole vaikutusta muihin mikrobilääkejäämiin.
6. Mikrobilääkejäämiä sisältävän raakamaidon rehukäytöstä kuluttajille aiheutuvaa jäämätariskia ei arvioitu tässä raportissa. Eläinten vähäisen altistumisen perusteella voidaan kuitenkin tehdä se johtopäätös, että meijerillä jäämätestaustuloksen perusteella hylätyn raakamaidon rehukäytöstä johtuva ihmisten altistuminen sian- tai naudanlihan kautta mikrobilääkejäämille on hyvin vähäistä nykyisessä tilanteessa.
7. Raakamaidossa, joka hylätään meijerillä mikrobilääkejäämätestauksen perusteella, voivat suolistoperäiset kampylobakteeri-, enterohemorraginen *E. coli* (EHEC) ja *L. monocytogenes* -infektiot olla mahdollisia vaaroja, joiden suhteen tarkempaa riskinarviota voi olla syytä harkita.

3 Summary and conclusions

3.1 Introduction

The milk of a medically-treated cow cannot be sent to the dairy during treatment or for a specific withdrawal period afterwards, but has either to be used at the farm or destroyed. Some milk containing antimicrobial drug residues does, however, end up at dairies. The most common reasons are human error and carelessness in following the withdrawal periods of medical preparations. Raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues above the maximum residue limits (MRL) set by the EU is unfit for human consumption (Council regulation 2377/90). Fortunately, the amount of raw milk containing antimicrobial residues sent to dairies has decreased in recent years (NFA 2004). In order to facilitate this positive development, farmers are being offered improved counselling, written instructions, and quality educational programs (Mäkelä, personal communication). In addition, through the use of new technology, such as AUTE-labelling, efforts are being made to reduce human error at farms (Nyman 2003).

EU member states are required to run a national residue control program (NRCP), under whose auspices antimicrobial drug residues are also monitored. In Finland, approximately 300 raw milk samples are analyzed annually with chemical methods accepted by the EU. In addition, ca. 2,000 raw milk samples are tested with the microbiological T101-screening test. Since 1999, only one positive raw milk sample has been confirmed with chemical methods to contain antimicrobial drug residues (EELA/MMM 2000; EVI/EELA/MMM 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004).

In addition to the national residue control program, Finnish dairy operators also perform their own checks in order to ensure that unsuitable raw milk is not used for human consumption. National legislation (MMM /31/EEO/2001) requires that each raw milk lot arriving at a dairy plant is tested for antimicrobial drug residues. The most commonly used microbiological screening test for this purpose is the T101-test (Valio, Finland). The EU does not require this kind of screening test, but national authorities in Finland allow operators to use it in their own checks. A positive T101-test is usually caused by antimicrobial drug residues, but other factors, such as a high cell count in the milk, might also give a positive result. Test-positive milk is not used in food production.

Annually ca. 50 test positive lots are either destroyed or used, frequently diluted, as feed. In 2002, as part of their own checks, dairies rejected 47 transportation lots of raw milk, containing over 500,000 kg. In 2003, the corresponding numbers were lower than the preceding year: 37 transport lots and 360,000 kg of raw milk were rejected for human consumption (NFA 2004). T101-test positive raw milk represents only a small fraction of all dairy by-products used as feed. According to Valio Ltd, the

largest milk refiner in Finland, T101-test positive milk represents about 0.3–0.4% of all dairy by-products used in feed (Konttinen, personal communication).

In Finland, the practice has been that raw milk lots rejected due to a positive residue test and other dairy by-products unsuitable for human consumption either are disposed of or are taken by a feed distributor to be used as animal feed (NFA 2003a). This practice is now being questioned due to new by-product regulation (1774/2002) which sets requirements on how milk by-products are to be handled. In the fall of 2003, at the request of the Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MMM), the National Veterinary and Food Research Institute (EELA) began a risk assessment on the use of raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues as feed.

Feed containing raw milk rejected due to the suspected presence of antimicrobial substances can contain residues and infectious agents which can be hazardous to animals which eat such feed (and hence also indirectly be hazardous to consumers). This report focuses on raw milk which tests positive for antimicrobial drug residues at the dairy, and its use as feed in pig and calf farms. It contains the following sections:

- **Risk assessment on antimicrobial drug residues:** the risks for pigs and calves eating feed which contains raw milk testing positive for antimicrobial drug residues.
- The relevance of the **testing methods** used in detecting antimicrobial drug residues in raw milk.
- The effect of **heat treatment, acidification of feed and the use of enzymes** on the reduction of antimicrobial drug residues.
- **Hazard identification of pathogens:** An assessment whether diseases on the World Organization for Animal Health's (OIE) list A and list B, as well as on the EU Council Directive of Zoonotic Diseases can spread via test-positive milk to pigs and calves, and would hence warrant further risk assessment.

In this project, we have not assessed the following issues:

- increase in antimicrobial resistance
- human exposure to antimicrobial residues
- risks caused by pathogenic hazards
- increased imports of raw milk to Finland or changes in current Finnish therapeutic and testing practices

3.2 Risk assessment of antimicrobial drug residues

This antimicrobial drug residue risk assessment follows the format of the Codex Alimentarius Commission (Codex Alimentarius 2004), consisting of four parts:

1. **Hazard identification** – describes the amount of antimicrobials used in treating cattle in Finland, as well as the test methods used to detect residues in raw milk. The first step of the risk assessment is to identify the antimicrobials which might be found in animal feed given current medical and testing practices. In addition, the properties of antimicrobials identified as potential hazards are briefly described, along with their excretion into milk.
2. **Hazard characterisation** – explains the use of toxicological ADI-values in animal exposure assessments. This section also discusses the toxicological characteristics and gastrointestinal absorption of the antimicrobials identified as hazards in the first section, as well as describes the studies through which the ADI-values have been determined.

3. **Exposure assessment** – describes the process by which test-positive raw milk makes its way from the dairy via feed distributors into pig and calf feed. Concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues in feed as well as the daily exposures of pigs and calves are determined with the aid of a simulation model.
4. **Risk characterisation** – brings together the preceding three sections. With the aid of a simulation model, the daily exposures of animals are compared to toxicological ADI-values, thus providing a view of the size and severity of these exposure levels.

This risk assessment used results of EELA's chemical analyses of raw milk samples from 2001-2003 (EELA 2003a). In addition, three different surveys were carried out to obtain data for this report. NFA inspection authorities collected information from dairy plants about test positive cases in Finland and dilution practices at dairy plants during 2002 and beginning of 2003 (NFA 2003b). KTTK inspection authorities did a follow-up survey of these rejected raw milk lots which were further delivered by feed distribution companies and used by farmers (KTTK 2004a). Based on the results of chemically-analyzed raw milk samples, EELA contacted all the dairy plants who had positive chemical test results in 2001–2003 (EELA 2003b).

3.2.1 Hazard identification

In Finland, the total sales of veterinary medicines is monitored by the National Agency for Medicines. In 2002, 13,200 kg (calculated as kg of active substance) of antimicrobials were sold for veterinary use. β -Lactams were the major group of antimicrobials used, and benzylpenicillin alone represented 46% of antimicrobials sold (Koppinen et al. 2003).

The use of antimicrobial drugs had previously been studied with a questionnaire sent to veterinarians which collected information on how antimicrobials were used with different animal species for one week. The largest group of medicines (calculated as kg of active substance) was β -lactams (86%), followed by aminoglycosides (6%) and sulphonamides combined with trimethoprim (5%) (Rantala 2003).

In Finland, dairies use the T101-screening test in their own checks for antimicrobial residues in raw milk (Valio, Finland), but rarely use other tests. In theory, the T101-test can detect almost all the antimicrobials approved for use with cattle, but in practice it can only detect benzylpenicillin, cephalexin, neomycin, pirlimycin and spiramycin at MRLs (Valio 2003).

According to chemical analyses, the most common residue causing a T101-test positive result is benzylpenicillin. Other antimicrobial residues, such as streptomycin as well as ampicillin and cloxacillin are occasionally found. There is no laboratory data on other substances in milk and their possible concentrations in milk are not known (EELA 2003a).

We can assume that test-positive raw milk, as well as any feed made from such milk, contains only those antimicrobial drug residues which can be detected by the T101-tests done at dairies. In order to identify the possible antimicrobial residues in feed, we calculated for all antimicrobials approved for treating cattle in Finland a **“theoretical maximum concentration”** of residues in milk which under current medical practice can be excreted from one treated cow into milk. In the calculation we assumed that all milk containing antimicrobial residues would be milked during two days into one farm tank. In terms of intramammary treatment, we assumed that treatment would be given in two quarters (and with dry cow therapy medication is given in four quarters) and that 100% of the antimicrobials used in intramammary therapy would be excreted in milk. According to the literature, only 0.005–2% of

drugs given as injections are excreted into milk. The raw milk in the farm tank would be collected by the transportation truck and the T101-test performed at the dairy facility. This **theoretical maximum concentration** was compared to the sensitivity of the T101-test, thus allowing us to calculate what antimicrobial residues would possibly end up in feed via test-positive raw milk.

On the basis of this theoretical maximum concentration, we estimated that the T101-test is only sensitive enough to identify ampicillin, benzylpenicillin, cloxacillin and cephalexin after several farm tanks are combined in one 10,000 litre transportation truck tank of raw milk.

Aminoglycosides and novobiocin are only used in preparations which also contain β -lactams. The residue concentrations of aminoglycosides and novobiocin are diluted under the detection limits of the T101-test, however, and so cannot be detected in raw milk in tests at the dairy. Nevertheless, combination drugs containing β -lactams would result in a positive test, and we can therefore assume that aminoglycosides and novobiocin might also end up in feed containing rejected raw milk.

Based on these theoretical maximum concentrations, we assume that feed containing T101-test positive raw milk could possibly have residues of the following antimicrobial drugs (Figure 1):

- Ampicillin
- Benzylpenicillin
- Dihydrostreptomycin
- Framycetin
- Cephalexin
- Cloxacillin
- Neomycin
- Novobiocin
- Streptomycin

The **potential hazards** referred to in this report are the antimicrobials listed above.

Although we do not in this report analyze the risks to humans from antimicrobial drug residues that might be present in milk, we can nevertheless state that based on these theoretical maximum concentrations, all other antimicrobials besides the ones listed above are diluted during the collection process below approved MRLs. The use of such milk for human consumption, therefore, is approved by the EU.

3.2.2 Hazard characterisation

Fattening pigs, sows and calves are exposed to antimicrobial drug residues through eating feed which has T101-test positive milk as one of its components.

In order to assess the seriousness and magnitude of risks to animals whose feed contains antimicrobial drug residues, we compare their exposure to acceptable daily intake (ADI) values. ADI-values are usually only used when determining the safety hazards of antimicrobial residues for humans. ADI-values are determined on the basis of toxicological, microbiological and pharmacological studies to calculate the amount of residue that can be ingested over a lifetime without increasing individual health risks.

In this report, we only use toxicological ADI-values to assess the safety of animal exposure. Since ADI-values are determined by using the most sensitive animal species, it is appropriate to use them for assessing the safety of pigs and calves as well. The highest concentration where no adverse effects are observed in the test animal after long-term exposure is extrapolated with the help of a wide safety factor to determine safe levels for humans. These safety factors also correct for intraspecies and

*only used in combination with β-lactams in cattle

Figure 1.

Classification of antimicrobial drug residues based on “theoretical maximum concentrations,” the sensitivity of the T101-test, MRLs and standard uses of combination drugs. Raw milk used as feed can contain antimicrobial residues whose theoretical maximum concentration is above the detection limit of the T101-test. In addition, aminoglycosides and novobiocin used in combination with these antimicrobials can also end up via raw milk in feed.

interspecies variability (EMA 2004b). No ADI-values have been set for different animal species, however. Since there is no reason to assume that pigs or calves would be more sensitive to antimicrobial drug residues than humans, and also because the expected lifetime of these animals (and hence also their exposures) are significantly shorter than for humans, we determined that ADI-values originally set for humans could be used to assess the risks to pigs and calves exposed to antimicrobial drug residues via feed (Table 1).

In order for antimicrobial drug residues to concentrate in animal tissue and therefore end up in the human food chain, orally-ingested antimicrobial drug residues must be absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Given a lack of data about pig absorption, we gathered data about human absorption. Since pigs and humans have similar digestive systems, we can assume that absorption is similar. Calf absorption is weaker than pig (Table 2).

Table 1.

Toxicological ADI-values for the antimicrobials which were identified as potential hazards

Active substance	Toxicological ADI µg/kg/day
β-lactams	
Ampicillin	200 ^{a*}
Benzylpenicillin	0.5 ^b
Cephalexin	500 ^b
Cloxacillin	200 ^a
Aminoglycosides	
Dihydrostreptomycin	25 ^b
Framycetin	60 ^b
Neomycin	60 ^b
Streptomycin	25 ^b
Other	
Novobiocin	20 ^b

^aAustralian Government (2003)

*ADI for ampicillin is not determined.

Assumption is made that it equals the ADI of amoxicillin

^bEMEA (2003)

Table 2.

The absorption of orally-ingested antimicrobials which were identified as potential hazards

Active substance	Oral bioavailability % pigs	Oral bioavailability % calves
β-lactams		
Ampicillin	55 ^{a1}	4.5 ^{f3}
Benzylpenicillin	30 ^{b2}	7 ^{g3}
Cephalexin	100 ^{a1}	29 ^{h3}
Cloxacillin	30–80 ^{c1}	d/a
Aminoglycosides		
Dihydrostreptomycin	1 ^{d1}	d/a
Framycetin	1 ^{d1}	d/a
Neomycin	1 ^{d1}	0.4 ⁱ³
Streptomycin	1 ^{d1}	d/a
Other		
Novobiocin	30 ^{e2}	d/a

^aMacGregor & Graziani (1997)

^bUSP DI (2003)

^cToxnet (2004a)

^dToxnet (2004c)

^eEMEA (2003)

^fZiv et al. (1977)

^gMusser & Anderson (2001)

^hSoback et al. (1987)

ⁱPedersoli et al. (1994)

d/a= data not available

¹ based on human data

² based on animal data

³ based on cattle data

3.2.3 Exposure assessment

In the exposure assessment we first describe the route whereby raw milk rejected at the dairy makes its way into animal feed. Based on this information, we then create a simulation model to assess the probable concentrations of antimicrobial drugs in feed and hence the exposure of animals.

3.2.3.1 Exposure route

When a load of milk arrives at the dairy, samples from the transportation truck and trailer are taken to check for antimicrobial drug residues. Sample collecting procedures vary case by case. If the T101-test or a supplemental Snap-test (Idexx, USA) give a positive test result, the following measures are immediately taken (Laitinen 2002; NFA 2003a):

1. Determine which part of the load is test-positive, and unload it into a silo reserved for milk by-products.
2. If the milk lot containing inhibitory substances is accidentally unloaded into a regular raw milk silo, all the milk in that silo is rejected without further testing silo.
3. Possible micropipette samples from each farm on that route are analysed or samples are collected from the farms in question as soon as possible to identify the farm which has delivered milk with a positive test result.
4. A consultant of the dairy cooperative contacts the farm.
5. Inspection authorities are informed about the incident. Usually the district veterinarian from the state provincial office inspects the farm and audits its medical records.
6. The dairy cooperative imposes a fine based on the extent of the damage.
7. If antimicrobial drug residues are found again within three years in raw milk from the same farm, the authorities place the farm under surveillance.

Using questionnaires, the NFA collected information about test-positive raw milk loads in 2002 (47 cases) and from the beginning of 2003 (13 cases - the total number of positive cases in 2003 was 37). The average volume of rejected raw milk was 10,000 litres/load. Of these 60 test-positive cases, the rejected milk most commonly became animal feed (72%). Raw milk could be mixed at dairy with other dairy by-products, such as rinse milk, whey or sour milk (60% of cases), where the dilution factor was on average 3.9. Mixing could also take place directly in the transportation tanks of feed distributing companies (23% of cases), in which case the dilution factor was on average 4.4 (NFA 2003b). Rejected raw milk could also be sent undiluted straight from the dairy to pig farms, in which case it was diluted with the addition of extra PFB (protein feed from barley) (16% of cases). Loads which were not diluted at the dairy were diluted at the farms with an average dilution factor of 5.8. Some of the rejected loads (13%) were used as fertilizer, were destroyed, or were buried in landfills. For the rest of the cases (15%), use was not determined (KTTK 2004a).

T101-test positive loads are rejected without chemical verification. For this reason, the cause of the test-positive result is usually not identified and the concentration is not determined. In some cases, the dairy, producer, or veterinarian wants the sample to be studied further, and antimicrobial residues are verified chemically. These assignments are performed by EELA. In 2001-03, EELA analyzed 5 samples from farm tanks, 12 samples from transportation truck tanks and raw milk samples from three individual cows. These analyses mainly found benzylpenicillin, as well as individual cases of ampicillin and cloxacillin. The concentrations of streptomycin in samples containing it did not go over the T101-test's detection limit (EELA 2003a; EELA

2003b). The positive T101-test had probably been caused by benzylpenicillin, which was found in all samples containing streptomycin. In this assessment, we were able to get reliable figures only for exposures to benzylpenicillin. For other antimicrobial residues, we used the theoretical maximum concentration when estimating residue concentrations (see chapter 5.1.4).

The KTTK did a follow-up survey on the use of T101-positive raw milk as feed in 2002 and beginning of 2003 based on the positive raw milk cases at dairies recorded earlier by the NFA. Of these positive loads, 78% were traced back to the farms responsible. All of these raw milk loads ended up at pig farms, where there was an average of 900 fattening pigs. Of these farms, 27% were combination farms, which in addition to fattening pigs had an average of 200 sows. A total of 30 farms accepted these loads, of which 3 were outside Finnish borders (KTTK 2004a). The 27 Finnish farms represent 0.7% of pig farms in Finland (Tietovakka 2003). After the completion of the actual study, additional information received in spring 2004 revealed that two calf farms had received rejected raw milk. Raw milk had been used in the calf's total mixed ration. The dilution of rejected raw milk at the calf farm was similar to that of pig farms (KTTK 2004b).

Each farm accepting rejected raw milk received an average of 16,000 litres of a mixture of raw milk and other dairy by-products, which were emptied into a storage silo at the farm. These silos might also already contain other feed components such as PFB or whey, so that the concentrations of residues in the raw milk would have been diluted still further. Due to a lack of data, however, we did not take this additional dilution into account when estimating final exposures.

The final feed is prepared at farms immediately before each feeding. Dairy by-products are transferred to a mixing tank, where other feed components, such as PFB, ground grain, water, acid and vitamin and mineral concentrate are mixed together and allowed to stand for approximately 30 minutes before feeding. During feed preparation, the concentration of antimicrobial residues was diluted by an average factor of 2.6. The optimal pH of feed is 4.2–4.5, and optimal temperature of +20 – +30°C (Kuoppala et al. 2004; KTTK 2004c).

Taken together, the concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues are diluted at the dairy and at the farm by an average factor of 14 (range 0.3–300) compared to concentrations in the transportation truck.

According to farmers, the amount of feed used for each animal varies by the animal's size. A full-grown fattening pig was estimated to eat 10 litres, sows 28 litres and calves 9 litres a day of the final feed mixture. Feed made from one load of T101-test positive raw milk was fed to animals an average of 3.6 days (range 1-6 days). Forty percent of the pig farms received only one load of T101-test positive raw milk during the time of the study. Other farms received an average of two such loads (range 1-4 loads) in four months, the life of a fattening pig (KTTK 2004a; KTTK 2004b). The two calf farms revealed after this study to have accepted rejected raw milk had received it just once.

3.2.3.2 The simulation model

In order to simulate the exposure of animals to antimicrobial residues, we constructed a model describing the successive dilutions. It contains five steps, each dependent on the others, where the result of one step is used as an input in the following step. The five steps in the model take into account the information presented above. The basic structure of the model includes:

1. Quantity of milk and concentrations of residues in a transportation truck.

Input for the quantity of milk is given as a probability distribution. Input for the con-

centration of benzylpenicillin is in the form of a probability distribution, while other possible antimicrobial drug residue concentrations in the transportation truck are expressed as point estimates from the worst case scenarios. These probability distributions are based on the NFA survey and EELA laboratory results (NFA 2003b; EELA 2003a).

2. **Dilution in dairy plant silo or feed truck.** Alternative input values for quantities in the silo or feed truck in which the T101-test positive lot of milk is diluted are given as probability distributions. There is also an option of no pre-farm dilution at this step. Data is based on the NFA and EELA surveys (NFA 2003b; EELA 2003b).
3. **Dilution in feed storage silos.** Input is given as a point estimate of the dilution factor, with data based on the KTTK survey (KTTK 2004a).
4. **End dilution of the final feed mixture.** Input is given as a dilution factor, with data based on the KTTK survey (KTTK 2004a). The results of steps 1–4 are the quantity of feed mixture containing antimicrobial residue and the concentration of the residue in it.
5. **Daily and total exposure of animals** (pigs, sows and calves) to residues. Feeding practices are obtained from the KTTK survey. The amount of feed consumed per day and the number of days the feed is given to pigs, sows or calves is averaged from the questionnaire data (KTTK 2004a). Comparison of these daily exposures to the human ADI-values for antimicrobial drugs is included for reference purposes.

We applied Monte Carlo simulation techniques to generate most probable outcomes (result distributions) of exposures. The simulation model was implemented on Excel spreadsheet program (Microsoft Corporation, USA), with a commercial Excel add-in module for risk analysis (@Risk, version 4.5.2, Palisade Corporation, USA). For each simulation, there was a minimum of 10,000 iterations, or possible dilution scenarios.

The model makes the following basic assumptions:

- The detected benzylpenicillin concentrations represent the true population in a load of rejected raw milk. The distribution of observed values conforms satisfactorily with lognormal distribution and the latter was employed in the model.
- For other antimicrobial drug residue concentrations, we assume that the theoretical maximum concentrations represent the actual maximum concentrations.
- The final concentration of residue in feed depends on the probability distributions of the dilution steps.
- Daily exposure consists of two factors: the final antimicrobial drug residue concentration in feed and the amount of feed eaten daily.
- Full-grown fattening pigs are estimated to weigh 100 kg and to eat 10 litres of the final feed mixture per day. These figures are based on data gathered from farmers on the feeding of fattening pigs.
- Sows are estimated to weigh 200 kg and to eat 28 litres of the final feed mixture per day. These figures are based on data gathered from farmers on the feeding of sows.
- Calves are estimated to weigh 90 kg and to eat 9 litres of the final feed mixture per day. These figures are based on data gathered from farmers on the feeding of calves.
- Daily exposures are proportioned to the body weight of animals.
- Human toxicological ADI-values can be used as reference values for the safety of antimicrobial drug residues in feed.

- Daily exposure to amounts of antimicrobial drugs not exceeding the human toxicological ADI-values is considered safe for animals.

The model provides probability distributions of the concentrations of antimicrobial residues in feed, daily exposures, and the percentage of the ADI-values of these exposures.

The simulation model of each dilution phase is based on a wide range of information about normal practices, and can therefore be considered fairly reliable.

3.2.4 Risk characterisation

Using the model, it is possible to estimate the daily exposure of fattening pigs, sows and calves to different antimicrobial drug residues. Exposures were estimated using concentrations derived from dilution at the dairy plant, as this was the most common. In addition, this option has the lowest dilution, so the results cannot be considered overly optimistic.

According to the simulation model, the average concentration of benzylpenicillin in a final feed mixture was 2.5 µg/litre [90% of results 0–5.8 µg/litre]. The average daily exposure proportioned to the body weight of exposed animals is 0.25 µg/kg/day for fattening pigs [90% of results 0–0.6 µg/kg/day] and 0.36 µg/kg/day for sows [90% of results 0–0.8 µg/kg/day] on those days when they were fed feed containing antimicrobial residues (average 3.6 days). Calves were exposed to 0.24 µg/kg/day of benzylpenicillin [90% of results 0–0.6 µg/kg/day], for an average of 9 days per load.

Compared to the toxicological ADI-value of benzylpenicillin set for humans, these average exposure doses represent approximately 50% (fattening pigs), 71% (sows) and 50% (calves) of the toxicologically acceptable daily intake dose. Over 80% of the simulation results stayed below the toxicological ADI-value for all animal groups evaluated.

Exposures to other antimicrobial drug residues were estimated using scenarios based on theoretical maximum exposures. The daily exposure of calves, fattening pigs and sows to ampicillin, cloxacillin, framycetin, neomycin and novobiocin re-

Table 3.

The simulated average antimicrobial concentrations in feed of ampicillin, cephalixin and cloxacillin exceeded MRLs set for raw milk. The average daily intake of fattening pigs, sows and calves remained under human toxicological ADI-values for all the antimicrobials evaluated.

Antimicrobial residue	Simulated average concentration in feed µg/litre	MRL (raw milk) µg/litre	Simulated average daily exposure µg/kg/day			Toxicological ADI-value µg/kg/day
			Fattening pigs	Sows	Calves	
			Ampicillin	18.8 *	4	
Benzylpenicillin	2.5	4	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.5
Cephalexin	112.7	100	11.3	15.8	11.2	500
Cloxacillin	37.5	30	3.8	5.3	3.7	200
Dihydrostreptomycin	113.2 *	200	11.3	15.8	11.2	25
Framycetin	7.5 *	1,500	0.8	1.0	0.7	60
Neomycin	33.6	1,500	3.4	4.8	3.3	60
Novobiocin	30.1	100	3.0	4.1	3.0	20
Streptomycin	165.6	200	16.5	23.2	16.3	25

*Concentration in feed exceed MRL set for raw milk

mained well under (>98% of results) the toxicological ADI-values. Exposure to dihydrostreptomycin and streptomycin was slightly higher, but the average exposure remained well under the **toxicological ADI-value** for both pigs and calves (Table 3).

3.2.5 Validation of the model

The model was validated using data collected after the period under study, though this data was not used in constructing the model. Samples of rejected test-positive milk from the end of 2003 and beginning of 2004 were sent to EELA, where they were chemically-analysed for antimicrobial residues. We traced two loads rejected at the dairy to use at 16 farms. In connection with these cases we also got the first information about test-positive milk lots ending up at calf rearing units.

The average concentration of benzylpenicillin in feed at these 16 farms was 0.5 µg/litre (standard deviation 0.3 µg/litre). This result is well in line with the results of the simulation model, so we can conclude that the model provides fairly reliable predictions of the dilution process of antimicrobial drug residues in feed.

3.2.6 Available risk management options

We studied the effectiveness of three options to reduce the amount of antimicrobial residues in feed: controlling the temperature, the pH, or using enzymatic products.

3.2.6.1 Heat treatment

We studied the effect of heat treatment on the degradation of antimicrobial residues in three different heating processes:

- Pasteurisation at 72°C for 15 seconds.
- UHT-processing at 135°C for one second.
- Dry milk processing: the process begins at a maximum temperature of 120°C (3 minutes), after which the evaporation temperature is 50–70°C (20 minutes). Final drying is done at 80–90°C for a few seconds (Valio 2004).

Antimicrobials degrade slowly in heat treatment. For example, at 71°C 100% degradation of benzylpenicillin requires a minimum of 28 hours. Thus, pasteurisation does not lower the concentrations of antimicrobials in milk (Shanani 1958).

In order to degrade 100% of benzylpenicillin and aminoglycoside residues in milk, a temperature of at least 100°C would be needed for 5 hours (Pilet et al. 1969) (see Annex 6). We therefore conclude that the heating processes described above cannot be used to significantly reduce antimicrobial drug residues in milk.

3.2.6.2 Acidification of feed

We studied the acidification of feed based on current practices:

- The optimal pH of pig feed is 4–5.
- Acidification lowering the pH to this level happens during the feed mixing procedure, which takes place only 30 minutes before feeding.
- Other by-products used to dilute raw milk, such as whey and PFB, are sour (pH 4–5), so the pH of rejected milk can be lowered to a pH near 5 for several days prior to feeding.

Nearly all antimicrobial substances studied were stable in the range of pH 4–5. Generally speaking, the degradation of antimicrobials requires the extreme ends of the pH scale, either totally acidic or alkaline solutions. The minimum time required to reduce 50% of ampicillin at pH 4 was 50 hours (Hou & Poole 1969). Only benzylpenicillin and cloxacillin might degrade somewhat in these conditions. Unfortunately, little

is known about degradation kinetics at pHs at or around 4. In addition, the effects of acidification on feed have mainly been studied at higher temperatures than normal feed (max +30°C), where degradation reactions are faster. Therefore, degradation in feed is likely to be even slower than in the test conditions (see Annex 6).

We can conclude that feed acidification has only a negligible effect on antimicrobial residues in feed, and cannot therefore be considered an effective method of reducing residues in feed containing T101-test positive raw milk.

3.2.6.3 Enzymatic products

If using enzymatic products to degrade antimicrobial drug residues in milk, the following should be taken into account:

- β -Lactamase is the only commercial enzymatic product available in Finland which is designed to degrade antimicrobial drug residues in milk.
- The enzyme hydrolyzes the cyclic β -lactam ring.
- β -Lactamase only degrades benzylpenicillin, amoxicillin and ampicillin.
- It does not degrade other antimicrobials.

If commercial enzymatic products are used to reduce antimicrobial residues in rejected raw milk, the enzyme should be added to the raw milk before it is mixed with other by-products, since any change in pH might reduce the enzymatic effect. If raw milk is mixed with products whose pH is the same as that of raw milk, however, β -lactamase can be added to the mixture even after dilution. The enzyme should be allowed to work at least 12 hours or more, depending on the degree of degradation wanted and the original level of residues (Vetcare 2003; Korycka-Dahl et al. 1985).

According to the manufacturer, one ml (24,000 units of β -lactamase) of this commercial product (Antipen™) is sufficient to degrade all penicillin residues in 40 litres of milk directly milked from a treated cow (Vetcare 2003).

Effective use of β -lactamase requires accurate information about both the active substance found in milk and its concentration. Studies have shown that 100% of benzylpenicillin degrades in 24 hours if enough β -lactamase is used (Korycka-Dahl et al. 1985). β -Lactamase effectively degrades benzylpenicillin and aminopenicillins, but is useless if the raw milk contains other antimicrobial residues.

3.3 Hazard identification of pathogens

Raw milk which, according to the T101-test, contains an agent inhibiting the growth of the test microbe, is not treated at the dairy (with the exception of possible mixing with other by-products). Thus, being a non-heat-treated raw product it might contain infectious agents found at the milk-producing farm.

In connection with this project, we studied viral, bacterial and parasitic diseases which can in theory spread via T101-test positive raw milk from a dairy farm to a farm using feed made from such milk. We focused on bovine infectious diseases on the World Organization for Animal Health's (OIE) list A and list B, as well as on reportable zoonoses in the EU's new Council Directive of Zoonotic Diseases. A total of 38 infectious diseases were studied. Conclusions about these diseases are based on:

- The current animal disease situation in Finland
- The epidemiology of the infections and diseases
- The excretion of the infectious agent into milk
- The possibility of milk contamination by pathogens in faeces or urine

We also present a short analysis of the effectiveness of risk management options on pathogens which perhaps require further risk assessment.

The conclusions of this analysis are presented in Table 4. For each infectious disease, we estimate the likelihood that T101-test positive milk would serve as a carrier of the disease. We used the scale: no hazard (1), negligible hazard, no need for further risk assessment (2), and possible hazard which might require further risk assessment (3).

We have determined that, of the 38 diseases assessed, intestinally-carried campylobacter, enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli* (EHEC) and *Listeria monocytogenes* infections are the possible hazards.

It is worth keeping in mind that T101-test positive milk represents only a small fraction of the milk rejected at dairies for various reasons. Milk rejected due to a high cell count, sourness or a foul odour might contain significantly higher concentrations of bacteria. Of the current risk management options, the acidification of liquid feed to a pH of 4–5 reduces the amount of campylobacter and listeria bacteria, but has only limited effect on enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) bacteria. All three infectious agents, however, are quickly destroyed by heat-treatment comparable to pasteurisation.

Table 4.

Pathogens possibly spread via milk and identification of the need for further risk assessment.

Disease	^a Last reported occurrence in Finland	Official disease status	^b Secreted into milk or faecal contamination a known route	^c Need for further risk assessment
Foot and mouth disease	1959	Free	3	1
Vesicular stomatitis	0	N	2	1
Rinderpest	1877	Free	1	1
Contagious bovine pleuropneumonia	1920	N	0	1
Lumpy skin disease	0	N	0	1
Rift Valley fever	0	N	1	1
Bluetongue	0	N	1	1
Anthrax	1988	N	1	1
Aujeszky's disease	0	Free	0	1
Echinococcosis (<i>E. granulosus</i>)	2003	N	0	1
Heartwater	0	N	0	1
Leptospirosis	2002	N	1	2
Q-fever	0	N	2	1
Rabies	1988	Free	0	1
Paratuberculosis	2001	N	3	2
Screwworm (both old and new world)	0	N	0	1
Bovine anaplasmosis	0	N	0	1
Bovine babesiosis	2003	N	0	1
Bovine brucellosis	1960	Free	3	1
Bovine cysticercosis (<i>C. bovis</i>)	2002	N	0	1
Bovine genital campylobacteriosis	0	N	0	1
Bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE)	2001	N	0	1
Bovine tuberculosis	1982	Free	3	1
Dermatophilosis	0	N	0	1
Enzootic bovine leukosis	1996	N	1	1
Haemorrhagic septicaemia	0	N	0	1
Infectious bovine rhinotracheitis (IBR/IBV)	1994	N	1	1
Malignant catarrhal fever	2003	N	1	1
Theileriosis	0	N	0	1
Trichomonosis	1952	N	0	1
Trypanosomosis	0	N	0	1
Campylobacteriosis (intestinal)	2003	N	3	3
Listeriosis	2003	N	3	3
Salmonellosis	2003	N	3	2
EHEC infection	2003	N	3	3
Yersiniosis	2003	N	2	2
Cryptosporidiosis	2003	N	1	2
Toxoplasmosis	2003	N	0	2

^a Reported before 31.12.2003

0 = Never

N = No official status

^b 0: No

1: Possible but epidemiologically insignificant

2: Possible

3: Yes

^c 1: No hazard, no need for further assessment

2: Negligible hazard, no need further assessment

3: Possible hazard, may need further assessment

3.4 Conclusions

Conclusions based on the situation in 2002-2003

1. Antimicrobial drug residues in test-positive raw milk rejected at the dairy and feed made from this milk do not pose a toxicological health risks to pigs and calves in the current situation.
2. When raw milk from a transportation truck is tested at the dairy, possible drug residue concentrations have been diluted to the extent that in practice residue test can only detect ampicillin, benzylpenicillin, cephalexin, and cloxacillin. Aminoglycosides and novobiocin are used in cattle only in combination with benzylpenicillin and cephalexin, so even though residue test at dairies cannot detect aminoglycosides and novobiocin, they might end up in feed via raw milk testing positive for benzylpenicillin or cloxacillin residues.
3. Since the antimicrobials mentioned in point 2 constitute the majority of antimicrobials used on cattle, with the help of the dairy test it is possible to prevent a significant portion of raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues from going via prepared food stuffs to the consumer.
4. According to the assessment, concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues other than those mentioned in point 2 have, by the time they arrive at the dairy, been diluted to the point where they are under the maximum residue limits (MRL) set by the EU.
5. The heat-treatment of raw milk or the acidification of feed do not significantly decrease the concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues. On the other hand, treating raw milk with β -lactamase enzymes effectively lowers the concentrations of benzylpenicillin and aminopenicillins, but it has no effect on other antimicrobial drug residues.
6. The risks to consumers from the use of raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues as animal feed is not considered in this report. However, based on the very low exposures of animals to these residues we can conclude that the risks of human exposure to antimicrobial residues via pork or beef meat are very small in the current situation.
7. When using raw milk rejected due to a positive test for antimicrobial drug residues as feed, Intestinally-carried campylobacter, enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) and *Listeria monocytogenes* are possible hazards, which may warrant a further risk assessment.

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4 Introduction

Milk which contains antimicrobial drug residues above maximum residue limits (MRL) set by the European Union (Council regulation 2377/90) is unfit for human consumption and should not be delivered to dairy plants. Despite intensive control of the use of antimicrobials, occasionally some quantities of raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues do end up at dairy plants, however.

Each EU member state runs a national residue control program (NRCP), and inspection of antimicrobial drug residues in milk is one part of this program. In Finland, approximately 300 raw milk samples are analysed annually with chemical methods accepted by the EU. In addition, ca. 2,000 raw milk samples are tested with the microbiological T101-screening test. Since 1999, only one positive raw milk sample has been confirmed with chemical methods to contain antimicrobial drug residues (EELA/MMM 2000; EVI/EELA/MMM 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004).

In addition to the national residue control program, national legislation (MMM 31/EEO/2001) requires that each raw milk lot arriving at a dairy plant is tested for antimicrobial drug residues as part of the operator's own checks. In Finland, therefore, over 135,000 raw milk samples are annually tested for inhibitory substances as part of these checks by dairy operators. The most commonly used microbiological screening test for this purpose is the T101-test (Valio, Finland). Raw milk which tests positive with this inhibitory test is not used in food production. The T101-test is not required and is not an officially-accepted test method in the EU, but the national authorities in Finland allow operators to use it in their own checks. The T101-test positive milk referred to in this report is raw milk containing substances inhibiting the growth of test microbes in milk. Similarly, in this report the inhibitory substance in raw milk is referred to as antimicrobial drug residue.

In 2002, 47 transportation lots contained inhibitory agents detected by the T101-test, with the result that over 545,000 kg of milk was not suitable for human consumption. In 2003, the corresponding numbers were 37 transport lots and 360,000 kg of milk. These test-positive lots were either destroyed or used after dilution as animal feed (NFA 2004).

T101-test positive raw milk represents only a small fraction of all dairy by-products. In normal operations, rinse milk, sour milk, whey and whey concentrate are the most important by-products which are used as feed. According to Valio Ltd, the largest milk refiner in Finland, T101-test positive milk represents about 0.3–0.4% of all dairy by-products (Konttinen, personal communication).

In autumn 2003, concerned about the possible risks to food-producing animals of using T101-test positive raw milk in feed, the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM) asked the National Veterinary and Food Research Institute (EELA) to assess

these risks. To support this effort, an expert group was established consisting of individual experts from different fields.

4.1 Legislation and concerns

Due to new EU regulations on animal by-products, there is concern about raw milk containing inhibitory substances being used for animal feed. According to Article 6 of Regulation 1774/2002, category 3 animal by-products can be used as animal feed, including raw milk which is discarded after delivery to dairies. This milk might be discarded based on sensory and other quality defects, failures in temperature regulation, and accidental addition of water or other ingredients to raw milk.

According to Article 5 of Regulation 1774/2002, the use of officially tested milk containing antimicrobial drug residues above MRLs (category 2 animal products) is banned. There are no rules concerning the use of raw milk which tests inhibitory positive as part of the operators' own checks as animal feed. However, according to feed legislation, feeds should not pose a danger to animals, to human health or to the environment.

The current practice of using these by-products as a component in animal feed has been justified on the basis of Finland's animal disease status and the fact that the raw milk is produced domestically. Mandatory heat-treatment of dairy by-products has not been applied in Finland due to the significant investments involved in such an operation. The concern is that the operation is too marginal to cover the costs and dairies would have to seek alternative methods which would then be a burden to the waste disposal systems. Another concern is that instead of testing each milk lot arriving at dairy plants, the protocol would be changed so that the screening test would be performed only after several truck loads were combined into a silo. Residues would then be diluted in the process and so might not be detected with a screening test, and would thus end up in human consumption.

4.2 Objectives

The focus of this study was to identify and characterise the hazards of antimicrobial drug residues in milk and to conduct an exposure assessment in order to help characterise the risks to pigs and calves that eat the feed containing test-positive raw milk. Pathogenic hazards in test-positive milk were also identified in order to determine the need for a proper risk assessment in the future. We also provide a brief description of the disease status in Finland of the main pathogens of bovine origin which have the potential to spread via raw milk.

A simulation model of the dilution process was built to obtain the most probable concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues in feed. Average daily exposures of pigs and calves for antimicrobial drug residues were compared to existing toxicological ADI-values set for humans.

This report is divided into two parts according to the hazards involved:

1. We first identify and characterise antimicrobial drug residues, which might be potential hazards in feed containing test positive raw milk. Then we describe the route and the process of making feed from T101-test positive raw milk rejected at the dairy plant. An exposure assessment is conducted to evaluate the antimicrobial drug residue concentrations in feed and to compare the animal exposure

levels to human ADI-values.

2. We also identify significant pathogens possibly present in test-positive raw milk, but conduct no further risk assessment.

This report does not evaluate human risks, nor does it discuss the issue of antimicrobial resistance. Furthermore, it is limited to the area of Finland and does not consider possible imports of raw milk.

In 2000, a MMM working group of experts was set up to evaluate the environmental impact of animal medication. Although they found that there was only a small amount of antimicrobial residues in milk which tested positive for these residues at the dairy, they nevertheless concluded that it might be worthwhile to look into methods to reduce antibiotic activity in milk. This would require research into aspects of food safety and the legal basis of these methods (MMM 2000a).

5 Risk assessment of antimicrobial drug residues

This risk assessment of antimicrobial drug residues includes four steps: hazard identification and characterisation, exposure assessment and risk characterisation.

Figure 2. Stepwise procedure of the risk assessment on antimicrobial drug residues and factors taken into consideration.

5.1 Hazard identification

The purpose of this section is to

- describe the use of antimicrobials in cattle treatment
- describe the test methods used to detect residues in raw milk
- identify those antimicrobials which might be found in feed due to the usage of T101-test positive raw milk as one feed component
- describe the properties of those antimicrobials which are identified as potential hazards

5.1.1 Control of the usage of antimicrobial drugs in Finland

In Finland, only licensed veterinarians are authorized to use and prescribe prescription drugs for animals. Treatment must be justified based on animal welfare or medical need and decisions are made in co-operation between the veterinarian and animal owner.

Veterinarians are authorized to prescribe drugs only if they have examined the animal or have otherwise confirmed the need for medical treatment. Veterinarians are obliged to keep records of purchased and further distributed and sold drugs (MMM 23/EEO/2002).

Owners of food-producing animals are also obliged to keep records of the drugs used for each animal (MMM 13/EEO/2000).

Since 1998, the national residue control program has annually tested ca. 100–200 raw milk samples for unlicensed drugs (chloramphenicol) in Finland. No positive samples have been detected (EELA/MMM 1999, 2000; EVI/EELA/MMM 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004).

Due to these regulations and the results of the NRCP, the medication of domestic animals can be considered well-controlled and illegal use of drugs can be estimated to be very low.

5.1.2 Antimicrobial drugs used for cattle treatment

In Finland, the total sales of veterinary medicines is monitored by the National Agency for Medicines. In 2002, 13,200 kg (calculated as kg of active substance) of antimicrobials were sold for veterinary use (Figure 3). β -Lactams were the major group of antimicrobials used, and benzylpenicillin alone represented 46% of antimicrobials sold (Koppinen et al. 2003).

Antimicrobials are administered to animals by injection (intravenously, intramuscularly, or subcutaneously), orally in food or water, topically on the skin and by intramammary infusions (Figure 4).

Most antimicrobial drugs are authorised for the treatment of several animal species, and the exact amount of antimicrobial drugs used for cattle is not known. However, all sold intramammary tubes can be assumed to be used for dairy cattle as antimicrobials are not given orally for dairy cattle. Only the amount of active substances given as injections to cattle is not known precisely.

Figure 3. Total sale of antimicrobial veterinary drugs (kg of active substances) (Koppinen et al. 2003).

Figure 4. Application methods of antimicrobial veterinary drugs (Koppinen et al. 2003).

The use of antimicrobial drugs had previously been studied with a questionnaire sent to veterinarians which collected information on how antimicrobials were used with different animal species for one week. The largest group of medicines (calculated as kg of active substance) was β -lactams (86%), followed by aminoglycosides (6%) and sulphonamides combined with trimethoprim (5%) (Rantala 2003).

The most common disease of dairy cattle is mastitis. In 2002, 33% of veterinarian calls to cattle farms were due to acute or subclinical mastitis, the main reasons antimicrobial drugs are prescribed for lactating cows (Rautala 2003). A list of authorized veterinary drugs is maintained and updated by the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (Table 5).

5.1.3 Testing methods

The screening of each raw milk lot for inhibitory substances as it arrives at the dairy plant is based on national regulations established by the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 31/EEO/2001). Each transportation lot of raw milk is tested, though several practices and methods have been used to collect the sample from the truck.

The most widely used test is the T101-test (Valio, Finland) which is approved for use in the operators' own checks. Another approved test is the Delvotest (Labimex, Finland), but it is rarely used in Finland. Indeed, according to questionnaires by EELA and EVI, 100% of the respondents normally used the T101-test in their own checks. Some dairy plants use an additional Snap-test (IDEXX, USA), but due to its narrow selection of detectable antimicrobials its usage alone is not approved by the authorities. Chemical confirmation is performed only in unclear situations or when information on the quantity or quality of the inhibitory substance causing a positive result in the microbiological test is needed.

Sensitivities of the tests in use are presented in Table 6.

5.1.3.1 T101-test

The test bacterium in the T101-test is the *Streptococcus thermophilus* T101-strain, which produces lactic acid from lactose. The change in pH is indicated by a change of colour. If the sample contains antimicrobial drug residues above the detection limit of the test, the growth of bacterium is inhibited and no colour change is observed; development of colour requires a 4-hour incubation (Valio 2003a). The result is "posi-

Table 5.
Antimicrobial drugs authorized for the treatment of cattle in Finland.

Group	Active substance	Injection	Intramammary	Indication
Aminopenicillins	Amoxicillin trihydrate	X		Bacterial infection
	*Ampicillin sodium		X	Clinical mastitis
	*Ampicillin trihydrate		X	Mastitis and its prophylaxis
	Ampicillin trihydrate	X		Respiratory and intestinal infections, metritis, cystitis
Penicillins	*Penethamatepenicillin		X	Bacterial mastitis and its prophylaxis
	*Benzylpenicillin		X	Bacterial mastitis and its prophylaxis
	Benzylpenicillin sodium	X		Bacterial infection
	Benzylpenicillin procaine		X	Mastitis therapy
	Benzylpenicillin procaine	X		Bacterial infections, mastitis, pulmonary infections, puerperal genital infections
	*Penethamate hydriodide		X	Mastitis and its prophylaxis
	Penethamate hydriodide	X		Mastitis
Cephalosporins	*Cephalexin monohydrate		X	Bacterial mastitis and its prophylaxis
Cloxacillins	Cloxacillin benzathine		X	Bacterial mastitis and its prophylaxis, clinical mastitis
	*Cloxacillin sodium		X	Mastitis and its prophylaxis
Quinolones	Danofloxacin	X		Respiratory and intestinal infections
	Enrofloxacin	X		Respiratory, intestinal, urinary tract and genital infections, severe mastitis
Aminoglycosides	*Framycetin sulphate		X	Mastitis and its prophylaxis
	*Dihydrostreptomycin sulphate		X	Mastitis and its prophylaxis
	*Streptomycin		X	Mastitis
	*Neomycin sulphate		X	Mastitis and dry cow therapy
Tetracyclines	Oxytetracycline	X		Pasteurellosis and respiratory infections, pneumonia and pasture fever. Alternatively metritis, interdigital necrobacillosis, peritonitis, wound infections, mastitis, enteritis, cystitis, neonatal infections
				Subclinical mastitis
Lincosamides	Pirlimycin hydrochloride		X	Infections caused by micro-organisms
	Spiramycin	X		Respiratory, intestinal, urinary tract and reproductive organ infections
Sulphonamides	*Sulphadiazine	X		Pneumonia, bronchitis, urogenital infections, mastitis, wound infections, sepsis
	*Sulphadoxine	X		Respiratory, intestinal, urinary tract and reproductive organ infections, pneumonia, bronchitis, urogenital infections, mastitis, wound infections, sepsis, combined to sulphonamides
Other	*Trimethoprim	X		Mastitis
	*Novobiocin		X	

*used only in combination medicines

tive” or “negative,” and does not indicate the quantity or quality of the reaction inhibiting agent.

The T101-test detects benzylpenicillin, cephalixin, neomycin, pirlimycin and spiramycin at MRLs (Valio 2003a). According to the veterinarian questionnaire, these drugs represent over 80% of the antimicrobials used (calculated as kg of active substance) for cattle (Rantala 2003).

In addition to antimicrobial drug residues, other growth-inhibiting substances can cause positive results. The microbiological test results should thus be confirmed with chemical methods.

5.1.3.2 Snap-test

Some dairy plants have adopted an additional voluntary test as a precautionary measure in order to get quick results and prevent the contamination of larger amounts of milk. However, the T101-test is always performed to confirm the results.

The Snap-test is an enzyme-linked receptor-binding assay for the screening of benzylpenicillin, ampicillin, cephalixin, amoxicillin and ceftiofur residues in raw milk (IDEXX 2004).

Despite the fact that the Snap-test only detects β -lactam antimicrobials, it is a useful tool for a quick screening of milk since β -lactams are the most common antimicrobials used in treating cattle.

5.1.3.3 Delvotest

The use of the Delvotest (Labimex Ltd.) is marginal in Finland. However, some small dairy plants may still use it and it is approved by the inspection authorities.

The Delvotest SP is a diffusion test. The test bacterium is *Bacillus stearothermophilus var. calidolactis* C953. If the milk sample contains antimicrobial residues, they will diffuse throughout the agar medium and, when present at sufficient concentration, retard or inhibit the multiplication of the germinated spores. During the incubation period, the acid produced will change the colour of the indicator from purple to yellow. If enough acid is not formed, the colour of the indicator stays purple. The result of the screening test is either “positive” or “negative” (Labimex 2004).

5.1.3.4 Chemical analyses

Chemical analyses are more reliable than microbiological tests. They are also more time-consuming and expensive to perform and are therefore mainly used to confirm positive microbiological test results and to specify and quantify the inhibitory substances. They are not suitable for large scale screening. Chemical analyses are important, however, for analysing those antimicrobials for which the microbiological tests are not sensitive enough.

Different antimicrobial groups are analysed with separate methods, all including a sample purification step with solid phase extraction or dialysis and analysis with high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Detection is done with a diode array detector (β -lactams, cephalixin, sulphonamides, and oxytetracycline) or with a fluorescence detector (quinolones, streptomycin, dihydrostreptomycin). An extra confirmation with a penicillinase enzyme is performed to identify β -lactams sensitive to it. The spectrum of the diode array detector is used for confirmation if needed.

All analyses are not performed on all samples, with the size of the sample usually being the limiting factor. The procedure is normally started with β -lactam analysis if the sample size is small. Sometimes there is also information available about the antimicrobials used on the farm where the milk originated.

The exposure assessment in this report is based on the laboratory data of EELA.

The number of analyses performed varied between the samples. Benzylpenicillin, cephalixin, cloxacillin and oxacillin were the most commonly analysed antimicrobials (100% of the tests). Amoxicillin and ampicillin were also analysed in 95% of the samples and dihydrostreptomycin, streptomycin, ciprofloxacin, enrofloxacin and danofloxacin in 45–50% of the samples. 9–27% of the samples were further analysed for the presence of oxytetracycline, sulphadiazine, sulphadimidine, sulphadoxine, sulphametazine, chlortetracycline and tetracycline. Framycetin, neomycin, pirlimycin, spiramycin, trimethoprim and novobiocin have never been tested due to the lack of existing methods in Finland (EELA 2003a) (Annex 1).

Table 6.

Limits of detection for antimicrobial residues in raw milk. Shaded areas indicate limits of detection at or below MRLs.

Active substance	µg/kg				
	MRL ⁽¹⁾	Snap ⁽²⁾	T-101 ⁽³⁾	HPLC ⁽⁴⁾	Delvo SP ⁽⁵⁾
Amoxicillin	4	10	30–50	4	5–10
Ampicillin	4	6	10–30	4	5–10
Benzylpenicillin	4	3	2–4	2	2–3
Cephalixin	100	nd	50–100	50	50–100
Cloxacillin	30	nd	100–150	8	25–30
Oxacillin	30	nd	150–200	8	uk
Danofloxacin	30	nd	uk	2	uk
Enrofloxacin	100	nd	1,000–1,500	5	uk
Ciprofloxacin	100	nd	uk	5	uk
Framycetin	1,500	nd	uk	nm	uk
Neomycin	1,500	nd	300–500	nm	500–1,500
Dihydrostreptomycin	200	nd	1,000–1,500	25	4,000–6,000
Streptomycin	200	nd	1,000–1,500	10	uk
Tetracycline	100	nd	200–300	10	400–1,000
Oxytetracycline	100	nd	200–300	10	300–800
Pirlimycin	100	nd	30–50	nm	uk
Spiramycin	200	nd	150–300	nm	uk
Sulphadiazine	100	nd	300–500	30	250–300
Sulphadoxine	100	nd	500–1,000	30	250–1,000
Trimethoprim	50	nd	2,000–5,000	nm	uk
Novobiocin	50	nd	1,000–1,500	nm	500–2,000

¹Council regulation (2377/90)

nd = not detectable

²IDEXX laboratories (2004)

uk = unknown

³Valio (2003)

nm = no method available in Finland

⁴EELA (2003c)

⁵Labimex (2004)

5.1.4 Possible residues in rejected T101-test positive milk

In theory, the T101-test can detect nearly all the antimicrobial drugs used in treating cattle. However, the detection limit is relatively high for most residues. We can assume that test-positive raw milk, as well as any feed made from such milk, contains only those antimicrobial drug residues which can be detected by the T101-tests done at dairies. In order to identify the possible antimicrobial residues in feed, we calculated for all antimicrobials approved for treating cattle in Finland a “theoretical

maximum concentration” of residues in milk which under current medical practice can be excreted from one treated cow into milk.

In this **worst case scenario**, the theoretically possible maximum concentration of residues in milk was estimated by calculating the recommended therapeutic doses and excretion of residues into milk. Since in normal operations, the milk collection interval at farms is two days, it was assumed that all milk containing antimicrobial residues during that period would be accidentally milked into one farm tank. The farm tank would then be collected by a transportation truck where it would get mixed with milk from other farms. In this process the possible residues dilute extensively. The T101-test detection limits were compared to the concentrations estimated to exist in a 10,000 litre transportation truck tank (average size of a rejected milk lot). Based on this worst case scenario, we made assumptions about which antimicrobial drugs would be detected given standard practices.

The assumptions in this scenario were:

- All milk containing residues during the two days of the recommended treatment was milked into one farm tank
- Only one cow was treated at a time
- Intramammary treatment was used for two infected quarters
- Dry cow therapy was used for four quarters
- If intramammary tubes were used, it was assumed that 100% of the antimicrobial drugs were flushed out with milking. The recovery of antimicrobial drugs into milk depends on the time interval between treatment and milking, the active substances used and other variables not specified in this report. Therefore, a worst case scenario uses a recovery of 100% of each intramammary therapy.
- The average weight of a lactating cow is 600 kg
- Only 0.005–2% of injected drugs were excreted into milk. These values were obtained from literature and were drug-specific.
- The raw milk in the farm tank including all residues from the treatment was collected by transportation truck every two days and the test was performed at the dairy facility. The average amount of rejected milk was 10,000 litres. It was assumed that the test was performed for this amount, but in practice there could be a much larger volume if a collection sample is taken from the whole transportation truck.

These assumptions are overestimations of the normal procedure to obtain the worst case scenario. Table 7 presents a summary of the estimates of the concentrations in transport trucks and comparisons with the detection limits of the T101-test.

Based on the worst case scenario, where raw milk lots are tested at the dairy plant, only certain β -lactam antibacterials (benzylpenicillin, ampicillin, cloxacillin and cephalixin) would be detected by the T101-test and therefore end up in feed which uses rejected raw milk as one component (Table 7). According to the veterinarian questionnaire, these drugs represent approximately 80% of the medicines used on cattle (Rantala 2003).

When raw milk lots are tested at the dairy plant, the worst case concentrations of aminoglycosides and novobiocin exceed the MRLs. However, the worst case concentrations remain below T101-tests detection limits and therefore would not be detected by the test. These antimicrobials are, however, used only in intramammary tubes in combination with β -lactam antibacterials, which are detected by the T101-test. It is therefore reasonable to assume that aminoglycosides and novobiocin may be found in feed containing rejected raw milk.

Based on these assumptions, it is reasonable to believe that feed which contains

Table 7.

The worst case scenario for antimicrobial drug residues in milk. Recommended therapeutic doses in Finland, the number of treatments in 2 days (expected interval between milk collection at farms), treated quarters and excretion into milk are summarised in the table. The theoretically maximum residue concentration in an average rejected tank size at the dairy plants is compared with the sensitivity of the T101-test and MRLs.

Active substance	Injection	Intra-mammary	Dry cow therapy	Therapeutic dose ^a mg/kg	Treatments ^a (2days)	Treated quarters	Total excretion into milk one cow (600kg) mg	Transport truck 10,000 litres C (µg/l)	Detection limit T-101 µg/l	MRL µg/l
Amoxicillin	X			15 mg/kg	2		0.005 ^b = 0.9	0.1	30–50	4
Ampicillin	X	X		7.5 mg/kg	2		0.1% ^c = 9.0	0.9	10–30	4
				75 mg	3	2	100% = 450	45		
				250 mg	1	4	100% = 1,000	100		
Penethamatehydriodide	X		X	15 mg/kg	2		0.03% ^b = 5.4	0.5	2–4	4
				100 mg	1	4	100% = 400	40		
Penethamatepenicillin			X	280 mg	1	4	100% = 1,120	112	2–4	4
Benzylpenicillin sodium	X			9 mg/kg	4		0.03% ^b = 6.5	0.6	2–4	4
Benzylpenicillin procaine	X	X	X	20 mg/kg	2		0.03% ^b = 7.2	0.7	2–4	4
				500 mg	3	2	100% = 3,000	300		
				500 mg	1	4	100% = 2,000	200		
Cephalexin		X	X	500 mg	4	2	100% = 4,000	400	50–100	100
				500 mg	1	4	100% = 2,000	200		
Cloxacillin		X	X	200 mg	3	2	100% = 1,200	120	100–150	30
				500 mg	1	4	100% = 2,000	200		
Danofloxacin	X			1.25 mg/kg	2		0.2% ^d = 3.0	0.3	not known	30
Enrofloxacin	X			5 mg/kg	2		0.2% ^e = 12	1.2	1,000–1,500	100
Framycetin			X	100 mg	1	4	100% = 400	40	not known	1,500
Neomycin	X	X	X	300 mg	2	2	100% = 1,200	120	300–500	1,500
				300 mg	1	4	100% = 1,200	120		
Dihydrostreptomycin		X	X	500 mg	4	2	100% = 4,000	400	1,000–1,500	200
				500 mg	1	4	100% = 2,000	200		
Streptomycin		X		1,100 mg	4	2	100% = 8,800	880	1,000–1,500	200
Oxytetracycline	X			10 mg/kg	2		0.08% ^c = 9.6	1.0	200–300	100
Pirlimycin		X		50 mg	2	2	100% = 200	20	30–50	100
Spiramycin	X			8 mg/kg	2		2% ^d = 192	19	150–300	200
Sulphadiazine	X			20 mg/kg	2		1.1% ^f = 264	26	300–500	100
Sulphadoxine	X			12.5 mg/kg	2		0.5% ^g = 75	7.5	500–1,000	100
Trimethoprim	X			4 mg/kg	2		0.1% ^f = 4.8	0.5	2,000–5,000	50
Novobiocin			X	400 mg	1	4	100% = 1,600	160	1,000–1,500	50

^aPharmaca Veterinaria Fennica (2002)^bMoretain & Boisseau (1984)^cPrescott et al. (2000)^dPyörälä, personal communication (2004)^eKaartinen et al. (1995)^fKaartinen et al. (1999)^gRoudaut & Moretain (1990)

Concentration below the detection limit of the T101-test

T101-test positive raw milk could possibly have residues of the following antimicrobial drugs:

- Ampicillin
- Benzylpenicillin
- Cephalexin
- Cloxacillin
- Framycetin
- Streptomycin
- Dihydrostreptomycin
- Neomycin
- Novobiocin

The **potential hazards** referred to in this report are the antimicrobials listed above.

In this scenario, the T101-test would not detect amoxicillin, spiramycin, fluoroquinolones, sulphonamides with trimethoprim, pirlimycin or oxytetracycline at the dairy plants. However, the estimated worst case concentrations of these antimicrobial residues in the transportation truck would be diluted below MRLs, permitting the use of milk for human consumption. Streptomycin, dihydrostreptomycin and novobiocin are the only substances in this scenario which potentially exceed the MRLs but are not detected by the T101-test. However, these substances are used in combination medicines with β -lactams (which are detected by the T101-test at MRLs) and would therefore be eliminated from raw milk intended for human consumption.

5.1.5 Properties of the antimicrobial substances

We will next briefly summarise general properties and metabolism in cattle, as well as examine the excretion into milk of those antimicrobials which were identified as potential hazards in raw milk.

5.1.5.1 β -Lactam antibacterials

β -Lactam antimicrobials are the most widely used antimicrobials in the treatment of cattle (79%) (Rantala 2003). Benzylpenicillin is highly susceptible to β -lactamases and has little activity against organisms that can produce these enzymes (USP DI 2003). It is also a strong inhibitor of the bacteria used in the dairy industry.

Benzylpenicillin salts (potassium, sodium), benzylpenicillin procaine and penethamate hydriodide are rapidly broken down into benzylpenicillin, which is further metabolised to some extent by hydrolysis of the β -lactam ring. The metabolites are microbiologically inactive. Metabolism is of little importance in elimination. Penicillins are mainly excreted via urine (Vaden & Riviere 2001).

Benzylpenicillins are used as injections and as intramammary therapy for cows (Pharmaca Veterinaria Fennica 2002).

A small fraction of injected benzylpenicillin is excreted into milk. For procaine benzylpenicillin it is estimated that 0.03% of the total dose is excreted into milk (Moretain & Boisseau 1984).

Depending on the quantity of antimicrobial drug administered, the nature of the vehicle and the volume infused, the mean recovery of procaine benzylpenicillin into milk after intramammary treatment has been observed to vary between 15–70% of the given dose (Moretain & Boisseau 1989).

Cloxacillin is **penicillinase-resistant penicillin**, representing 2% of antimicrobials used in the treatment of cattle (Rantala 2003).

Cloxacillin is partially metabolised to active and inactive metabolites. It is hydrolysed into penicilloic acids, which are microbiologically inactive. To a small extent

cloxacillin is also hydroxylated into active metabolites. Cloxacillin and its metabolites are rapidly excreted in urine (TOXNET 2004a).

Cloxacillin is used in intramammary preparations (Pharmaca Veterinaria Fennica 2002). The mean recovery percentage of cloxacillin in milk varies between 21–59% after intramammary administration (Moretain & Boisseau 1989).

Broad-spectrum penicillin ampicillin is broken down by β -lactamases (Bishop 1996). Together with amoxicillin they represent less than 1% of antimicrobials used in the treatment of cattle (Rantala 2003).

Ampicillin is rapidly distributed to most body fluids and is excreted in the urine. 10–20% of the administered dose is metabolised into penicilloic acid which is microbologically inactive (USP DI 2003).

Aminopenicillins are used as injections and intramammary treatment for cows (Pharmaca Veterinaria Fennica 2002). Total recovery of the injected dose into milk is low, up to 0.01% for ampicillin trihydrate (Moretain & Boisseau 1984). The mean recovery of ampicillin into milk after intramammary treatment varies between 25–69% (Moretain & Boisseau 1989).

A first generation **cephalosporin**, cephalexin represents approximately 3% of antimicrobials used in the treatment of cattle (Rantala 2003). It is resistant to destruction by β -lactamase enzymes (Prescott & Baggot 1988).

After intramammary administration, cephalexin is mainly excreted via urine (63%) and in faeces (6%) (EMEA 2003). The mean recovery of cephalexin into milk after intramammary treatment is 3.5% (Moretain & Boisseau 1989).

5.1.5.2 Aminoglycosides

Aminoglycosides (framycetin, neomycin, dihydrostreptomycin and streptomycin) represent approximately 3% of antimicrobials used in the treatment of cattle (Rantala 2003).

Aminoglycosides are not biotransformed and are mainly excreted unchanged via urine (USP DI 2003).

Aminoglycosides are used in intramammary preparations (Pharmaca Veterinaria Fennica 2002). According to a study by Moretain and Boisseau, the mean recovery of neomycin and dihydrostreptomycin into milk was 56% and 69%, respectively (Moretain & Boisseau 1993).

5.1.5.3 Others

Novobiocin is used with benzylpenicillin in intramammary treatment of cows. It represents less than 1% of antimicrobials used in the treatment of cattle (Rantala 2003).

Novobiocin is quickly absorbed from the udder after intramammary infusion and is rapidly metabolised and excreted.

In lactating animals about 20% of the total dose is excreted into milk, all as unmetabolised novobiocin (EMEA 2003).

5.2 Hazard characterisation

Acceptable daily intake (ADI) values are the basis for evaluating the safety of veterinary medicine residues for humans. The ADI is an estimate of the residue that can be ingested daily over a lifetime without increasing human health risks. The ADI can be set on the basis of toxicological, pharmacological or microbiological data.

Toxicological ADI-values are based on prolonged animal exposure studies. The lowest no-observable-effect-level (NOEL) of the most sensitive parameter and in the

most sensitive animal species is divided by a safety factor to determine the ADI-values. Safety factors vary from 10 to 1,000 (the most common being 100) to correct for intraspecies variability and interspecies extrapolation (EMEA 2004b). The expected lifetime of domestic animals is much shorter than humans and there is no reason to assume that pigs or calves would be more sensitive to antimicrobial drug residues than humans. It is therefore assumed that evaluating the safety of antimicrobial drug residues for calves and pigs via feed can be done by referring to toxicological ADI-values originally set for humans.

In this report, only toxicological ADI-values are used as a reference point to assess domestic animal safety. We do not use microbiological or pharmacological ADI-values, nor do we here evaluate antimicrobial resistance. Background information about the ADI-

Table 8.

Toxicological ADI-values for the antimicrobials which were identified as potential hazards

Active substance	Toxicological ADI µg/kg/day
β-lactams	
Ampicillin	200 ^{a*}
Benzylpenicillin	0.5 ^b
Cephalexin	500 ^b
Cloxacillin	200 ^a
Aminoglycosides	
Dihydrostreptomycin	25 ^b
Framycetin	60 ^b
Neomycin	60 ^b
Streptomycin	25 ^b
Other	
Novobiocin	20 ^b

^aAustralian Government (2003)

*ADI for ampicillin is not determined. Assumption is made that it equals the ADI of amoxicillin

^bEMEA (2003)

Table 9.

The absorption of orally-ingested antimicrobials which were identified as potential hazards

Active substance	Oral bioavailability % pigs	Oral bioavailability % calves
β-lactams		
Ampicillin	55 ^{a1}	4.5 ³
Benzylpenicillin	30 ^{b2}	7 ^{g3}
Cephalexin	100 ^{a1}	29 ^{h3}
Cloxacillin	30–80 ^{c1}	d/a
Aminoglycosides		
Dihydrostreptomycin	1 ^{d1}	d/a
Framycetin	1 ^{d1}	d/a
Neomycin	1 ^{d1}	0.4 ⁱ³
Streptomycin	1 ^{d1}	d/a
Other		
Novobiocin	30 ^{e2}	d/a

^aMacGregor & Graziani (1997)

^bUSP DI (2003)

^cToxnet (2004a)

^dToxnet (2004c)

^eEMEA (2003)

^fZiv et al. (1977)

^gMusser & Anderson (2001)

^hSoback et al. (1987)

ⁱPedersoli et al. (1994)

d/a= data not available

¹ based on human data

² based on animal data

³ based on cattle data

values used and toxicological profiles for each antimicrobial evaluated in this report are given in annex 2.

In order for antimicrobial drug residues to concentrate in animal tissue and therefore end up in the human food chain, orally-ingested antimicrobial drug residues must be absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Given a lack of data about pig absorption, we gathered data about human absorption. Since pigs and humans have similar digestive systems, we can assume that absorption is similar. Calf absorption is weaker than pig (Table 9).

5.3 Exposure assessment

This exposure assessment contains two parts. The first part describes general practices and data collection, while the second part describes the mathematical simulation model used to estimate the most likely concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues in the final feed mixture, as well as the daily exposure of animals.

5.3.1 Data collection

Results of chemical analyses of raw milk samples conducted at EELA in 2001–2003 were used in this study (EELA 2003a). In addition, three different surveys were carried out to obtain data for this report. NFA inspection authorities collected information from dairy plants about test positive cases in Finland and dilution practices at dairy plants during 2002 and beginning of 2003 (NFA 2003b). KTTK inspection authorities did a follow-up survey of these rejected raw milk lots which were further delivered by feed distribution companies and used by farmers (KTTK 2004a). Based on the results of chemically-analysed raw milk samples, EELA contacted all the dairy plants who had positive chemical test results in 2001–2003. Information about antimicrobial drug residue concentrations, tank sizes, dilution processes and test practices were obtained with this survey (EELA 2003b).

5.3.2 Route of raw milk from cattle farms to dairy plants

Dairy cattle farming make up over 27% of all farm production in Finland. In 2002, Finland had over 20,000 farms with 348,000 lactating cows, producing 2,458 million litres of milk, of which 97% is delivered to dairy plants. The average herd size is 17 cows (Tietovakka 2003).

The average volume of raw milk in a farm tank was 670 litres in 2002. Some individual farms use the T101-test in order to avoid accidents, but it is not required by the authorities. Some dairy companies collect additional samples from each farm tank as they pick up raw milk, which enables them to trace back the farm if a positive T101-test result is obtained at the receiving facilities. However, these practices vary greatly from one company to another (NFA 2003a).

When raw milk from the farm tank is loaded into the transportation truck, possible antimicrobial drug residue concentrations are diluted several fold (Figure 5). Sizes of the transportation trucks vary from company to company, and the number of farm tanks loaded into the truck is not constant. It is estimated that approximately 20–40 farm tanks are loaded onto one transportation truck. However, in normal operation, the tanker and its trailer are separated into several compartments, thus keeping the milk portions separate. The head of the truck usually contains 3–4 compartments holding 13–15,000 litres of milk and the trailer 4–5 compartments holding up to 26,000 litres (NFA 2003a).

Figure 5.
The route of raw milk from cattle farm to dairy plant

5.3.3 Procedures at dairy plants

Each lot of raw milk arriving at a dairy plant is tested for antimicrobial drug residues. If the contents of the transportation truck were unloaded into a silo at the dairy plant without testing, antimicrobial drug residues would most likely be diluted to the extent that the screening test would not be sensitive enough to detect them. Current testing practices make it easier to trace back to the individual farm responsible if residues are found in raw milk.

The authorities have not prescribed how samples are to be collected from each milk lot. A sample can be taken from the whole vehicle or truck and trailer separately (Figure 6). Depending on the location of the collection sites, the driver may have started the testing procedure while collecting, but at short distances tests are most likely performed at the reception facilities. If a positive test result is obtained, there is an attempt to discover the individual compartment containing the test positive milk (NFA 2003a).

According to the EELA and NFA surveys, 100% of dairy plants used the T101-test to detect inhibitory substances in raw milk (NFA 2003b; EELA 2003b) and 71% reported that they also used additional Snap-tests (EELA 2003b).

According to Valio Ltd., which represents approximately 80% of the milk refined in Finland, several measures are taken immediately if a positive test result is obtained (Laitinen 2002; NFA 2003a).

1. Determine which part of the load is test-positive, and unload it into a silo reserved for milk by-products.
2. If the milk lot containing inhibitory substances is accidentally unloaded into a regular raw milk silo, all the milk in that silo is rejected without further testing.

3. Possible micropipette samples from each farm on that route are analysed or samples are collected from the farms in question as soon as possible to identify the farm which has delivered milk with a positive test result.
4. A consultant of the dairy cooperative contacts the farm.
5. Inspection authorities are informed about the incident. Usually the district veterinarian from the state provincial office inspects the farm and audits its medical records.
6. The dairy cooperative imposes a fine based on the extent of the damage.
7. If antimicrobial drug residues are found again within three years in raw milk from the same farm, the authorities place the farm under surveillance.

Positive milk lots must be transported out of the dairy plant. According to the NFA survey, two possible methods have been used in Finland.

1. Rejected milk is disposed of in a dumping ground, manure sludge or used as fertilizer (13% of cases).
2. Diluted or non-diluted milk is picked up by feedstuff distributing companies and used as feed (72% of cases).

In 15% of cases, usage was not known (NFA 2003b).

Rejected T101-test positive raw milk is usually mixed with other dairy by-products, such as raw milk with unacceptable taste or odour, rinse water from the production line, sour milk or whey (NFA 2003b).

Figure 6.
Sample collection procedure at dairy plants

In 38% of cases, after mixing the rejected raw milk with other dairy by-products, some sort of screening test was performed (the T101-test or the Snap-test) (EELA 2003b). However, this is not required by the authorities and the reliability of the test in a matrix other than raw milk is unknown.

5.3.3.1 Results of the antimicrobial drug residue concentrations analysed at EELA

Usually the T101-test positive raw milk lots are discarded without chemical confirmation. However, in some cases dairy plants, individual farmers or veterinarians might want to have chemical confirmation of the positive test results, in order to confirm what antimicrobial substance in milk causing the positive test result.

In Finland, chemical analyses of raw milk samples are conducted at EELA. In 2001–2003 (data until 29.10.03), EELA had 25 assignments from all over Finland. 84% of the raw milk samples were confirmed to contain antimicrobial drug residues (EELA 2003a). Nineteen questionnaires were sent to dairy plants with confirmed positive samples, and seventeen (89%) were returned to EELA. The number of laboratory results is higher than the number of cases, since some raw milk samples contained more than one active substance.

Out of 26 laboratory results, 4 positive results were from samples of 3 individual cows. Seven results represented 5 positive farm tank samples and 15 results represented 12 different transportation tank samples (EELA 2003a; EELA 2003b) (Annex 3).

Four different antimicrobial drug residues were detected in the chemically-analysed samples, benzylpenicillin being the most commonly found substance (95%). Cloxacillin and ampicillin were found in only one sample, even though the test percentage was high, 95–100%. Streptomycin was found in five samples (50% of the tested samples) (EELA 2003a). The detected concentrations of streptomycin were below the detection limits of the T101-test and all the samples also contained benzylpenicillin (Annex 3). This supports the theory that aminoglycosides can be found in rejected milk, even if the detection limit for these substances is too high to be detected by the T101-test alone in raw milk.

According to data obtained in the EELA laboratory (EELA 2003a) and the survey of dairy refiners (EELA 2003b), the average concentration of benzylpenicillin in rejected transport truck tanks was 15 µg/litre. The average concentration of benzylpenicillin in a rejected silo was 2.3 µg/litre after the addition of whey, rinse milk and raw milk (Annex 3).

5.3.3.2 Dilution factors according to a survey of dairy plants

A survey of dairy plants to obtain information about dilution factors and the usage of the T101-test was done by the NFA. Dairy operators were asked to report the number of positive cases found as a part of their own checks in 2002. The volume of rejected milk and volume of other by-products added to rejected milk were also reported by the dairy plants (NFA 2003b). Sixteen dairy operators answered the NFA survey, reporting 60 positive cases. Data included all 47 cases from 2002 and additional information about 13 cases in 2003 (the total number of positive cases in 2003 was 37). Out of the 60 known cases, information about discarded milk volumes and dilutions factors were not obtained for 9 cases due to the fact that some of the dairy operators were no longer in operation. The average volume of rejected raw milk was 10,000 litres. This amount was mixed with other dairy by-products and diluted by the process, either at the dairy plant (60%) or straight into the transportation tanks of the companies distributing feed (23%). 16 lots were transported to farms without

mixing with other dairy by-products, though additional dilution was performed at the farms. The dilution factors averaged 3.9, 4.4 and 5.8, respectively (NFA 2003b) (see Annex 4).

Unfortunately we do not have any information about the concentrations of anti-microbial drug residues in these rejected test positive lots. Milk lots were rejected based on microbiological tests and distributed further without chemical confirmation. In practice this means that lots with possible false T101-test positives would also have been used as feed.

5.3.4 Route of diluted raw milk to animal feed

In practice, after the milk lot is determined to be test-positive and is rejected, the staff at the dairy plant informs local feed companies who further distribute the by-products to local farms. Since the dairy plants need to get rid of the test positive milk lot as soon as possible, they usually pay the feed distributor who picks up the load.

Dilution practices and the components added to raw milk vary case by case. Milk can be diluted by

1. dairy operators with other dairy by-products
2. feed-producing companies with other dairy by-products
3. farmers with other feed by-products.

A follow-up survey on the rejected raw milk lots recorded by the NFA in 2002 and part of 2003 was carried out by the KTTK. Feed-distributing companies were asked about the destinations of the rejected milk lots as well as about the dilution factors used in the process. Individual farms which used milk containing inhibitory substances as feed explained their own practices at the farm level, providing information about the number of animals, portion size per feeding, number of feedings and acidification practices. 38 loads of rejected milk (63%) could be traced back. These rejected lots were usually divided into smaller portions and delivered to separate farms. On average, each milk lot was divided and delivered to 2–3 farms, though this number varied from one to nine farms depending on the size of the rejected milk lot. The average amount received was 16,000 litres/farm/delivery (KTTK 2004a).

In this study 100% of the lots were transported to pig farms, with a total of 30 farms receiving these lots. Six milk lots (16%) were transported to three farms outside the country (KTTK 2004a). As the total number of pig farms in Finland is 3815 (Tietovakka 2003), the 27 farms receiving this type of raw milk represented 0.7% of all pig farms in Finland. No milk lots containing antimicrobial drug residues were transported to calf rearing units during this study. However, after this study additional information was discovered about two cases where milk was delivered to 16 different farms at the end of 2003 and beginning of 2004. Of these 16 farms, two were revealed to have calves which were partially fed with raw milk containing inhibitory substances (KTTK 2004b).

5.3.4.1 Feeding routines at pig farms

In Finland, the 3815 pig farms represent approximately 5% of all farms, and contain a total of 477,000 pigs of which 30% are sows and 70% fattening pigs (Tietovakka 2003). Approximately 65–70% of these farms are using a liquid feed system and this number is growing (Kuoppala et al 2004).

The liquid feed system utilizes the liquid by-products of industry. Whey, protein feed from barley (PFB) and brewery yeast are the most common by-products used in this system. Other possible by-products are milk and sour milk, curd cheese, eggs, dough and fat (Farmit 2003). Food industries do not usually market or distribute their

by-products, but rather a few specialised feed companies market and distribute the by-products as feed. These companies usually offer counselling for farmers and specialised feed schemes (Alaviuhkola et al. 1999).

Farms using the liquid feed system have a storage tank where the by-products can be unloaded as they arrive from industry. Storage tanks are protected from freezing and sedimentation is prevented by stirring (Kuoppala et al. 2004). Dairy by-products, including milk which has been rejected due to a positive test result, are not suitable as such for feeding. Normally either whey or PFB is added to the mixture, depending on the feed value of the dairy by-products. The feed is usually processed just before feeding. The components are first moved to a mixing tank, and at this point, depending on what by-products are used, other components might be added, such as water, grain (oat, barley and wheat), PFB, whey, vitamin and mineral concentrate and possibly formic or propionic acid. The contents may vary case by case, depending on the by-products used and the quality needs of the farmed animals. In this feed-mixing step, the average dilution factor was 2.6 (KTTK 2004c).

The pipe system of the feed-metering device contains lactic acid bacteria, which lower the pH of the feed. This decreases the number of coliformic bacteria in both the feed and the pig's intestine, and pigs readily eat acidic feed (Huovinen et al. 2001). Some by-product components such as PFB and whey have a low pH of their own accord, <4 and 4–5, respectively (Alaviuhkola et al. 1999). The feed in the mixture tank can also be acidified with formic or propionic acid. The recommendation is to adjust the pH to between 4.2 and 4.5 in feed, as this prevents abnormal fermentation (Kuoppala et al. 2004). The feed mixture is brewed at least half an hour before distribution to animals, as this allows enzyme activity to get started, improving the digestion of the feed in the intestine. The recommended temperature of the feed mixture is +20°C, which is regulated by the incoming water temperature (Kuoppala et al. 2004). Above +30°C the growth of harmful bacteria increases and feed deteriorates in the pipe system, so the temperature of the feed mixture should be kept between +20 – +30°C (Huovinen et al. 2001).

5.3.4.2 Profiles of pig farms using this type of raw milk as a feed component

According to the KTTK survey, the average number of fattening pigs and sows at the farms receiving inhibitory test positive milk was approximately 900 and 200, respectively. Twenty seven percent of the farms had sows and reported using the same feed for them as for fattening pigs. Fifty percent of the farms used acid to control the pH of the final feed mixture. Of the total number of rejected lots, 62% were reported to be acidified. Each of the 30 farms received an average of 2.6 deliveries of the residue-containing milk in 2002 and part of 2003, corresponding to one delivery every 4 months. Normally, fattening pigs are farmed until the age of 3–4 months, so in practice this means that one fattening pig would on average eat milk containing inhibitory substances only once (for 3–4 days) in its life. However, the delivery period varies greatly from one farm to another. Forty percent of the farms received only one load of milk containing inhibitory substances in 2002 and the beginning of 2003, but some had more frequent deliveries, up to seven during this survey period. The time between deliveries was less than 10 days in 17% of the cases, indicating that exposure to low levels of residues continued in some farms for a few weeks. Also, the amount of raw milk received varied depending on the size of the herd, ranging from 3,000 to 55,000 litres per load (KTTK 2004a) (see Annex 5).

5.3.4.3 Feeding of fattening pigs

The fattening period starts when pigs reach the weight of 20–25 kg. Farms reported

that each milk lot transported to the farm lasted an average of 3–4 days, varying from one to eight days, depending on the size of the lot and the number of animals fed at the farm (KTTK 2004a). We assumed that a full-grown fattening pig weighs 100 kg (Alaviuhkola 1999) and that it would eat 10 litres/day of the final feed mixture (KTTK 2004a).

5.3.4.4 Feeding of sows

Eight farms out of thirty (27%) reported feeding sows with this type of by-product. Other combination farms (7%) reported that sows were not fed rejected milk.

The amount of liquid feed given to sows varied between 22–28 litres/day (KTTK 2004a). Therefore, we used the value of 28 litres in the calculations to prevent underestimating the exposure. The average size of a sow is 200 kg (Alaviuhkola 1999).

5.3.4.5 Use of rejected raw milk in the feeding of calves

In Finland, the production of veal calves with white meat is not permitted. Calves are fed according to feeding schemes whose objectives are to grow healthy animals for production of calf meat or for later usage as beef or dairy cattle.

Approximately 90% of all dairy by-products are consumed at pig farms, so only a minor portion is transported to calf-rearing units. It is quite rare for a calf farm to receive T101-test positive milk, though it is possible in theory (Kuoppala, personal communication). According to the KTTK survey of feed-distributing companies and farms, no raw milk lots containing inhibitory substances were transported to cattle farms (KTTK 2004a). However, after the survey, additional information received in spring 2004 revealed that two calf farms had received rejected raw milk (KTTK 2004b).

At the age of 10–20 days, calves are transported to calf-rearing units, where they are given acidified milk from week 2–3 up to week 8 (Kuoppala, personal communication). Rough-grained feed or hay along with concentrated feed are readily available at all times (Aspila et al. 2001).

The number of calves at the two farms which received raw milk containing inhibitory substances was 200 and 250 calves/farm. The dilution of rejected milk at calf farms was similar to that of pig farms. The average amount of final feed mixture fed to calves was 9 litres/day (KTTK 2004b). Calves at the age of 8 weeks are estimated to weight 90 kg (Aspila et al. 2001).

5.3.5 The simulation model

Our model simulating the exposure of pigs, sows and calves to antimicrobial drug residues consists of five consecutive steps, where the output of one step is used as the input for the next step. The sources for the input distributions and point estimates are described in more detail in Table 10. The five steps are (cf. Figure 7):

1. **Quantity of milk and concentrations of residues in a transportation truck.** Input for the quantity of milk is given as a probability distribution. Input for the concentration of benzylpenicillin is in the form of a probability distribution, while other possible antimicrobial drug residue concentrations in the transportation truck are expressed as point estimates from the worst case scenarios. These probability distributions are based on the NFA survey and EELA laboratory results (NFA 2003b; EELA 2003a).
2. **Dilution in dairy plant silo or feed truck.** Alternative input values for quantities in the silo or feed truck in which the T101-test positive lot of milk is diluted are given as probability distributions. There is also an option of no pre-farm dilution at this step. Data is based on the NFA and EELA surveys (NFA 2003b; EELA 2003b).

3. **Dilution in feed storage silos.** Input is given as a point estimate of the dilution factor, with data based on the KTTK survey (KTTK 2004a).
4. **End dilution of the final feed mixture.** Input is given as a dilution factor, with data based on the KTTK survey (KTTK 2004a). The results of steps 1—4 are the quantity of feed mixture containing antimicrobial residue and the concentration of the residue in it.
5. **Daily and total exposure of animals** (pigs, sows and calves) to residues. Feeding practices are obtained from the KTTK survey. The amount of feed consumed per day and the number of days the feed is given to pigs, sows or calves is averaged from the questionnaire data (KTTK 2004a). Comparison of these daily exposures to the human ADI-values for antimicrobial drugs is included for reference purposes.

Using the probability distributions as inputs makes it possible to apply Monte Carlo simulations to yield most probable outcomes (result distributions). The simulation model was implemented on commercial spreadsheet software (Excel 2002, Microsoft Corporation, USA), with a commercial Excel add-in module for risk analysis (@Risk, version 4.5.2, Palisade Corporation, USA). The spreadsheet workbook ("Milkdilutionmodel RAPORTTI.xls") is available on request, but the simulations in the developed model cannot be run without the add-in module (which is not included in the workbook). The output of the model consists of distributions of the quantity of feed mixture containing antimicrobial residue and the concentration of the residue in it, as well as the daily and total exposures of the animals. These exposures are compared with reference values.

Figure 7.
Five steps in the simulation model

The preliminary estimates or assumptions made in the model are:

- The detected benzylpenicillin concentrations represent the true population. The distribution of observed values conforms satisfactorily with lognormal distribution and the latter was employed in the model.
- For other antimicrobial drug residue concentrations, we assume that the theoretical maximum concentrations represent the actual maximum concentrations.
- The final concentration of residue in feed depends only on the dilution steps during the process.
- Daily exposure consists of two factors: the final antimicrobial drug residue concentration in feed and the amount of feed eaten daily.
- Full-grown fattening pigs are estimated to weigh 100 kg and to eat 10 litres of the final feed mixture per day.
- Sows are estimated to weigh 200 kg and to eat 28 litres of the final feed mixture per day.
- Calves are estimated to weigh 90 kg and to eat 9 litres of the final feed mixture per day.
- Daily exposures are proportioned to the body weight of animals.
- Human toxicological ADI-values can be used as reference values for the safety of antimicrobial drug residues in feed.
- Daily exposure to amounts of antimicrobial drugs not exceeding the human toxicological ADI-values is considered safe for animals.

The simulation is based on actual data obtained from different production steps, so the model can be considered to yield satisfactorily reliable results.

Figure 8. The simulation model consists of five consecutive steps. An example of one iteration is shown in the table. The simulation is run with 10,000 iterations.

Table 10. Distributions and point estimates of the inputs used in the milk dilution model

Inputs	Employed distributions	Data obtained from
Quantity in transport truck	Lognorm(9,911;6,219)	Based on EELA and NFA surveys. Average and standard deviation values calculated from Annex 3 (only benzylpenicillin) and Annex 4.
Benzylpenicillin concentrations in transport truck	Tlognorm(14,8;16,4;0,65)	Based on EELA laboratory analyses. Average, standard deviation and max values calculated and obtained from Annex 3. Min value of 0 used based on the observation of false positives.
Other antimicrobial drug residue concentrations in transport truck	Point estimates See table 7	Worst case scenario: it was assumed that during two-day treatment of one cow, all milk containing antimicrobial drug residues was accidentally poured into one farm tank whose milk was collected by the transportation truck.
Quantity in silo	Lognorm(36,380;28,147)	Based on EELA and NFA surveys. Average and standard deviation calculated from Annex 3 (only benzylpenicillin) and Annex 4.
Quantity in feed truck	Triang(12,000;46,554;62,500)	Based on the NFA survey. Min, average (most likely), and max values values calculated and obtained from Annex 4.
Feed storage dilution factor	Point estimate of 5.75	Based on the NFA survey. Calculated average from Annex 4.
Final feed dilution factor	Lognorm(2,56;0,84)	Based on the KTTK survey. Average and standard deviation values calculated from the results
Quantity of final feed given / day	Point estimates: 10 litres for fattening pigs, 28 litres for sows and 9 litres for calves	Based on the KTTK survey.
Weight of the fattening pigs, sows and calves	Point estimates: 100 kg fattening pigs, 200 kg sows and 90 kg calves	Based on literature. Alaviuhkola (1999), Aspila (2001).
Toxicological ADI-values: Benzylpenicillin Ampicillin Cephalixin Cloxacillin Framycetin Neomycin Dihydrostreptomycin Streptomycin Novobiocin	0.5 200 500 200 60 60 25 25 20	Reference values obtained from Table 8.

5.4 Risk characterisation

The most likely concentrations of each antimicrobial drug residue in feed and the daily exposures of domestic animals to these antimicrobials were obtained from the simulation model. Data presented in the earlier chapters was used in the model.

The final concentrations of antimicrobial drug residues in feed were compared with the MRLs set for raw milk; in other words, raw milk containing antimicrobial drug residues at this level would be permitted for human consumption. However, MRLs have not been set for feed. The average daily exposures were expressed as a proportion of body weight ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day) and were compared to the **toxicological ADI**-values in order to evaluate the safety of exposure levels.

Earlier in this report, three different dilution scenarios were identified (at the dairy plant, feed truck or farm). Since the dairy plant dilution scenario is the most common dilution procedure, and also has the lowest dilution factor, safety is evaluated based on this scenario. The exposure of domestic animals would be lower in the other two dilution scenarios.

5.4.1 Safety evaluation of benzylpenicillin in feed

According to the simulation model, the average concentration of benzylpenicillin in a final feed mixture was $2.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{litre}$ [90% of results $0\text{--}5.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{litre}$]. The average concentration of benzylpenicillin in feed remains below the MRL ($4 \mu\text{g}/\text{litre}$) set for raw milk.

The average daily exposure proportioned to the body weights of exposed animals is $0.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ for fattening pigs [90% of results $0\text{--}0.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$], $0.36 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ for sows [90% of results $0\text{--}0.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$] and $0.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ for calves [90% of results $0\text{--}0.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$]. Compared to the toxicological ADI-value set for humans, these average exposure doses represent approximately 50% (fattening pigs), 71% (sows) and 50% (calves) of the toxicologically acceptable daily intake doses. In 10,000 iterations (possible dilution scenarios) over 80% of the theoretically possible values stay below the toxicological ADI-value (Figure 9).

If a worst case scenario of benzylpenicillin is put into the simulation model instead of the actually detected concentrations, the average benzylpenicillin concentration would be $56.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{litre}$ and the daily exposure would exceed the human ADI-value over ten times.

5.4.2 Safety evaluation of other antimicrobial drug residues in feed

Since no data about the concentrations of other theoretically possible drug residues in milk exists, the worst case scenarios are used as input values for the simulation model (see Table 7). Worst case scenarios are high estimations of antimicrobial drug residue concentrations in milk, which would most likely not occur in normal practice. However, no other reliable data are available and these scenarios are used as the basis for the safety evaluation.

The average concentrations of framycetin, dihydrostreptomycin, neomycin, novobiocin and streptomycin in feed remain below MRLs set for raw milk. Ampicillin, cephalexin and cloxacillin concentrations, by contrast, exceeded the MRLs set for raw milk.

The average daily exposure of fattening pigs, sows and calves to ampicillin, cephalexin, cloxacillin, framycetin, neomycin and novobiocin remained well below the human toxicological ADI-values (>98% of the results under ADI). Streptomycin and dihydrostreptomycin had slightly higher daily exposure concentrations, but the average daily exposure still remained well below the ADI-values (>70% of the results below ADI-values) (Table 11).

Figure 9.

Probability distributions of daily exposures to benzylpenicillin. Daily intake values in $\mu\text{g/kg}$ are shown on the category (x-) axis and the relative frequency of the simulation results on the value (y-) axis. The columns thus reflect the number of times the simulation results have fallen between their lower and higher boundaries on the category axis. The number of columns is arbitrary. The vertical line indicates the toxicological ADI-value and the percentage of values below the indicated ADI.

Figure 10.

Daily exposure of pigs/sows/calves to antimicrobials, plotted as percentages of the respective toxicological ADI-values. The boxes contain the middle half of the values and the solid lines indicate the medians. 90% of the results are within the indicated whiskers.

Table 11.

Simulation model estimations of the antimicrobial drug residue concentrations in feed were compared to MRLs set for raw milk. Daily exposures of sows, fattening pigs and calves were compared to human toxicological ADI-values.

Antimicrobial residue	Simulated average concentration in feed $\mu\text{g/litre}$	MRL (raw milk) $\mu\text{g/litre}$	Simulated average daily exposure $\mu\text{g/kg/day}$			Toxicological ADI-value $\mu\text{g/kg/day}$
			$\mu\text{g/kg/day}$			
			Fattening pigs	Sows	Calves	
Ampicillin	18.8 *	4	1.9	2.6	1.9	200
Benzylpenicillin	2.5	4	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.5
Cephalexin	112.7	100	11.3	15.8	11.2	500
Cloxacillin	37.5	30	3.8	5.3	3.7	200
Dihydrostreptomycin	113.2 *	200	11.3	15.8	11.2	25
Framycetin	7.5 *	1,500	0.8	1.0	0.7	60
Neomycin	33.6	1,500	3.4	4.8	3.3	60
Novobiocin	30.1	100	3.0	4.1	3.0	20
Streptomycin	165.6	200	16.5	23.2	16.3	25

*Concentration in feed exceed MRL set for raw milk

5.5 Validation of the simulation model

Some additional data were collected after the study period in order to validate the model, though these data were not used when the model was created. At the end of 2003 and beginning of 2004, dairy plants collected milk samples from each T101-test positive raw milk lot which was rejected. Six milk samples were analysed at EELA laboratories for antimicrobial drug residues. Benzylpenicillin was the only antimicrobial drug residue found in five of these milk samples. The average concentration of benzylpenicillin in rejected raw milk lots before dilution was 26 µg/l (min 5, max 92 µg/l) (EELA 2004). After dilution with other by-products at the dairy plant, the average concentration was 1.2 µg/l. The cause of the sixth positive T101-test result was not found through chemical analyses.

In five of these six cases, the rejected milk was used as feed; one raw milk lot was destroyed at the waste treatment plant. The KTTK was able to trace back how two milk lots were used (KTTK 2004b). These transport lots were distributed to 16 different farms. After the feed mixing procedure, the final concentration of benzylpenicillin in feed at these 16 farms was 0.5 µg/litre (standard deviation 0.3 µg/litre). This result is fairly similar to the simulation model estimation. Therefore, it can be concluded that the simulation model gives reliable and plausible estimations of the exposure to antimicrobial drug residues in feed.

5.6 Available risk management options

This section discusses three options to reduce the amount of antimicrobial residues in feed mixtures: controlling the temperature, the pH, or using enzymatic products. More detailed information about the degradation of individual antimicrobials is available in Annex 6; here we briefly evaluate each risk management option.

5.6.1 Heat treatment

Heat degradation was studied in three different heating processes: raw milk could be pasteurised, UHT-processed or turned into dry powdered milk.

- The pasteurisation of milk requires a temperature of 72°C and a minimum of 15 seconds.
- The UHT-processing of milk requires a temperature of 135°C for at least one second.
- Dry milk processing has several heating steps: pasteurisation takes 3 minutes at a maximum temperature of 120°C. After that milk goes through evaporation at 50–70°C for 20 minutes. Final drying is done for a few seconds at 80–90°C (Valio 2004).

Degradation of antimicrobials at 72°C is a slow process, requiring a significantly longer period than that used in pasteurisation. For example, at 71°C 100% degradation of benzylpenicillin requires a minimum of 28 hours (Shanani 1958). In 15 minutes, only 10% of residues are degraded at this temperature (Shanani et al. 1956). If the temperature were raised to 121°C, degrading 100% of the benzylpenicillin would still require 25 minutes (Shanani 1958).

In order to degrade 100% of the benzylpenicillin and aminoglycoside residues in milk, a temperature of at least 100°C would need to be maintained for over 5 hours (Pilet et al. 1969) (see Annex 6).

Conclusions: All antimicrobial drug residues require extensively long periods at

elevated temperatures before any significant degradation can be observed. The effect of the proposed heating processes is therefore considered negligible for reducing the levels of antimicrobial drug residues in raw milk.

5.6.2 Acidification of feed

When considering the acidification of feed, it is important to take into account the following factors:

- The optimal pH of pig feed is 4–5.
- Acidification which lowers the pH to this level during the feed mixing procedure happens only 30 minutes before feeding.
- Other by-products which are used to dilute raw milk, such as whey and PFB, are sour (pH 4–5) and could change the pH for several days in storage tanks.

Nearly all antimicrobial substances studied were stable in the range of the optimum pH of the feed mixture (pH 4–5). Degradation of residues was both time-consuming and incomplete in these pH ranges, requiring higher temperatures than can normally be used for storing or producing feed. The minimum time required to reduce 50% of ampicillin at pH 4 was 50 hours (Hoe & Poole 1969). Since degradation rates have been studied at higher temperatures than normal feed storage temperatures, even longer degradation times are assumed to exist in practice (see Annex 6).

The only substances which can be significantly reduced in a reasonable time through decreasing the pH are benzylpenicillin and cloxacillin. However, no data was found on the degradation rate at pH 4.

Conclusions: The effect of feed acidification in order to reduce antimicrobial drug residues in feed is negligible.

5.6.3 Enzymatic products

If using enzymatic products to degrade antimicrobial drug residues in milk, the following facts should be considered:

- β -Lactamase is the only commercial enzymatic product in Finland which is designed for the degradation of antimicrobial drug residues in milk.
- The enzyme hydrolyses the cyclic β -lactam ring
- β -Lactamase only degrades benzylpenicillin, amoxicillin and ampicillin
- The optimal conditions for using β -lactamase are +6°C at the normal pH of raw milk (pH 7).

This enzyme should be added to raw milk before it is mixed with other dairy by-products since the change in pH might reduce the enzymatic effect. At least 12 hours or longer is required to degrade residues, depending on the degree of degradation wanted and the original level of residues (Vetcare 2003, Korycka-Dahl et al. 1985).

Effective use of β -lactamase requires accurate information about the active substance found in milk and its concentration, and is gratuitous if the milk contains other residues besides benzylpenicillin and aminopenicillins. An enzymatic product for degradation of antimicrobials in milk has been developed in Finland by Vetcare Ltd, which claims that one ml (24,000 units of β -lactamase) of this commercial product (Antipen™) is sufficient to degrade all penicillin residues in 40 litres of milk directly milked from a treated cow (Vetcare 2003).

According to the manufacturer, treated milk poses no risk of increased resistance in the environment or in animals fed with this milk, but these degradation products may still trigger allergic reactions. Added β -lactamase is digested as any protein in the gastrointestinal tract (Vetcare 2003).

Benzylpenicillin and aminopenicillins are the most commonly used antimicrobial drugs in the treatment of cattle. Since the enzyme is able to degrade nearly 100% of these residues in milk, it could be considered a possible risk management option. However, this might give a false belief that the milk is free of residues which is not true if it contains other residues besides penicillins.

The safety of this product is not evaluated in this report.

Conclusions: The use of enzymatic products in the reduction of antimicrobials in milk is considered effective for benzylpenicillin, ampicillin and amoxicillin. However, it does not affect other antimicrobial residues possibly found in milk.

5.7 Discussion

In this report the daily exposures of domestic animals to antimicrobial drug residues are compared with **toxicological ADI**-values which have originally been set for humans. Extrapolating from humans to animals is justified, and exposures below these reference values are considered safe from the toxicological point of view.

In addition to toxicological ADI-values, **microbiological ADI**-values have been set for some antimicrobials; these are calculated according to the formula recommended by the Committee for Veterinary Medicinal Products (CVMP). Disruption of the colonization barrier and the increase of the populations of resistant bacteria are the factors which are considered when microbiological ADI-values are established (EMA 2004a).

Although microbiological safety has been a concern for many years, a harmonized approach to determining threshold doses has not been established. Formula-based approaches to determining microbiological ADI-values are based on minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) data against human intestinal bacteria, the fraction of an oral dose available for microorganisms and daily faecal bolus proportioned to human body weight (EMA 2004c).

The only β -lactam antibacterial which has a determined microbiological ADI-value is cephalixin. A microbiological ADI-value has not been set for ampicillin, benzylpenicillin or cloxacillin. Microbiological ADI-values of aminoglycosides are higher than their toxicological ADI-values. Novobiocin has a lower microbiological ADI-value than the toxicological ADI.

The microbiological safety of antimicrobial residues in feed is not evaluated in this report. However, it can be concluded that according to the simulation model the daily exposures for cephalixin, framycetin, dihydrostreptomycin, streptomycin and neomycin remain well below the microbiological ADI-values.

Table 12.

The toxicological and microbiological ADI-values of antimicrobials which are potential hazards in T101-test positive raw milk (according to the worst case scenario).

Active substance	Toxicological ADI µg/kg/day	Microbiological ADI µg/kg/day
β-lactams		
Ampicillin	200 ^{a*}	not determined
Benzylpenicillin	0.5 ^b	not determined
Cephalexin	500 ^b	54 ^b
Cloxacillin	200 ^a	not determined
Aminoglycosides		
Dihydrostreptomycin	25 ^b	120 ^b
Framycetin	60 ^b	160 ^b
Neomycin	60 ^b	160 ^b
Streptomycin	25 ^b	120 ^b
Other		
Novobiocin	20 ^b	1.25 ^b

^aAustralian Government (2003)

*ADI for ampicillin is not determined.

Assumption is made that it equals the ADI of amoxicillin

^bEMEA (2003)

6 Hazard identification of pathogens in raw milk

6.1 Introduction

In addition to the risks posed by antimicrobial drug residues, we must also consider the possible presence of pathogenic micro-organisms in raw milk. This chapter contains a short presentation of bovine infectious diseases which are listed either in OIE-list A and B or in the Council Directive (2003/99/EC) of zoonotic diseases. Some of the infections and diseases described in this chapter are specific to cattle, while some pathogens can also infect other ruminants or swine; some diseases are potential zoonoses. Milk as a vehicle can be contaminated either through blood during the septicaemic phase of the infection, or as secondary contamination from the skin of the teats and udder. Other domestic animals possibly sharing the same sheds with lactating cows can contribute to the contamination load of milk, but this source is excluded from the discussion due to a complete lack of data.

The predominant criteria applied in identifying potential pathogen hazards were:

- The current (spring of 2004) animal disease situation in Finland. Diseases which are absent, i.e. which were present either a long time ago or never, were considered to pose no risk.
- The epidemiology of the infections or diseases
- The potential of the pathogen to spread from an infected animal through use of its raw (not heat-treated) milk (OIE 2000, Gillespie et al. 1988). Pathogens for which milk is not an epidemiologically-significant vehicle of spread were considered to pose no risk.

The infections or diseases of cattle which are considered endemic to Finland are discussed in greater detail. In each case, we consider whether there is need for a proper risk assessment.

6.2 Diseases of OIE-list A

The cattle diseases of OIE-list A have either never been reported in Finland or were reported many years ago (Table 13). The table includes further information about the official disease status in Finland, the possibility of the disease spreading via milk, and of the need for a proper risk assessment.

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, all cattle diseases on OIE-list A are classified as diseases which spread easily and must be immediately reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995). In case of an outbreak, the spread, for example, of FMD via milk dis-

Table 13.

The occurrence of major diseases/infections in Finnish cattle, the official disease status of Finland, the possibility of spreading via milk, and the need for proper risk assessment.

Disease	^a Last reported occurrence in Finland	Official disease status	^b Secreted into milk or faecal contamination a known route	^c Need for further risk assessment
Foot and mouth disease	1959	Free	3	1
Vesicular stomatitis	0	N	2	1
Rinderpest	1877	Free	1	1
Contagious bovine pleuropneumonia	1920	N	0	1
Lumpy skin disease	0	N	0	1
Rift Valley fever	0	N	1	1
Bluetongue	0	N	1	1
Anthrax	1988	N	1	1
Aujeszky's disease	0	Free	0	1
Echinococcosis (<i>E. granulosus</i>)	2003	N	0	1
Heartwater	0	N	0	1
Leptospirosis	2002	N	1	2
Q-fever	0	N	2	1
Rabies	1988	Free	0	1
Paratuberculosis	2001	N	3	2
Screwworm (both old and new world)	0	N	0	1
Bovine anaplasmosis	0	N	0	1
Bovine babesiosis	2003	N	0	1
Bovine brucellosis	1960	Free	3	1
Bovine cysticercosis (<i>C. bovis</i>)	2002	N	0	1
Bovine genital campylobacteriosis	0	N	0	1
Bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE)	2001	N	0	1
Bovine tuberculosis	1982	Free	3	1
Dermatophilosis	0	N	0	1
Enzootic bovine leukosis	1996	N	1	1
Haemorrhagic septicaemia	0	N	0	1
Infectious bovine rhinotracheitis (IBR/IBV)	1994	N	1	1
Malignant catarrhal fever	2003	N	1	1
Theileriosis	0	N	0	1
Trichomonosis	1952	N	0	1
Trypanosomosis	0	N	0	1
Campylobacteriosis (intestinal)	2003	N	3	3
Listeriosis	2003	N	3	3
Salmonellosis	2003	N	3	2
EHEC infection	2003	N	3	3
Yersiniosis	2003	N	2	2
Cryptosporidiosis	2003	N	1	2
Toxoplasmosis	2003	N	0	2

^a Reported before 31.12.2003

0 = Never

N = No official status

^b 0: No

1: Possible but epidemiologically insignificant

2: Possible

3: Yes

^c 1: No hazard, no need for further assessment

2: Negligible hazard, no need further assessment

3: Possible hazard, may need further assessment

carded because of a positive T101-test result would be possible. However, the probability that there would be an established but yet undetected FMD virus infection on a dairy farm coupled with a positive T101-test result of milk from that farm is deemed insignificant, especially considering the most likely very short incubation period of the disease in the highly-susceptible domestic cattle population.

Conclusion: Given the absence of list A cattle diseases in Finland, and given that these diseases either do not spread via milk or milk is not an epidemiologically significant vehicle for them, the spread of any of these diseases to cattle or pigs through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3 Diseases of OIE-list B

Many of OIE-list B diseases of cattle have not occurred in Finland and, with certain exceptions, those OIE-list B diseases which have, are rare (MMM 2003a).

OIE-list B multiple species and cattle diseases, their occurrence in Finland, the official disease status of Finland, the possibility of spreading via milk and the need for a proper risk assessment are included in Table 13.

All OIE-list B diseases are, according to Finnish animal disease legislation, notifiable animal diseases.

Conclusion: There is no need to perform further risk assessment on using T101-test positive milk as feed-stuff in the spread of any multiple species or cattle-specific OIE-list B disease which has never been reported in Finland. Below we briefly discuss those infections or diseases on OIE list B which have been reported in Finland at least once, and draw conclusions in each case on the likelihood of their spread if T101-positive milk is used as feed.

6.3.1 Anthrax

Anthrax is an acute, contagious, and usually fatal septicaemia affecting a wide range of mammalian species, including humans. Anthrax is caused by *Bacillus anthracis*, a non-motile, capsulated, spore-forming, aerobic bacterium. Anthrax infection occurs by spore ingestion, inhalation, or cutaneous penetration. The most common sign of anthrax in cattle following spore ingestion is sudden death. The disease can possibly spread via raw milk but in acute cases the probability of milking the cow in the short bacteraemic period before death and having this milk unknowingly end up as feed is extremely low. Legal provisions concerning anthrax (MMM 180/80) provide instructions on handling milk on an anthrax-positive farm.

Anthrax is rare in Finland; the last reported cases were in one cattle herd in 1988 (MMM 2003a). The previous occurrence was in 1974.

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, anthrax is a dangerous animal disease and must be immediately reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: The rarity of the disease and the extremely low probability of T101-test positive milk coinciding with *B. anthracis* contamination make unnecessary further risk assessment of the spread of the disease through the use of T101-test positive milk as feed.

6.3.2 Echinococcosis / hydatidosis

Echinococcosis is a zoonotic disease caused by the cestodes *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *E. granulosus*. Cattle are intermediate hosts of *Echinococcus granulosus* and hydatid cysts can develop in the liver, lungs or other organs. Echinococcosis

does not spread via the milk or faeces of infected cattle (OIE 2000).

Most of the reported cases (*E. granulosus*) in Finland in 2002 were reindeer (*Rangifer tarandus*); the parasite was also found in the lungs of some moose (European elk, *Alces alces*). There were no positive cattle in meat inspection findings in 2002 (MMM 2003a).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, echinococcosis / hydatidosis must be reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry by the next working day at the latest (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Since cestodes of *Echinococci* do not spread through milk, the spread of echinococcosis / hydatidosis through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.3 Leptospirosis

Leptospirosis is caused by *Leptospira interrogans*, a gram-negative bacterium which includes over 20 serogroups, comprising over 200 pathogenic serotypes. All domestic mammals are susceptible to the infection. The most common serotypes associated with cattle are pomona, hardjo and grippotyphosa. Rodents are considered to be the main reservoir in nature and the most important route of infection is through contact with contaminated urine. All bulls intended for artificial insemination (AI) service are routinely tested for leptospira antibodies (MMM 6/EEO/2004) but no surveys of lactating cows have been conducted. In cows a severe infection frequently leads to abortion, especially during the 3rd trimester. Serovar hardjo is occasionally associated with mastitis (Gillespie et al. 1988).

Low positive titres (cutoff 1:100) are occasionally found in AI bulls (5 cases in 1998–2003, according to EELA LIMS statistics); however, the evidence for specific leptospira infections remains inconclusive. The organism was not isolated from cattle samples sent in for pathological diagnostics in 1998–2003.

Leptospiras can be secreted into milk during the bacteraemic phase of the infection but this route is epidemiologically insignificant (Gillespie et al. 1988). Milk can conceivably be contaminated via the urine-tainted skin of udder and teats.

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, leptospirosis must be reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry by the next working day at the latest (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Leptospira infections among Finnish dairy cattle are exceedingly rare if they exist at all, rendering the possibility of leptospiral contamination of T101-test positive milk highly improbable. Further risk assessment is thus unnecessary.

6.3.4 Rabies

Rabies is a fatal viral neurologic disease that affects most warm-blooded animals, including humans. The rabies virus is highly neurotropic, localizing in nerve tissues as well as in the salivary glands. It is shed in saliva, as well as in low levels in milk (George 1990), but transmission of the disease via the ingestion of milk has not been demonstrated.

From 1959 until 1988 Finland was free of rabies. An outbreak of sylvatic rabies started in April 1988 and a total of 66 cases were confirmed in different animals. The outbreak was controlled and limited with bait vaccination of wild carnivores and vaccination of domestic animals (mainly dogs). The last case was found in February 1989. After two years with no cases of rabies, at the end of February 1991 Finland was declared free of the disease (MMM 2002). A bait vaccination campaign is conducted annually in a zone along the south-eastern border. In 2003, a horse imported from Estonia was diagnosed as infected with rabies. It was concluded that the horse

had contracted the disease in Estonia where sylvatic rabies is endemic, and the event did not change the Finnish rabies-free status. There is continuous monitoring of the rabies situation among wildlife. In 2002 the brains of 524 animals were examined for rabies.

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, rabies is a dangerous animal disease and must be immediately reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Given the absence of the disease in Finland and the very low potential of its spreading through milk, the spread of rabies through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.5 Paratuberculosis

Paratuberculosis is a chronic enteritis of ruminants caused by *Mycobacterium avium ssp paratuberculosis*. The disease has also been reported in pigs. *M.a. ssp. paratuberculosis* can spread by faeces or by milk (OIE 2000), but the excretion of bacteria into milk is rare and occurs only in the fulminating type of infection.

Paratuberculosis was reported in 1992 for the first time since 1920. Between 1992 and 2000 paratuberculosis was reported in a total of five, mainly beef, herds. According to Finnish animal disease legislation, paratuberculosis is a contagious animal disease and must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Given that paratuberculosis is most likely exceedingly rare among Finnish dairy herds, the hazard of its spread through the use of T101-positive milk as feed does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.6 Bovine babesiosis

Babesiosis ('red water disease') is caused by the protozoans *Babesia bovis*, *B. bigemina*, *B. divergens* and others. Babesiosis is a tick-borne disease (OIE 2000). The organism is not secreted into milk, urine or faeces.

In 2002 there were 74 reported cases of babesiosis in Finland (MMM 2003a).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, bovine babesiosis is a contagious animal disease and must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Since *Babesiae* are not secreted into milk and contamination of milk through urine or faeces is not possible, the spread of bovine babesiosis through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.7 Bovine brucellosis

Bovine brucellosis is usually caused by *Brucella abortus*, less frequently by *B. melitensis* and rarely by *B. suis*. It is manifested by abortion, with excretion of the organisms in uterine discharges and in milk. *B. abortus*, *B. melitensis* and *B. suis* are highly pathogenic for humans. *B. suis* causes porcine brucellosis (OIE 2000). Brucellosis can spread by milk.

The last reported case of bovine brucellosis in Finland was in 1960 (MMM 2003a). Finnish bovine herds have officially been granted brucellosis-free status according to Article 3 § 13 of Council Directive 64/432/EEC. This disease-free status was established by Commission Decision 94/960/EC of 28 December 1994, and confirmed by Commission Decision 2000/69/EC in 2000 (MMM 2002).

Maintaining disease-free status requires testing of all suspected cases of brucellosis and implementation of regular national screening programmes. Dairy herds have been tested annually through screening programmes since 1994 (3,078 milk sam-

ples in 2002); similarly, beef cattle have also been tested by sampling since 1994 (277 blood samples in 2002). All AI bulls in insemination centres and all new bulls entering insemination centres and their herds of origin are tested annually. Samples are frequently taken in connection with cases of bovine abortion. In 2002 this led to the testing of 946 blood samples from cattle herds. Organ samples of 45 animals and blood samples of 72 animals were tested due to suspected disease. All samples were negative (MMM 2003a).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, brucellosis is a dangerous animal disease and must be immediately reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Given that the disease is absent, the spread of bovine brucellosis through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.8 Bovine tuberculosis

Bovine tuberculosis is an infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium bovis*, and is usually characterised by formation of nodular granulomas known as tubercles. Although cattle are true hosts of *M. bovis*, the disease has been reported in several other species including pigs and humans (OIE 2000). *M. bovis* and human *M. tuberculosis* are genetically very closely related species. Bovine tuberculosis can spread by the milk or faeces of infected animals (Smith 1990).

Tuberculosis was eradicated to a large extent during the 1960s. The last case of bovine tuberculosis in Finland was recorded in one cattle herd in 1982 (MMM 2003b).

Finnish bovine herds have officially been granted tuberculosis-free status according to Article 3 § 14 of Council Directive 64/432/EEC. Disease-free status was established by Commission Decision 94/959/EC of 28 December 1994, and confirmed by Commission Decision 2000/69/EC in 2000 (MMM 2002).

Tuberculosis control started in Finland at the beginning of the 20th century. Today it is mainly based on testing undertaken at meat inspection. No positive cases were diagnosed in 2002. All four samples from suspected bovines, 47 from pigs and seven from zoo animals tested negative for *M. bovis* (MMM 2003b). Bovine tuberculosis with a single intradermal test is carried out annually on all new bulls transferred to AI stations and bulls at the AI stations. In 2002, 598 of these tests were conducted, all with negative results (MMM 2003b).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, bovine tuberculosis is a dangerous animal disease and must be immediately reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Since the disease is absent, the spread of bovine tuberculosis through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.9 Bovine cysticercosis

Cysticercosis is caused by the larval stages (metacestodes) of cestodes (tapeworms), whose adult stages occur in the intestines of humans and dogs or wild Canidae. Bovine and porcine cysticercosis are caused by the metacestodes (cysticerci) of the human intestinal cestodes *Taenia saginata* (in muscles) and *Taenia solium* (muscles and brain), respectively (OIE 2000). Cattle are intermediate hosts of cestodes, and cysticercosis does not spread by the milk or faeces of infected cattle.

In 2002 one case of cysticercosis (*Cysticercus bovis* / *Taenia saginata*) in cattle was diagnosed in Finland. The previous finding dates back to 1996 (MMM 2003a).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, bovine cysticercosis is a conta-

gious animal disease and must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Since larval stages of *Taeniae* are not secreted into milk or faeces, the spread of bovine cysticercosis through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.10 Enzootic bovine leukosis

Enzootic bovine leukosis is a disease of adult cattle caused by a deltaretrovirus, the bovine leukosis virus. The virus is present in blood lymphocytes, and is also found in the cellular fraction of various body fluids, possibly including milk (OIE 2000).

In Finland the prevention of bovine leukosis was started in the 1960s. At the end of 1996 Finland informed the European Commission that, with the exception of the island district of Ahvenanmaa, the country was free of leukosis, in accordance with Council Directive 64/432/EEC. In 1997, the Ahvenanmaa district started to monitor its leukosis status, with the objective of reaching leukosis-free status. No cases of leukosis occurred in Ahvenanmaa from 1997 to 2002, and on 13 July 1999 leukosis-free status was extended to Ahvenanmaa as well (Commission Decision 1999/465/EC) (MMM 2003a).

A national leukosis screening programme was introduced in 1990, and continued in 2002. Since 1991 all Finnish dairy herds have been screened annually for leukosis by means of pooled milk samples. Individual blood samples from beef cattle have been tested since 1993 (2816 blood samples in 2002) (MMM 2003a).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, enzootic bovine leukosis must be reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry by the next working day at the latest (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: The disease is absent and hence the spread of enzootic bovine leukosis through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.11 Infectious bovine rhinotracheitis / infectious pustular vulvovaginitis (IBR/IPV)

IBR / IPV, caused by bovine herpesvirus 1, is a disease of domestic and wild cattle. The virus enters the animal via the nasopharynx and replicates to high titres in the mucous membranes of the upper respiratory tract and in the tonsils. A low level viraemia can occasionally occur. After genital infection, BHV1 replicates in mucous membranes of the vagina or prepuce (OIE 2000). BHV1 has also been isolated from vesicular lesions of the bovine udder (Guy et al. 1984) and there is a possibility of milk contamination by the virus.

The first case of IBR / IPV in Finland was diagnosed in 1990 in a sample survey of dairy herds. A total of six dairy herds were found to be infected. The last positive herd was slaughtered in the summer of 1994 (MMM 2003a).

Finland has IBR / IPV-free status, and as a result has been granted additional guarantees relating to IBR / IPV (Commission Decision 94/962/EC of 28 December 1994) (MMM 2003b). Dairy herds have been tested annually since 1990 (19,870 bulk milk samples in 2002). Individual blood samples from beef cattle have been examined since 1993 (2,816 blood samples in 2002). In addition to the screening programme, 1,524 further milk and blood samples, collected under the health control programme of AI bulls, were tested in 2002. All results were negative (MMM 2003a and b).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, IBR / IPV must be reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry by the

next working day at the latest (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: The disease is absent and hence the spread of IBR / IPV through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.12 Trichomonosis

Bovine venereal trichomonosis is caused by *Trichomonas fetus*, a flagellate protozoan. Transmission is primarily by coitus, but mechanical transmission by insemination instruments or by gynaecological examination can occur (OIE 2000). The organism is not secreted in milk or faeces. Urine contamination from genital organs is possible, but this is not considered an epidemiologically significant route of infection (OIE 2000).

The last reported case in Finland was in 1952 (MMM 2003a).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, trichomonosis must be reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry by the next working day at the latest (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: The disease is absent and hence the spread of trichomonosis through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.13 Malignant catarrhal fever

Malignant catarrhal fever is a generally fatal disease of cattle and many other species of Artiodactyla, including swine, which occurs following infection with either alcelaphine herpesvirus-1 or ovine herpesvirus-2. The main reservoir for OvHV-2 is sheep and possibly goats, while cattle do not normally harbour the virus (Müller-Doblies et al. 2001). The epidemiology of the disease is not fully understood. The infection is transmitted through the respiratory route. Infection via milk has not been demonstrated.

The last reported case in Finland was in 2003 (MMM 2003b).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, malignant catarrhal fever must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Since the disease is very rare and the potential of milk to act as a vehicle has not been demonstrated, the spread of malignant catarrhal fever through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.3.14 Bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE)

BSE is a fatal neurological disease of adult cattle. The pathological changes, the epidemiological pattern, and the transmissibility of the disease indicate that BSE is one of the subacute spongiform encephalopathies caused by unconventional transmissible agents or prions. The BSE agent is also believed to be the common source of transmissible spongiform encephalopathies (TSEs) in several other species of *Bovidae* and species of *Felidae*. There is evidence of a causal link between the BSE agent and a new variant form of one of the human TSEs, Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease. The current, mainly British epizootic of BSE, can be explained by oral exposure to a scrapie-like agent in the ruminant-derived protein of meat-and-bone meal included in proprietary concentrates or feed supplements (OIE 2000). There is no evidence of BSE spreading through milk (EU Scientific steering committee 2002), but even so, milk from diseased animals must be destroyed (MMM 15/EEO/1998).

No cases of BSE were encountered in Finland in 2002. The only case in Finland so far was found in December 2001 (MMM 2003b).

In 2001 considerable amendments were made in Community legislation concerning TSEs. As a result of this, the testing for BSE of all bovines over 24 months of

age subject to emergency slaughtering, testing of samples from dead bovines over 24 months of age and of bovines over 30 months of age subject to normal slaughter by the rapid tests was started in Finland as well. A national centralised collection system for carcasses was started to increase the testing of dead animals in densely populated areas. In 2002 a total of 137,317 bovines were tested for BSE in Finland (MMM 2003a).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, BSE is a dangerous animal disease and must be immediately reported to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Since the disease is very rare, and is not known to spread through milk, the spread of BSE through using T101-positive milk as feed-stuff does not need further risk assessment.

6.4 Other diseases besides OIE-list A or B diseases listed in the Commission Directive on zoonotic diseases

6.4.1 Campylobacteriosis

Bovine genital campylobacteriosis (*C. fetus* spp. *fetus* and *venerealis*, OIE list-B, cattle-specific diseases) has never been detected in Finland. Furthermore, this disease spreads venereally. Hence, the spread of these pathogens through using T101-test positive milk as feed does not need further risk assessment. This section focuses on intestinal carriage and mastitic infections caused by thermophilic *C. jejuni/coli*.

The 2003 pathogen survey project yielded a tentative 30% positive (n=715) result for *C. jejuni/coli* in faecal or surface swab sampling in the period 1.1–1.9.2003 (Hakkinen, personal communication). In a 1979 study, 5.5% of the 200 examined cattle faecal samples were positive for *C. jejuni* (Hänninen and Raevuori 1981). No information is available on the variation in carriage prevalence due to age, breed or region. A moderate seasonal trend can be observed, the prevalence varying from 25% in winter to 40% in August (Hakkinen, personal communication). Mastitis caused by thermophilic campylobacters was not diagnosed between 1.1.1998 and 1.11.2003, according to EELA database statistics. The infection is probably very rare, but then again standard methods employed in bacteriological mastitis diagnostics do not detect this infection.

In intestinal carriage of adult animals, the pathogen is not secreted into milk. Contamination of milk can take place by faecal contamination of udder and teat surfaces, and milking appliances. Raw milk is a known vehicle for campylobacter infections (e.g. Kalman et al. 2000). Little information is available on the duration of intestinal carriage, but it probably lasts for several months. Significant numbers of bacteria may be secreted in milk during mastitis. Active infection most likely lasts less than a week. There is no information available about campylobacter mastitis becoming chronic.

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, campylobacteriosis must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: The comparatively high level of contamination or carriage of campylobacters among dairy cattle, and the known association of raw milk with campylobacteriosis outbreaks, may warrant a more thorough assessment of the risk posed by the use of T101-positive milk as feed.

6.4.2 Listeriosis

Listeria monocytogenes, the cause of listeriosis, is rather ubiquitous in nature; cattle are constantly exposed to it on the pasture and through hay and silage. It is fair to assume that most bovine animals carry it in their intestines. Immunologically competent animals are usually not susceptible, but occasionally *L. monocytogenes* develops a true infection and causes abortion or meningitis which is usually fatal (Gillespie et al. 1998). *Listeria* positive animals (clinical cases) were detected in 9 bovine herds (0.03%) in 2002 (MMM 2003b). *Listeria* is also associated with mastitis. Little information is available on the variation in prevalence of listeriosis in dairy cattle due to age, breed or region. *L. monocytogenes* retains the ability to grow at refrigerator temperatures.

Adult carrier animals do not secrete the pathogen into milk, but milk can be contaminated faecally via udder and teat surface. Intestinal carriage is probably continuous because of constant exposure but faecal shedding of the organism may be intermittent. The prevalence of *Listeria*-contaminated lots of raw milk has been shown to be a few percent. Secretion of the organism in milk during bacteremia of systemic infection or mastitis may be significant but these infections run their course within two weeks.

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, listeriosis must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: The occurrence of listeriosis among bovine herds and of *L. monocytogenes* in raw milk may warrant a more thorough assessment of the risk posed by the use of T101-positive milk as feed.

6.4.3 Salmonellosis

The point prevalence of salmonella infection in dairy herds, based on the number of imposed restrictions, is at most 0.05%; e.g. 9 out of ca. 20,000 herds in 2002 (MMM 2003b). The prevalence according to lymph node samples taken on an individual basis at slaughter (as part of the National Salmonella Control Programme) was 0.06% in 2002 (MMM 2003b). The herds under restrictive orders due to salmonella are concentrated in the western part of the country. Little information is available on variation in the prevalence of salmonella infection among adult cattle due to age or breed in Finland. However, infections in humans tend to rise during the summer months.

The serotypes prevalent in cattle (*S. enterica* Infantis and *S. e.* Typhimurium) are predominately non-invasive, and are excreted in the faeces. Undetected salmonella carriage can persist for several months and milk can become contaminated via faecally contaminated skin of udder and teats. Salmonella is also occasionally associated with mastitis. Milk from herds under restrictive orders cannot be used for feed without heat treatment (pasteurisation, MMM 23/EEO/95).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, salmonellosis in cattle must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Undetected salmonella infection among dairy cattle is very rare, far below 1% in Finland. The probability of contaminated T101-positive milk from an infected herd ending up as feed is considered too negligible to justify further attention.

6.4.4 EHEC infection

In 1997, the prevalence of enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) serotype O157 infection in individual cattle was estimated on average to be 1.3% in Finland. There

seems to be a seasonal trend in the occurrence of EHEC in cattle faeces, with prevalence reaching a maximum of 3.9% in July (Lahti et al. 2001). A longitudinal study in a cattle finishing unit was conducted in 1999–2001; during the fattening period the EHEC infection rate varied between 0 and 39%. However, it was concluded that the infection prevalence did not reflect the occurrence in new animals introduced, but was rather due to contamination on barn surfaces (Lahti et al. 2003). There is some indication of regional variation, so that the infection is rare or nonexistent in the northern part of the country (Lahti et al. 2001). Less is known about the effect of age or breed on prevalence. There is some indication that verocytotoxic *E. coli* serotypes other than O157:H7 may be even more prevalent among cattle (MMM 2002).

EHEC is not pathogenic to adult cattle but they can act as carriers of the organism and excrete it in faeces. The carrier state very probably can persist for over a year, though shedding is typically intermittent. Milk can be contaminated via the tainted skin of udder and teats. EHEC is not known to be associated with mastitis. EHEC O157:H7 was not detected in the milk or cheese samples examined in 1996–1999 (MMM 2000b).

Conclusion: The appreciable prevalence of serotype O157:H7 infection among dairy cattle, the unusual characteristics of the organism, and especially the unknown occurrence of other verotoxic serotypes may warrant a more thorough assessment of the risk of using T101-test positive milk as feed.

6.4.5 Yersiniosis

Yersinia enterocolitica and bacteria resembling it are ubiquitous, being isolated frequently from soil, water and animals. They comprise a biochemically heterogeneous group but a feature common to all is the ability to grow at refrigerator temperatures. *Y. pseudotuberculosis* is less common than *Y. enterocolitica*, and although frequently associated with animals, has only rarely been isolated from soil, water or foods. Both species contain both pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains, but their virulence factors have been incompletely characterised. A majority of the *Y. enterocolitica* strains isolated from foods of animal origin in Finland are non-pathogenic according to the chromosomal virulence markers employed in EELA (Hakkinen, personal communication).

Y. enterocolitica is known to be a frequent and *Y. pseudotuberculosis* an occasional resident of swine oropharynx. Little is known about the prevalence of these organisms in the tonsils or intestines of dairy cattle. Given the ubiquity of these organisms it is likely that cattle intestines are colonised by them, at least on a low level. Both *Y. enterocolitica* and *Y. pseudotuberculosis* have occasionally been associated with enteritis and mastitis. There is no data on seasonal or regional variance.

Yersinias are not secreted into milk in asymptomatic intestinal carriage, though milk can be contaminated via the tainted skin of udder and teats. According to a report, in 1979 4% of raw milk samples in Finland were positive for *Y. enterocolitica* biotype 1 (Hänninen & Raevuori 1981).

According to Finnish animal disease legislation, yersiniosis in cattle must be reported monthly to the Department of Food and Health of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MMM 1346/1995).

Conclusion: Although there is some indication of not insignificant contamination of raw milk, the contaminants are most likely of the environmental non-pathogenic type. Further assessment of risk of using T101-test positive milk as feed is therefore considered unnecessary.

6.4.6 Cryptosporidiosis

Cryptosporidiosis is caused by unicellular protozoans belonging to the genus *Cryptosporidium*. The most important species is *C. parvum*, and especially its genotype 2 is known to infect or cause enteritis in all domestic mammals. Young animals are especially susceptible. Reported occurrences among calves with diarrhoea range between 5 and 24% of the examined animals (MMM 2000b). An estimate of 6.5% for population prevalence was obtained from a study of 186 asymptomatic calves (MMM 2000b). All bovine breeds are susceptible. There are no data on seasonal fluctuations, but since water is an important vehicle it is possible that prevalence is higher during the summer months.

Adult lactating cows can contract the *C. parvum* infection, and carry and secrete the organism for a limited period. However, *C. muris* may persist in the abomasum for several months. The organism is not secreted into milk, but milk can conceivably be contaminated via the skin of udder and teats. There are no reports of milk contaminated with cryptosporidial oocysts, but this may reflect diagnostic inadequacy.

Conclusion: Since *Cryptosporidiae* are not secreted into milk, further assessment of the risk of using T101-test positive milk as feed is unnecessary.

6.4.7 Toxoplasmosis

Toxoplasmosis is caused by a eucoccidian sporozoa, *Toxoplasma gondii*. The sexual life cycle of the organism takes place only in *Felidae* but the asexual stages can take place in most mammals, including cattle. Toxoplasmosis can induce abortion in sheep and goats, though very rarely in cattle. There is no known breed predisposition or seasonal variation. In 2002, toxoplasmosis was diagnosed in 7 wild hares and 2 domestic cats, but in no other domestic animals (MMM 2003b). It is conceivable that cattle can be exposed to oocysts in cat faeces on farm premises but this route of infection is most likely highly sporadic.

Tachyzoites of the organism have (very rarely) been demonstrated in the milk of affected animals. However, detection requires special methods and expertise.

Conclusion: Since infection in dairy cattle is most likely rare and there are no reports of raw milk serving as a vehicle for toxoplasma infection, the hazard connected to the use of T101-test positive milk as feed is considered insignificant.

6.5 Risk management options

This section discusses two main options to reduce the levels of microbial contamination in raw milk used in feed mixtures: controlling pH or temperature. The option of using residue-degrading enzyme preparations is not elaborated further since these enzymes most likely have no effect on the survival of microbes. This discussion is limited to thermophilic campylobacters, enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) and *Listeria monocytogenes*, since these were thought to pose potential hazards in connection with the use of T101-test positive milk as feed.

6.5.1 Effect of controlling the pH

The normal, near neutral pH of milk does not limit the growth of campylobacters, coliformic organisms or listeria. However, adjusting the pH of the feed mixture to the optimal level (4–5) does reduce the level of campylobacters and to some extent also of listeria. The survival of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* was < 2h at pH 4 (Chaveerach et al. 2003). The mean reduction in populations of *L. monocytogenes* after 6 h was 4.76 log CFU/ml at pH 3.5 (Koutsoumanis. and Sofos 2004). Enterohemorrhagic *E.*

coli is more acid tolerant than non-pathogenic commensal *E. coli* types and survives lengthy periods, up to 2 months at a pH of 4.5 (Doyle et al. 1997).

6.5.2 Effect of heat treatment

At 55°C the decimal reduction time (D-value) of campylobacters is ca. 1 min and of coliforms ca. 6 min in milk. The D value for *L. monocytogenes* in milk is max 0.58 min at 63.3°C (USDA 2000).

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Annexes

Annex 1: Antimicrobial drugs tested at EELA

Table 14.

Proportion of the antimicrobial drugs tested at EELA (results were used in this exposure assessment) (EELA 2003a).

Antimicrobials tested at EELA	Number of tests/ number of samples	Test % n=22 samples	Number of positives/ number of tests	Positive results % out of tested
Benzylopenicillin	22/22	100	21/22	95.5
Cephalexin	22/22	100	0/22	0
Oxacillin	22/22	100	0/22	0
Cloxacillin	22/22	100	1/22	5.0
Amoxicillin	21/22	95	0/21	0
Ampicillin	21/22	95	1/21	4.8
Dihydrostreptomycin	11/22	50	0/11	0
Streptomycin	10/22	45	5/10	50.0
Ciprofloxacin	10/22	45	0/10	0
Enrofloxacin	10/22	45	0/10	0
Danofloxacin	9/22	40	0/9	0
Oxytetracycline	6/22	27	0/6	0
Sulphadiazine	6/22	27	0/6	0
Sulphadimidine	3/22	14	0/3	0
Sulphadoxine	6/22	27	0/6	0
Sulphametazine	3/22	14	0/3	0
Chlortetracycline	2/22	9	0/2	0
Tetracycline	2/22	9	0/2	0
Framycetin	0/22	0	0/0	0
Neomycin	0/22	0	0/0	0
Pirlimycin	0/22	0	0/0	0
Spiramycin	0/22	0	0/0	0
Trimethoprim	0/22	0	0/0	0
Novobiocin	0/22	0	0/0	0

Annex 2: Toxicological profiles of antimicrobials

β -Lactam antibacterials

Benzylpenicillins

Penicillins have low toxicity. The most common side-effects are hypersensitivity reactions. The therapeutic index is more than 100 and toxic effect has only been seen at extremely high doses. No teratogenic effects have been seen (EMEA 2003).

Benzylpenicillin

Penicillins have been shown to cross the placenta; however, no teratogenic problems have been associated with the use of benzylpenicillin during pregnancy in studies on the mouse, rabbit and rat (EMEA 2003).

Safety evaluations of benzylpenicillin residues in food commodities need to take into account allergies. Because no adequate experimental data were available to establish a NOEL for allergic effects, human clinical data were used for estimating a safe level. No evidence was found of sensitization in humans caused by benzylpenicillin residues in food. It was therefore decided to base a safe level in food commodities on the ability of benzylpenicillin to provoke an allergic reaction in already sensitized humans (EMEA 2003).

According to the Codex Alimentarius Commission, residues of benzylpenicillin should be kept below 30 μg penicillin/person/day (human) (Codex Alimentarius 2004). If the ADI-value is calculated as a proportion of body weight, the acceptable daily intake is 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day.

Gastric absorption of benzylpenicillin is poor in many species because it is rapidly hydrolyzed in the acid environment of the stomach. Generally, only 15–30% of benzylpenicillin is absorbed by the oral route in fasted animals and that amount decreases when there is food in the stomach (USP DI 2003).

According to Mussen & Anderson (2001), the bioavailability of orally-administrated sodium benzylpenicillin in 5- and 1-week-old calves is 7 to 10%, respectively.

Penethamate

The toxicity of penethamate hydriodide to laboratory animals is low (EMEA 2003).

Diethylaminoethanol, which is released by hydrolysis of penethamate, is of low acute oral toxicity. The toxicological risk from the small amount of diethylaminoethanol released by hydrolysis of penethamate is unlikely to appear. Antimicrobial activity of penethamate is exclusively related to benzylpenicillin, which is released by hydrolysis of penethamate (EMEA 2003).

Antistaphylococcal isoxazolyl penicillins

Cloxacillin

Prolonged dose studies at high doses in rats and dogs showed no haematological, biochemical or histological abnormalities (Brander 1996).

According to the Department of Health and Ageing of the Australian Government, the ADI-value for cloxacillin is 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day. The established NOEL-value in animal experimental data was 500 mg/kg bw/day (Australian Government 2003). An ADI-value was not established by the JECFA.

No data about the oral bioavailability of cloxacillin in pigs was found. However, the bioavailability for humans was estimated to be 30–80% (TOXNET 2004a).

Broad-spectrum penicillins

Ampicillin

Ampicillin is considered to be more toxic taken by the oral rather than by the subcutaneous route based on a hamster study. Tolerance is developed to multiple dosing. Ampicillin is considered non-carcinogenic for humans. However, there is limited evidence of carcinogenicity in experimental animals (TOXNET 2004b).

An ADI-value was not established by the JECFA. However, according to the Department of Health and Ageing of the Australian Government, the NOEL-value for amoxicillin in animal experimental data was 200 mg/kg bw/day. By using a safety value of 1000, the ADI-value of 200 µg/kg/day for amoxicillin was established (Australian Government 2003).

Ampicillin is closely related to amoxicillin. Due to a lack of data, the ADI-value of ampicillin was assumed to be equal to the ADI-value of amoxicillin as determined by the Australian Government.

Aminopenicillins are stable in gastric fluid. The effect of milk on oral bioavailability was studied by Palmer et al. Ampicillin absorption is slightly less if antibiotics are given orally with milk rather than with water (Palmer et al. 1983).

No data about the oral bioavailability of ampicillin in pigs was found. However, the bioavailability for humans was estimated to be less than 55% (MacGregor & Granziani 1997). Oral bioavailability for calves fed with milk was 4.5% (Ziv et al. 1977).

Cephalosporins

Cephalexin

Cephalexin is relatively non-toxic and less likely to cause allergic reactions than penicillins. (Bishop 1996). Local reactions account for the majority of adverse reactions, and are usually mild. Hypersensitivity reactions have been reported in people, but appear to be uncommon in domestic animals (Vaden & Riviere 2001).

Cephalexin is not teratogenic and is not considered to be mutagenic or carcinogenic. No evidence for immunological effects has been found in repeated dose toxicity studies (EMEA 2003).

The toxicological ADI-value of 500 µg/kg bw is based on a teratogenicity experiment in mice using the safety factor of 200. The microbiological ADI is 54.4 µg/kg bw, which is lower than the toxicological ADI (EMEA 2003).

No data about the oral bioavailability of cephalexin in pigs was found. However, the bioavailability for humans was estimated to be close to 100% (MacGregor & Granziani 1997). The oral bioavailability of cephalexin for calves was 29% of the administered dose (Soback et al. 1987).

Aminoglycosides

Streptomycin and dihydrostreptomycin

Streptomycin and dihydrostreptomycin are closely related in structure and their toxicological profiles are similar.

No teratogenic effects have been seen related to these two substances and no adverse effects on reproduction have been reported (EMEA 2003)

Toxicity after oral administration of streptomycin and dihydrostreptomycin is low to rodents. The toxicological ADI (25 µg/kg bw) is derived from a two year rat study using the safety factor of 200 on the observed NOEL of 5 mg/kg bw/day. The toxicological ADI is lower than the established microbiological ADI (120 µg/kg bw) (EMEA 2003).

Neomycin and framycetin

Neomycin and framycetin are closely related drugs, framycetin consisting largely of one of the compounds in neomycin. Ototoxicity has been observed after intramuscular and subcutaneous administration in pigs, but not following oral dosing.

Neomycin is unlikely to be genotoxic and no evidence about teratogenicity exists. No adverse effects on reproductive function have been recorded (EMEA 2003).

Neomycin has a low acute toxicity. Based on a NOEL for ototoxicity in guinea pigs of 6.0 mg/kg bw, a toxicological ADI of 60 µg/kg bw/day was established using a safety factor of 100. This ADI is lower than the microbiological ADI of 160 µg/kg bw/day (EMEA 2003).

Neomycin and framycetin are poorly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract of humans (less than 10%) and animals. Calves dosed orally showed low bioavailability. The absorption was minimal, 1–11% and about 90% was recovered in faeces. However, there can be a significant difference in absorption of neomycin in young calves versus older animals (EMEA 2003).

According to Pedersoli et al. (1994), the bioavailability of neomycin after repeated oral administration for calves was as low as $0.45 \pm 0.45\%$.

Aminoglycosides are highly polar cations and are poorly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Less than 1% of the dose is absorbed following oral administration. The drugs are not inactivated in the intestine and are eliminated in faeces. Long term oral administration may result in accumulation of the aminoglycosides to toxic concentrations (TOXNET 2004c).

Others

Novobiocin does not have the potential to affect fertility or intrauterine development and no mutagenic effects have been observed. Novobiocin is not carcinogenic in rats (EMEA 2003).

The toxicological ADI is 2 µg/kg bw/day, based on a 3-generation rat study. The NOEL in that study was 2 mg/kg bw/day and a safety factor of 100 was used. The microbiological ADI was lower (1.25 µg/kg bw/day) than the toxicological ADI of 20 µg/kg bw/day (EMEA 2003).

Novobiocin is stable under acidic conditions and is rapidly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Oral bioavailability in laboratory animals is around 30% (EMEA 2003).

Annex 3: Laboratory data and results of EELA survey

Table 15. Chemical analysis carried out as assignments and results of the EELA survey (EELA 2003a; EELA 2003b)

Case	Detected Substance	Test at arrival		Farm tank		Transporter tank		Silo		Dilution factor	Added component	Test at departure		Usage	
		Snap	T101	µg/l	l	µg/l	l	µg/l	l			Snap	T101		
1	Benz.pen Streptom.	X	X			29 50	4,349 4,349				rinse milk whey				
2	Benz.pen		X			65									
3	Benz.pen		X			4.2									
4	Benz.pen Streptom.	X	X			10 20	13,100 13,100	2.1 4.2	31,200 31,200	4.8 4.8	whey	X		feed feed	
4	Benz.pen Streptom.							3.3 6.6	19,900 19,900	3.0 3.0	whey	X		fertilizer fertilizer	
5	Benz.pen	X	X			6	6,570	1.0	27,070	4.1	whey	X	X	feed	
6	Benz.pen		X			6	14,000	2.0	42,000	3.0	whey			feed	
7	Benz.pen Streptom.	X	X			9 20	4,000 4,000							dumbed dumbed	
8	Benz.pen		X			24			78,536		sour milk			feed	
9	Benz.pen	X	X			14	6,000	2.0	42,000	7.0	whey		X	feed	
10	Benz.pen	X	X	216	512	17	6,500	2.8	40,000	6.2	whey			feed	
11	Benz.pen	X	X	61	500	6	5,000								
12	Benz.pen	X	X	99	600	7.7	7,693	3.0	19,693	2.6	rinse milk		X	feed	
13	Benz.pen Streptom.		X	164 270	500 500	3 5	27,162 27,162	0.9 1.6	87,188 87,188	3.2 3.2	raw milk		X	feed feed	
14	Ampicillin Cloksacil.	X	X	5.5 28	80 80	0.06 0.32	7,000 7,000	0.0 0.0	100,000 100,000	14.3 14.3	raw milk			humans humans	
15	Benz.pen	X	X	105	415	6	7,245	3.5	12,445	1.7	rinse milk		X	feed	
		71% 100%										17%	28%		
All cases		Average Stdev		398.4 202.7			9,661 7,306		49,221 31,817	5.4 4.0				Usage feed fertilizer dumbed humans not known	% 61 6 6 6 22
Benzylpenicillin		Average Stdev		129.0 61.0		14.8 16.4		2.3 0.9							
Streptomycin		Average Stdev				23.8 18.9		2.9 2.5							

Value calculated, not measured

Annex 4: Results of the NFA survey

Table 16.

Dilution factors of rejected raw milk and its use. Survey made by NFA (NFA 2003b).

Dairy operator	Volume of rejected milk (l)	Volume of diluted milk (l)	Dilution factor	Usage
1	12,985	165,677	12.8	feed
1	9,941	49,733	5.0	feed
2	15,450	43,450	2.8	feed
3	5,400	25,000	4.6	feed
3	3,000	26,000	8.7	feed
3	4,300	25,000	5.8	feed
3	5,200	26,000	5.0	feed
3	4,470	25,000	5.6	feed
3	5,400	26,000	4.8	feed
4	25,651	45,339	1.8	feed
4	19,276	49,000	2.5	feed
4	18,830	43,888	2.3	feed
4	24,492	35,900	1.5	feed
5	12,918	52,000	4.0	feed
5	14,000	52,000	3.7	feed
5	22,018	49,900	2.3	feed
5	2,000	12,000	6.0	feed
5	10,506	80,900	7.7	feed
5	4,600	28,000	6.1	feed
5	17,103	62,500	3.7	feed
5	11,705	56,700	4.8	feed
5	22,029	55,000	2.5	feed
5	11,980	44,440	3.7	feed
6	12,579	26,179	2.1	feed
6	4,612	22,612	4.9	feed
6	11,468	27,268	2.4	feed
6	7,525	27,425	3.6	feed
6	7,693	19,693	2.6	feed
6	7,245	12,445	1.7	feed
6	13,732	37,732	2.7	feed
6	6,675	20,675	3.1	feed
6	4,450	10,450	2.3	feed
6	11,187	34,187	3.1	feed
6	10,423	17,823	1.7	feed
6	4,320	35,520	8.2	feed
6	3,794	7,794	2.1	feed
6	5,183	60,183	11.6	feed
7	4,578	26,778	5.8	feed
7	6,570	27,070	4.1	feed
8	6,500	31,200	4.8	feed
8	6,600	39,900	6.0	feed
9	7,640	7,640	1.0	feed
10	7,548	16,800	2.2	feed
11	16,893*			discharged
11	16,893*			discharged
11	16,893*			discharged
11	16,893*			discharged
11	16,893*			discharged
11	16,893*			discharged
11	16,893*			discharged
11	16,893*			discharged
12				not known

Volume of Dairy operator	Volume of rejected milk (l)	diluted milk (l)	Dilution factor	Usage
13				not known
14				not known
15				not known
15				not known
16				not known
16				not known
16				not known
Average	10,083	36,949	4.3	
Min	2,000	7,640	1	
Max	25,651	165,677	12.8	

Dilution at the dairy plant 21/37
No Dilution 6/37
Dilution in a feed truck 10/37
*average of 8 cases

Annex 5: Pig farms receiving rejected raw milk

Table 17.

Profiles of the farms receiving rejected milk based on the KTTK survey (KTTK 2004a)

Farm	No. of pigs	No. of sows	Acidification	Date	Amount received (l)	Total No. of loads	No. of days between deliveries
1			Yes	11.2.2002	45,339	4	
				13.9.2002	49,000		214
				22.12.2002	43,880		100
				17.9.2003	35,900		269
2	1,800			4.7.2002	3,000	3	
				10.11.2002	5,200		129
				28.10.2003	5,400		352
3	1,400			8.1.2002	4,300	3	
				2.7.2002	5,400		175
				22.5.2003	4,470		324
4	1,200		Yes	19.4.2002	3,900	4	
				15.9.2002	40,000		149
				16.7.2003	9,200		304
				13.10.2003	11,640		89
5	1,000		No	4.2.2002	15,000	7	
				19.4.2002	21,400		74
				12.7.2002	49,900		86
				14.7.2002	12,000		2
				15.7.2002	23,500		1
				8.8.2002	34,950		24
13.10.2003	7,800	66					
6	1,400		Yes	4.2.2002	10,000	5	
				19.4.2002	11,000		74
				15.7.2002	32,400		87
				8.8.2002	18,350		24
				13.10.2003	25,000		66
7	1,000		Yes	16.3.2003	11,300	1	
8	1,400		No	16.1.2002	54,500	2	
				6.7.2002	8,200		171
9	1,450		Yes/no	1.8.2002	28,000	2	
				22.11.2002	26,000		113
10	Exported			6.6.2003	18,000	2	
				31.7.2003	18,000		55
11	Exported			6.6.2003	20,000	2	
				31.7.2003	22,000		55
12	Exported			29.7.2003	55,000	2	
				31.7.2003	23,000		2
13	600		Yes	13.3.2002	15,000	3	
				22.7.2002	6,000		131
				18.2.2003	11,000		211
14	400		Yes	13.3.2002	10,000	1	
15	1,000		No	13.3.2002	25,000	6	
				13.3.2002	10,000		0
				4.7.2002	14,000		113
				6.7.2002	15,000		2
				27.12.2002	10,000		174
				18.2.2003	10,000		53

Farm	No. of pigs	No. of sows	Acidification	Date	Amount received (l)	Total No. of loads	No. of days between deliveries
16	650	100	Yes	13.3.2002	11,000	5	115 16 211 127
				6.7.2002	15,000		
				22.7.2002	9,000		
				18.2.2003	10,000		
				25.6.2003	12,000		
17	1,000	200	Yes	13.3.2002	12,000	1	
18	700	60	No	13.3.2002	12,000	1	
19	500	100	Yes	13.3.2002	6,000	5	113 2 16 338
				4.7.2002	7,000		
				6.7.2002	9,000		
				22.7.2002	6,000		
				25.6.2003	6,000		
20	700	100	Yes	22.7.2002	7,000	1	
21	700	120	Yes	27.2.2003	11,000	1	
22	1,400		Yes	28.8.2002	4,000	2	264
				19.5.2003	4,000		
23	450		No	31.7.2003	13,000	1	
24	800	800	No	16.3.2003	15,100	1	
25	800		Yes	13.3.2002	10,000	3	342 90
				18.2.2003	7,000		
				19.5.2003	7,000		
26	1,000		No	28.8.2002	7,000	1	
27	500		Yes	13.3.2002	10,000	4	168 121 62
				28.8.2002	9,000		
				27.12.2002	3,000		
				27.2.2003	10,000		
28	150		No	25.6.2003	5,000	1	
29	600	100	No	4.7.2002	7,000	2	12
				16.7.2002	11,000		
30	260		Yes	13.3.2002	5,000	1	
Average	879	198	Yes 50%		15,559	2,6	121,0
Min	150	60			3,000	1	0
Max	1,800	800			55,000	7	352

Annex 6: The effects of heating and controlling pH on antimicrobial degradation

Effect of heating

Penicillin degradation

The stability of a benzylpenicillin solution in water was studied by Rose et al. (1997). Benzylpenicillin was found to be stable at 65°C but not at higher temperatures. The half-life at 100°C in water was approximately 60 minutes. When heating benzylpenicillin in oil up to 140 and 180°C, the half-lives were 45 and 20 minutes, respectively, indicating that benzylpenicillin is less stable in an aqueous than in a lipid environment. Degradation is caused by acid- or base-catalysed hydrolysis, and the likely products from heating benzylpenicillin are benzylpenillic acid, isomers of benzylpenicilloic acid and penicillenilic acid (DaPaolis et al. 1977).

Degradation of penicillin G in milk by heating has been investigated by several studies, which showed that milk had a marked protective effect on penicillin G relative to heating in water (Moats 1999). Heating at 100°C for 30, 60 and 90 minutes reduced benzylpenicillin 20–40%, 50–65% and 85–100%, respectively (Konecny 1978; Pilet et al. 1969). Lower temperatures had only a small reduction effect on benzylpenicillin. Shanani et al. report 8% and 10% reduction in 30 and 15 minutes heating at 62 and 71 °C, respectively (Shanani et al. 1956).

Reduction of 100% of benzylpenicillin was obtained with temperatures of 71°C (28 h), 87°C (7 h), 93°C (4 h) and 121°C (25 min) (Shanani et al. 1956).

Aminoglycoside degradation

The heat stability of framycetin, neomycin and streptomycin was studied in milk. 100% reduction was obtained only at high temperatures for prolonged periods.

Streptomycin was reduced 100% only by heating at 71°C for 22 hours; a temperature of 100°C for 30 minutes was sufficient to reduce 42% of the substance.

Up to 100% reduction of neomycin was observed at 100°C for 3–5 hours. Less than 35% was reduced in temperatures under 100°C if the time was no more than 30 minutes.

Up to 100% reduction of framycetin at 100°C was observed within 2 hours. One hour at 100°C was sufficient to reduce the amount 85% (Moats 1988).

Table 18.

The effect of heating on the degradation of antimicrobial drug residues.

Active substance	Temp (°C)	Time (min)	Degradation (%)	Reference
Amoxicillin				nd
Ampicillin				nd
Benzylpenicillin	71	15	10	Shanani et al. (1956)
	71	1,705	100	Shanani (1958)
	87	420	100	Shanani (1958)
	93	230	100	Shanani (1958)
	100	90	85–100	Pilet et al. (1969)
	100	10	10	Konecny (1978)
	121	25	100	Shanani (1958)
Cephalexin				nd
Cloxacillin				nd
Danofloxacin				nd
Enrofloxacin				nd
Framycetin	100	60	85	Pilet et al. (1969)
	100	120	100	
	120	20	75	
Dihydrostreptomycin				nd
Streptomycin	70	30	8	Konecny (1978)
	71	1,320	100	Shanani (1958)
	100	30	42	Konecny (1978)
Neomycin	70	20	9	Konecny (1978)
	100	300	100	Pilet et al. (1969)
	120	20	15–50	
Tetracycline	100	60	100	Pilet et al. (1969)
Oxytetracycline	71	190	100	Shanani (1958)
	100	60	100	Pilet et al. (1969)
Pirlimycin				nd
Spiramycin	100	180	50	Pilet et al. (1969)
	120	20	0–20	
Sulphadiazine				nd
Sulphadoxine				nd
Trimethoprim				nd
Novobiocin				nd

nd = no data available

Effect of acidification

Most substances are studied in relation to stability at storage or in conditions similar to the human stomach. We found only incomplete data on stability and degradation kinetics in conditions reflecting the conditions in feed.

Penicillin degradation

Hydrolysis is the main cause of penicillin degradation (Vaden & Riviere 2001). Benzylpenicillin was found to be most stable at pH 6.5 (Finholt et al. 1965).

Penicillin degradation was studied by Blaha et al. (1976). At pH 2.70 (37°C) five degradation products were detected as penicillin completely degraded, indicating a

half-life of 30 minutes. Benzylpenicillenic acid was the first degradation product occurring in solution, but this quickly degraded into benzylpenillic acid, benzylpenamaldic acid, benzylpenilloic acid and penicillamine, which were still present after 48 hours. An increase in temperature and buffer concentration had a direct effect on degradation profiles, accelerating penicillin degradation.

In a citrate buffer at pH 1.8, benzylpenicillin was found at 20°C and 37°C to have a half-life of 20 and 3 minutes, respectively. Under acidic conditions similar to the human stomach at 37°C, benzylpenicillin was found to have a half-life of 2 minutes (Dušinský & Antolík 1969).

Ampicillin degradation

The degradation of ampicillin shows first-order kinetics at a constant temperature, pH and total ionic strength. The minimum rate of degradation was observed in the pH range of 4.5–5.7, the isoelectric point of ampicillin where the molecule is in its most stable form.

The degradation constant increases as a function of both a decrease and increase of pH outside the isoelectric point range. At a temperature of 35°C the degradation half-life is approximately 50 hours at pH 3.9, and is reduced to 7–8 hours at pH 1.2.

An increase above the isoelectric point also shows increased degradation rates. The half-life of ampicillin at pH 6.9 is approximately 28 hours. In basic solutions the hydrolytic rate of ampicillin is almost 1400 times faster than in acid solutions. Evidently, the β -lactam ring of ampicillin is extremely susceptible to nucleophilic attack initiated by a hydroxyl ion.

Ampicillin is about 200 times more acid-stable than penicillin G (Hou & Poole 1969).

Cephalosporin degradation

According to Yamana and Tsuji it is expected that the degradation of deacetoxycephalosporins, such as cephalexin, occurs only at the β -lactam moiety. Acidic degradation of cephalexin at 35°C was pH-independent even in strong acid solutions and the molecule is fairly acid stable. Cephalexin is about 25 times more stable than the other cephalosporins and approximately 180 times more stable than ampicillin at pH 1.0 (Yamana & Tsuji 1976).

Cephalexin degradation at 60°C showed pseudo-first-order kinetics according to Rattie et al. (1978). The half-lives increased as the pH was increased from pH 4 to 7. pH independent ranges were observed between 4–6 and 8–9. The half-life of cephalexin (60°C) at pH 7 was approximately 2 hours and at pH 4 approximately 15 hours.

Cloxacillin degradation

Cloxacillin degradation at 25°C was determined by Landersjö et al. (1974). Degradation followed first-order kinetics and had maximum stability at pH 6.3, corresponding to a $t_{10\%}$ of about 12 days. In the pH range of 4.4–8.2, the $t_{10\%}$ value exceeds 48 hours. In the pH-ranges under 4.0, 3.6 and 3.2, the $t_{10\%}$ -value is less than 24, 12 and 6 hours, respectively. For pH-ranges above 8.6, 9.0 and 9.4, the $t_{10\%}$ value is less than 24, 12 and 6 hours, respectively.

The half-life of cloxacillin at pH 1.0, 1.3 and 1.5 was 10, 23 and 33 minutes, respectively (Bundgaard & Ilver 1970).

Table 19.
Summary of the effect of pH on antimicrobial drug residues.

Active substance	pH	Temp (°C)	t _{1/2} (h)	t _{1/10} (h)	Most stable pH range	Reference
Amoxicillin	4	37	177		4–7	Erah et al. (1995) Charda et al. (2003)
	4–5	30	270–350			
	1	30	8.5			
Ampicillin	3.9	35	50		4.5–5.7	Hou & Poole (1969)
	1.2	35	8			
Benzylpenicillin	2.7	37	0.5		6.5	Blaha et al.(1976) Finholt et al. (1965) Dušinský & Antolík (1969)
	1.8	20	0.3			
Cephalexin	1	35	25		4–6	Yamana & Tsuji (1976) Rattie et al. (1978)
	4	60	15			
Cloxacillin	1.5	35	0.5		6.3	Bundgaard & Ilver (1970)
Tetracycline	4	60		0.75	3	Vej-Hansen & Bundgaard (1978)
Oxytetracycline	4	25		19	2	Vej-Hansen et al. (1978)
	4	60		0.7		
Danofloxacin						nd
Enrofloxacin						nd
Framycetin						nd
Dihydrostreptomycin						nd
Streptomycin						nd
Neomycin						nd
Pirlimycin						nd
Spiramycin						nd
Sulphadiazine						nd
Sulphadoxine						nd
Trimethoprim						nd
Novobiocin						nd

nd = no data available

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Vuonna 2002 ja 2003 tässä sarjassa julkaistuja

01/2002

Kalaterveyspäivä 13.3.2002

Luentokokoelma

02/2002

Kotimaisten kevytjuustojen laatututkimus

Loppuraportti 12.3.2002

03/2002: Mari Eskola

Study on Trichothecenes, Zearalenone and Ochratoxin A in Finnish Cereals: Occurrence and Analytical Techniques

Väitöskirja

04/2002

Riskinarviointi Echinococcus granulosus -loisesta Suomessa

Riskinarviointiraportti

05/2002: Meri Kokkonen

Automatisoidun näytteenkäsittelymenetelmän kehittäminen ja käyttöönotto okratoksiini A:n ja zearalenonin määrittämisessä

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